

**Reimagining
Communication
in the 21st Century:
Sociological,
Political & Economic
Perspectives**

**BOOK OF
ABSTRACTS**

Two- Day International Conference
on
**Reimagining Communication in the 21st Century :
Sociological, Political and Economic Perspectives**

20th & 21st March, 2025

Book of Abstract

Editors

Venugopal Gowda M K, Ph.D.

Vagdevi H S, Ph.D.

Convenors – ICRC-2025

St. Philomena's College

Post Graduate Department of
Studies & Research in Journalism & Mass Communication
Bannimantap
Mysuru, Karnataka, India

© St. Philomena's College, Post Graduate Department of Studies & Research in Journalism & Mass Communication, Bannimantap, Mysuru, Karnataka, India

ISBN: 978-93-342-4858-6

Published By: St Philomena's College

Editors:

Venugopal Gowda M. K., Ph.D.

Vagdevi H S, Ph.D.

Editorial Support

Mr. Raviraj I Vadigeri, HoD, B.VoC, Media & Entertainment

Mr. Ravithej S P, Asst. Prof, Post Graduate Department of Studies & Research in Journalism & Mass Communication

Mr. Sanju T S, Asst. Prof, Post Graduate Department of Studies & Research in Journalism & Mass Communication

Ms. Vaishnavi S Patil, M A Student, Post Graduate Department of Studies & Research in Journalism & Mass Communication

Cover Design:

Mr. Sanju T S, Asst. Prof, Post Graduate Department of Studies & Research in Journalism & Mass Communication

Find us :

 - <https://www.linkedin.com/in/international-conference-icrc-a2366a350/>

Contact

Post Graduate Department of Studies & Research in Journalism & Mass Communication

St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Bannimantap, Mysuru, Karnataka, India

Phone 0821-4240900 / 4240912 / 4240918

Fax 0821-4240950

Email : stphilos1946@gmail.com / pgjournalism@stphilos.ac.in

Contents

	Page No.
Forewords	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Rev. Fr. Lourdu Prasad Joseph, Rector, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Bannimantap, Mysuru, Karnataka, India• Dr. Ravi J D Saldanha, Principal, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Bannimantap, Mysuru, Karnataka, India	
Convenors' Note	
Conference Schedule	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Inauguration• Panel Session Details	
Key Note Address	1
Panellists Abstracts	2
Technical Session Details	35
Research Paper Abstracts	48
Annexure	119
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• List of Organising Committee Members	

Rector's Message

It is with great joy and pride that I welcome you all to St. Philomena's College, a historic institution that has stood as a pillar of academic excellence and inclusivity since 1946. Over the decades, we have blended tradition with innovation, embracing the motto *Caritas in Scientia*— Service through Knowledge. Today, we take immense pride in fostering a diverse and dynamic learning community that welcomes students from all corners of the world.

Rev. Fr. Lourdu Prasad Joseph
Rector, St. Philomena's College
(Autonomous)
Bannimantap, Mysuru,
Karnataka, India

As you step into our vibrant campus for the international conference *Reimagining Communication in the 21st Century: Sociological, Political, and Economic Perspectives*, you are not just attending an academic event—you are becoming part of a collective effort to address some of the most pressing communication challenges of our time. In an era shaped by digital transformations, misinformation, media ethics, political polarization, artificial intelligence, and financial fraud, we need more than just conversations; we need action, collaboration, and innovative thinking. This conference serves as a platform for scholars, media professionals, policymakers, and thought leaders to exchange ideas, spark new perspectives, and create meaningful solutions.

And what could be a more fitting venue for this exchange than St. Philomena's College in Mysuru; where a historic institution thrives within a heritage city! With its rich cultural legacy, intellectual vibrancy, and timeless charm, Mysuru offers a perfect setting for insightful discussions and inspiring interactions. We hope that beyond the academic rigour, you also take time to soak in the beauty, history, and warmth of this city.

We are truly honoured to have you here with us. Beyond gaining knowledge and forging meaningful connections, we hope this experience ignites a renewed passion for the power of communication in shaping a better world. May you take away valuable insights, lasting collaborations, and, above all, fond memories of your time at St. Philomena's College and Mysuru.

Wishing you all an enriching, inspiring, and unforgettable experience!

Principal's Message

Dear Friends and Esteemed Delegates,

It is truly a joy to welcome you all to St. Philomena's College and to the vibrant city of Mysuru for this important international conference on “Reimagining Communication in the 21st Century: Sociological, Political, and Economic Perspectives”.

At St. Philomena's, we have always believed that education is not just about classrooms and books but it is also about bringing people together, sharing knowledge, and creating spaces where ideas can flourish. That is why hosting this conference means so much to us. In a world where communication can build bridges or walls, spark unity or division, we need conversations that matter — conversations like the ones we are about to have over the next few days.

This gathering is special because it brings diverse voices to a common platform be it scholars, thinkers, media practitioners, and changemakers who are all committed to understanding and addressing the complex realities of communication in today's world. Whether it's navigating misinformation, technology's impact, media ethics, or political and economic divides, I believe that your ideas, experiences, and reflections will pave the way for meaningful solutions.

As you immerse yourselves in the conference, I also hope you will take a moment to experience the unique spirit of Mysuru — a city that is as much about intellectual energy as it is about heritage and hospitality. From its rich cultural traditions to its warm people, Mysuru has a way of making every visitor feel at home.

On behalf of our students, faculty, and staff, I want to express our joy in welcoming you and our eagerness to share this enriching experience with you. May this conference leave you not only with new knowledge and collaborations, but also with lasting memories of friendship, inspiration, and the joy of shared purpose.

Dr. Ravi J D Saldanha
Principal,
St. Philomena's College (Autonomous),
Bannimantap, Mysuru,
Karnataka, India

Convenors' Note

Dr. Venugopal Gowda M. K.
HoD, Post Graduate Department
of Studies & Research in
Journalism & Mass Communication

In an era where communication continuously reshapes the contours of society, politics, and the economy, it is imperative to engage in scholarly discourse that critically examines these transformations. The International Conference on “Reimagining Communication in the 21st Century: Sociological, Political, and Economic Perspectives” seeks to foster meaningful academic engagement, bringing together scholars, researchers, media professionals, and industry experts from across the globe.

Dr. Vagdevi H. S.
Asst. Prof. Post Graduate Department
of Studies & Research in
Journalism & Mass Communication

The PG Department of Studies and Research in Mass Communication and Journalism, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Mysuru, has taken a significant step towards advancing academic inquiry by organizing this prestigious international conference. When we first conceptualized this herculean task of organizing an international conference, we were driven by excitement and hope. However, as we ventured further into the planning process, the realities of a post-COVID world and the dominance of hybrid conferences posed significant challenges. We were apprehensive about whether we could bring together enough participants in person and whether we could gather a diverse panel of speakers. Yet, with the unwavering support of St. Philomena's College and the relentless efforts of our students and colleagues, we are proud to share that we received 155 abstracts, out of which 112 participants registered for paper presentations in person, and together paper presenters and attendees we have a total of 150 registrations — a testament to our collective dedication and the relevance of the conference theme.

This conference offers a crucial platform for interdisciplinary engagement. The conference examines key sociological themes such as cultural hybridization, vernacular media, gender representation, and AI-driven narratives. It also addresses political concerns around media's role in elections, cybersecurity, and democracy, alongside ethical challenges of misinformation and algorithmic bias. Economically, it highlights how media shapes digital inclusion, financial literacy, the gig economy, and consumer behaviour, redefining global economic dynamics.

The integration of artificial intelligence and social media has not only redefined the way information is disseminated but also raised profound questions about truth, agency, and digital ethics. While AI-driven innovations have enhanced accessibility, data-driven governance, and information retrieval, they have also amplified challenges such as misinformation, deep fakes, and algorithmic biases. Similarly, social media's dual role as an enabler of grassroots activism and a vehicle for political propaganda calls for a nuanced scholarly examination of its implications.

We express our sincere gratitude to St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Mysuru, for its unwavering support in organizing this prestigious event. We also extend our heartfelt gratitude to the distinguished resource persons, scholars, and industry experts from across the world whose insights and expertise enrich this discourse. Their invaluable contributions will not only elevate the academic rigor of this conference but also pave the way for meaningful research and policy initiatives in the field of communication. Not to forget our students, our pillar of support - a heartfelt gratitude.

We came together to reimagine 21st-century communication — engaging in meaningful dialogue, exploring pioneering research, and exchanging ideas that will shape future academic and industry practices. This dialogue will continue, fostering new insights and collaborations for the future.

Invitation

St. Philomena's College (Autonomous)

Bannimantap, Mysuru, Karnataka

**PG Department of Studies & Research in
Journalism & Mass Communication**

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

on

**REIMAGINING COMMUNICATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY :
SOCIOLOGICAL, POLITICAL, AND ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVES**

Inauguration

Chief Guest

Dr. D.V. Guruprasad

*Former Director General of Police &
Former Director of Information Department, Karnataka*

Key Note Address

Prof. Srinivas Melkote

*Professor Emeritus
Bowling Green State University, USA*

Presided By

Most. Rev. Dr. Bernard Moras

*Apostolic Administrator
President - MDES*

Presence

Rev. Dr. Lourdu Prasad Joseph

Rector

Dr. Ravi J.D. Saldanha

Principal

ALL ARE WELCOME!

Date
20-03-2025

Venue
Indoor Stadium

Time
10:00 am

Schedule of the Two-Day International Conference

Day One: Thursday 20, March, 2025

Time	Event
8:00 AM – 8:30 AM	Assembly & Breakfast
8:30 AM – 9:30 AM	Registration
9:45 AM – 11:15 AM	Inauguration Ceremony (Indoor Stadium)
11:15 AM – 11:30 AM	Tea Break
11:30 AM – 1:30 PM	Panel Discussion 1: Media in Contemporary Political Settings Role of Media in Political Polarization
1:30 PM – 2:30 PM	Lunch Break
2:30 PM – 4:15 PM	Panel Discussion 2: Media Economics in the 21st Century Digital Inclusion and Economic Development
4:15 PM – 4:30 PM	Tea Break
4:30 PM – 5:30 PM	Technical Session
6:15 PM – 8:30 PM	Cultural Night
8:30 PM Onwards	Dinner

Day Two Friday 21, March, 2025

Time	Event
9:30 AM – 11:15 AM	Panel Discussion 3: AI and Contemporary Media Promises and Challenges of Harnessing AI in Digital Landscape
11:15 AM – 11:30 AM	Tea Break
11:30 AM – 1:30 PM	Panel Discussion 4: Media Ethics in the Digital Sphere Ethics and Regulations in the 21 st Century
1:30 PM – 2:30 PM	Lunch Break
2:30 PM – 4:15 PM	Panel Discussion 5: Media and Sociological Transformation Cultural Hybridization and Communication Trends for Social Change
4:15 PM – 4:30 PM	Tea Break
4:30 PM – 5:30 PM	Technical Session
5:30 PM – 6:00 PM	Valedictory Ceremony

International Conference Panels and Panelists

Panel Number	Title	Resource Persons	Day and time(IST)
Inauguration	Keynote Address	Prof. Srinivas Melkote	Day one 10.00 am
1	Media in Contemporary Political Settings Role of Media in Political Polarization	Prof. Shashidhar Nanjundaiah Prof. Vinod Pavarala Prof. Ujjwal K Chowdhury Prof. Satish Kolluri Dr. Asha Krishnaswamy	Day 1 11:30am- 1:30pm
2	Media Economics in the 21st Century Digital Inclusion and Economic Development	Prof. Usha Raman Prof. Shashidhar Nanjundaiah Prof. Sundeep R Muppidi Prof. Mira K Desai Prof. A.S.Balasubramanya	Day-1 2.30-4.30pm
3	AI and Contemporary Media Promises and Challenges of harnessing AI in digital landscape	Prof. Usha Raman Prof. Sundeep R Muppidi Dr. Arpan Yagnik, Prof. Ujjwal K Chowdhury Prof. Vandana Pednekar Ms. Malavika Melkote	Day 2 9:30-11:30am
4	Media Ethics in the digital sphere Ethics and Regulations in the 21 st Century	Prof.Mohan Dutta Prof.Mira K Desai Prof. B.P. Sanjay Prof.Usharani Narayana Prof. Niranjan Vanalli	Day- 2 11.30 am - 1.30pm
5	Media and Sociological Transformation Cultural Hybridization and Communication trends for social change	Prof. Srinivas Melkote Prof. Vinod Pavarala Prof. Biswajit Das Prof. B.P. Sanjay Dr. Dhiman Chattopadhyay	Day 2 2:30:4:30p m
	Valedictory		5.30 pm onwards

KEYNOTE ADDRESS

For most of the 20th Century, people and their cultures were boxed in by their dominant media channels and sources in an information world where top-down communication flows from a dominant source to a passive public. In the past 45 years, we have seen media systems transform from predominantly national systems to a truly global landscape where the media are multicultural and global in character. I will briefly address how the impressive developments in media technologies, starting in the 1990s, laid the groundwork for a multicultural and global mediascape.

I acknowledge the complexity of analyzing the growth of media in the context of globalization for the following reasons: a. the invention of ever-newer information and communication technologies (ICTs) characterized by the convergence of various media; b. the rise of mobile and social media, plus their ever-increasing flexibility and accessibility; c. the ready and easy circulation of information via digital and social networks; d. the “shrinking” of physical space; and e. the 'glocalization' of foreign formats to fit local needs and interests. These realities pose both opportunities and challenges for social change, empowerment and social justice.

PANEL 1

Panel Number	Title	Resource Persons
1	Media in Contemporary Political Settings Role of Media in Political Polarization	Prof. Shashidhar Nanjundaiah Prof. Vinod Pavarala Prof. Ujjwal K Chowdhury Prof. Satish Kolluri Dr. Asha Krishnaswamy

“Distrust and politics: Interlinking two opposing forces in media”

Disclaimer: This position summary lays down the premise and not the argument for how the media may influence political polarization: That would be an effects position, and here I remain limited to its precursor.

Sometimes a watchdog and at other times a lapdog, the world news media has flip-flopped and limped its way along since its formulation as a public good and again as a capital good. On the other hand, our entertainment media—television shows, films, etc.—have for long toed the nationalistic line in a seemingly organic fashion and yielding to what appears to be a popular trend. Secondly, combined with the five big dynamics of legacy corporate media—consumerism, conglomeration, competition, consolidation, integration—are the hidden dynamics that play a big part in mobilizing much of what happens in corporate media. Government interference both through alternately regulating and deregulating is one such mechanism. The other is unleashing a series of misrepresentations based on culture, religion, and on information itself.

To claim that the rise of social media and alternative media has a relationship with distrust and political influence cannot be dismissed. It can actually serve as a good hypothesis to test. Our media ecology and media logic are such that they have operated as a monolith—an undisputed surface that is supposed to be objective. Now, the arrival of independent media in the digital system changed all that. Had it not been for our independent media, the truth would have remained hidden from us because of the power of the official sources, including the government and a pliant news media.

Factors of distrust

The annual Reuters Report on Digital Media 2024, whose main investigation is around public trust in digital media, reports that while 69% people in Finland say they trust their news media, only 23% in Greece said they do. For the champions of a modern and informed society, this is an alarming trend, one that began nearly 10 years ago and continues unabated even as the most powerful sections of the media in Western countries have attempted to course-correct by installing better investigation mechanisms, invested in field reporting, and connected better with technology. AI newsrooms are becoming increasingly the norm.

Although distrust is a consumer-driven, sentiment-driven, cognitive phenomenon, the sociology behind it cannot be ignored. Specifically, at this time, we may delineate three factors as particularly important in the churn:

- a) technological changes in our media ecosystem, including the advancement of AI logic to replace human logic,
- b) the political changes around the world, and

Dr. Shashidhar Nanjundiah

Founding Dean and Professor at
Mahindra University, Hyderabad

c) the arrival of the alternative voice and the social media influencer as a factor of mediated influence on public opinion.

These factors must be scaffolded by geographic, political, economic, historical, sociocultural, and media landscapes and contexts.

Why are we witnessing an increasingly steep decline in public distrust in our media? Not the least of the factors for distrust is “concerns about undue political and business influence over the media” (Reuters Institute Report on Digital News Media 2024, p. 11). This indicates that the public at large feels betrayed when our institutions that promised to be independent no longer remain so, and more so when the public is not informed that the media are influenced by political or business interests. However, this is not new. Since the Hutchins Commission report of 1947, the social media have been reminded of their social responsibility, the most important of which is independence from influence. Political influence, too, has long driven media agendas.

In that ecosystem, what role does technology play? Here, we may see that the distrust of media is so deep that the public is less enamoured by AI's role in news than we would expect it to be. The perception that human-curated programs generate “AI logic” and that this logic as a replacement of media logic is not good enough.

Why distrust's “bad” effects should be disputed

Political influences on our independent digital media have so far been minimal, but efforts are underway to change that and bring in government-driven but seemingly independent regulation on ownership and legitimacy. However, that route is a slightly more circuitous than straightforward. It entails that democracies become non-democracies. Distrust must first be created about democracy, and that's not hard to do. Democracy is flawed and often chaotic, long-winded, and frustrating. Those flaws show up everywhere from elections to our daily practices. Meanwhile, therefore, straightforward steps to curb speech must be avoided.

There is always a back door, and this door leads to a dark alley. We don't know what's happening in the alley, and the outcome is hardly noticed. Let us consider a case study: One, our governments and the legacy media painted the nation red by proclaiming that the Mahakumbh Mela is returning after 144 years. That would mean that the last such event happened in 1881 and all subsequent Kumbh Melas were the smaller 12-year melas. Any politician who challenged that, as Samajwadi Party's Akhilesh Yadav did in the Parliament, was immediately shouted down by the more aggressive Hindutva forces such as Giriraj Singh. It turns out Akhilesh is probably right. We must remember the world had plenty of newspapers in 1881. Certainly, in the years following. Independent YouTubers who are former journalists went about investigating this dispute. They found that such claims of 144 years were made in 1989, 2001, and as lately as 2013. The big difference, however, is that the current government is making the claim this time. UP Chief Minister Yogi Adityanath, who is himself a religious figure, repeatedly campaigned for the

Maha Kumbh, and was promptly parroted by what we may term the “lapdog media”.

We will probe the point that distrust should be seen as the symptom, not the syndrome. Moreover, is this churn and the ascent of distrust necessarily a trend for the worse for societies? It is a question that is not frequently asked in academic or even public discourse. Our assumption that we are worse off without trusting our legacy media can be challenged, however.

Tackling the benefits of propaganda

Media literacy is often seen as a ready solution, a panacea even. Placing the onus entirely on the consumer, media literacy's practices are important but still flawed, tactical, and developing. Moreover, media literacy is an organic process that a media consumer experiences over time. However, understanding the problem does not completely address the deeper outcomes of problematic media messages.

Today, there is a cost and a benefit to spreading propaganda, hate, even fake news. (Recall Mahakumbh.) A recent study by two scholars discusses the benefits of spreading propaganda (Margolin and Wang, 2025). This study quantifies how systemic incentives encourage the spread of misinformation on social media; how social media's algorithmic opacity and “open entry” nature incentivize users to overproduce misleading messages.

Specifically, these users are encouraged to “propagation hunt,” producing many messages to identify the few that go viral. The problem is not that misinformation is being spread—the problem lies in the fact that we cannot distinguish between genuine and fake. The solution cannot lie in what is loosely termed media literacy, because there is no reliable, valid and generalizable formula that the consumer can apply. Margolin and Wang claim that the solution may lie in regulation—forcing propagandists to comply with a statement that they call attestation. This process asks the user to declare whether the message was invented, provoked, etc. The four features of this attestation being: The attestation framework offers four benefits, specifically attestation should (a) reduce the number of inaccurate messages eligible to spread; (b) reduce the number of messages the platform must evaluate; (c) increase the accuracy of evaluations; and (d) enable platforms to share important, user-generated context for other users to consider when evaluating messages.

While attestation as a self-regulatory mechanism can work, the politics and the economics of the benefits of non-attestation are far greater for specific political agendas. Politics and governance are joined at the hip, so then it all boils down to the intent of specific governments to regulate. For example, the Indian government has completely shied away from budgeting for media literacy programmes.

The survival of democracy is the premise of much of the critical discourse around political influences on media. The concepts of digital commons (Fuchs, 2021) and digital democracy will be probed.

Media in contemporary political settings and its role in political polarization have been subjects of discourse and debate for the entire period of modern times globally. Every major media house in every democracy, say Washington Post, New York Post, USA News, CNN, Fox News etc in USA or The Guardian, BBC and others in UK, all have been known for a certain political line of thinking.

However, in our contemporary times of extreme political polarization in the society with the rise of the right-wing politics in most major nations on one hand, and the rise of the total control of digital media with an increasing use of Artificial Intelligence in it, the situation is qualitatively different. There are several aspects to this rising political polarization in times of AI driven digital media, some of which are outlined below, with an Indian and a foreign case for each.

Prof Ujjwal K Chowdhury
Director-General, MSEED, Mumbai,
Vice President, GMEC

1. Amplifying Extreme Views and Creating Echo Chambers:

- **Algorithms and the Attention Economy:** Media platforms, driven by algorithms and the pursuit of engagement, often amplify extreme views and polarizing narratives. This creates echo chambers and filter bubbles, where individuals are primarily exposed to information reinforcing their existing beliefs.
- **India:** News channels like Republic TV and Times Now frequently feature debates with panelists holding extreme viewpoints, leading to increased polarization among viewers. Similarly, social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter often show users content that aligns with their existing political views, reinforcing biases.
- **Europe:** The rise of far-right online platforms in Europe, such as Breitbart News and Gefira, which disseminate divisive content and promote nationalist agendas, contributes to political polarization. The Cambridge Analytica scandal in the UK highlighted the potential for manipulation and reinforcement of existing political divides through targeted advertising.

2. Spread of Misinformation and Disinformation:

- **Erosion of Trust:** The rapid spread of misinformation and disinformation through social media and online platforms can exacerbate political polarization and erode trust in institutions.
- **India:** The spread of fake news and rumors through WhatsApp groups during elections, often targeting specific communities and inciting violence, is a major concern.
- **Europe:** Disinformation campaigns by foreign actors, such as Russia's Internet Research Agency, aimed at influencing elections and sowing discord within European societies, highlight the vulnerability of democracies to external manipulation.

3. The Changing Media Landscape and Partisan Bias:

- **Decline of Traditional Media:** The decline of traditional media outlets and the rise of

partisan news sources can contribute to political polarization by catering to specific ideological audiences.

- **India:** The increasing popularity of online news portals and social media platforms with clear political leanings, such as OpIndia and The Wire, caters to specific ideological audiences, leading to a more fragmented and polarized media landscape.
- **Europe:** The rise of partisan news channels in Europe, such as Fox News in the UK and RT (formerly Russia Today), which often promote biased narratives, contributes to political divisions. This partisan bias is also evident in traditional media, with outlets like The Guardian and The Daily Telegraph in the UK taking opposing stances on issues like Brexit.

4. Sensationalism and Negativity Bias:

- **Amplifying Conflict:** The media's tendency towards sensationalism and negativity bias can amplify conflict and exacerbate political polarization.
- **India:** News channels often focus on negative news stories and political scandals, creating a sense of outrage and division among viewers.
- **Europe:** Tabloid newspapers in the UK often engage in sensationalized reporting and character assassination of politicians, contributing to a climate of distrust and animosity.

5. The Role of Political Leaders and Media Manipulation:

- **Divisive Rhetoric:** Political leaders can use media platforms to promote divisive rhetoric and attack opponents, contributing to political polarization and undermining democratic discourse.
- **India:** The use of Twitter by Indian politicians to engage in personal attacks and spread misinformation, often targeting specific communities or individuals, is a common occurrence.
- **Europe:** The rise of populist leaders in Europe, such as Viktor Orbán in Hungary and Matteo Salvini in Italy, who use social media to bypass traditional media and directly appeal to their base, often with divisive rhetoric, further fuels polarization.

6. Lack of Media Literacy and Critical Thinking Skills:

- **Susceptibility to Manipulation:** A lack of media literacy and critical thinking skills among the public can make them more susceptible to misinformation and manipulation, further fueling political polarization.
- **India:** There is a need for greater media literacy education in India to equip citizens with the skills to critically evaluate information and identify fake news.
- **Europe:** The European Commission's Digital Competence Framework emphasizes the importance of media literacy and critical thinking skills in navigating the digital landscape.

7. Commercialization of Media and the Attention Economy:

- **Incentivizing Polarization:** The commercialization of media and the attention economy can incentivize the production of polarizing content, as it often generates more engagement and revenue.

- **India:** The pressure on news channels to generate high ratings often leads to sensationalized reporting and biased coverage, contributing to political polarization.
- **Europe:** The rise of clickbait journalism and the use of algorithms to prioritize engagement over accuracy contributes to the spread of misinformation and reinforces existing biases.

8. Lack of Diversity and Representation in Media:

- **Marginalization and Exclusion:** A lack of diversity and representation in media can lead to marginalized communities feeling excluded from the political process and further exacerbate political polarization.
- **India:** The underrepresentation of women and minority groups in Indian media leads to their voices and perspectives being marginalized in political discourse.
- **Europe:** The lack of diversity in European newsrooms can contribute to biased reporting and a lack of understanding of the concerns of minority communities.

9. The Role of Media in Promoting Dialogue and Understanding:

- **Bridging Divides:** While media can contribute to political polarization, it can also play a crucial role in promoting dialogue and understanding across different political divides.
- **India:** Initiatives like the "India Inclusion Summit" and the "Citizens for Justice and Peace" use media platforms to promote dialogue and bridge divides between different communities.
- **Europe:** The European Broadcasting Union's (EBU) commitment to public service media aims to provide impartial and balanced news coverage and foster social cohesion.

10. Regulation and Oversight:

- **Balancing Freedom and Responsibility:** Effective regulation and oversight can help ensure balanced reporting and reduce polarization, but it's crucial to balance this with protecting freedom of expression.
- **India:** The IT Rules 2021 have been criticized for increasing government control over digital platforms, raising concerns about censorship.
- **Europe:** The European Union's efforts to combat fake news and ensure media pluralism, such as the Digital Services Act (DSA), face the challenge of balancing free speech with the need to curb harmful content.

Conclusion:

The relationship between media and political polarization is complex and multifaceted. While media can contribute to polarization, it can also play a crucial role in promoting dialogue and understanding. By recognizing the challenges and harnessing the positive potential of media, we can work towards a more informed, inclusive, and cohesive society. This requires a multi-pronged approach, including strengthening media literacy, promoting responsible journalism, encouraging constructive dialogue, and fostering a diverse and representative media landscape.

Reimagining Political Communication in the Present: A View from an American Classroom

How does a radical shift in geopolitics that we are witness to in today's algorithmically driven, attention-challenged world necessitates a closer look at traditional theories of political communication that may not work to explain the present? Do those theories still have the intellectual bandwidth to explain the effects of (social) media and our interpersonal and networked communication in a highly polarized political environment? What is the impact of digital technology and social media on newsgathering, gatekeeping, and citizen journalism in the context of the decline in democratic values and human rights with a corresponding and disconcerting rise in supremacist/nationalist movements? Does reality have a liberal or conservative bias and how do 'culture wars' cause political polarization and make citizens vote against their own economic interests? What help does political psychology offer us in understanding the dumbing down of our citizenry and the growing moral chasm that has opened

Dr Satish Kolluri
Associate Professor,
Department of Communication and
Media Studies, Pace University,
418, 41 Park Row, New York, NY 10038

between the so-called Left and Right, and what does it say about our selective perception and exposure to the news we consume which appear to confirm our inherent political biases? What kinds of regulatory and ethico-political interventions are necessary to guard the citizen-subject against the excesses of 'surveillance capitalism' and state surveillance?

The above questions which resonate well with the suggested “Political Perspectives” of the conference will form the crux of my presentation as I set about to answer them specifically in the context of teaching American politics that is as unrecognizable as it is unpredictable today, and how students in my classroom who keep themselves suitably informed and civically engaged for most part, respond to the accusation of being politically and culturally 'woke.'

Displaying cool detachment and signs of cynicism is no longer a privilege they can afford, and the sharing and self-expression constitute their political subjectivities in the world of a profit and celebrity driven 'influencer culture' where there is pressure to be visible by sharing political and popular culture content and follow people of varying levels of influence in the public sphere.

The pedagogical aspect entails unpacking old and new theories of political communication, evaluating their appropriateness to quotidian politics and digital and political literacy levels of students, and generating a more heightened awareness of the 'political' that seeks to point to an urgency in deliberation on important topics and engender much needed political participation beyond the act of voting itself.

At a time when “corporations are people,” oligarchs and (political) lobbyists write public policy, and elected representatives in government are beholden more to their ideologically extremist bases and money of the tiny minority on “Wall Street” than the will of the people that constitute the majority on “Main Street,” Abraham Lincoln's iconic line in his Gettysburg Address about “government of, by, and for the people” rings hollower than ever, the need of the hour is to deepen our understanding of theory and praxis and the mutual imbrication of digital, political and economic subjectivities as they evolve, adapt, and change to accommodate newly emergent political realities.

As digital platforms evolve, so do their political impacts
We will examine their role in elections, governance, and policymaking

Digital platforms, particularly social media, can no longer be considered a new public space for content dispersal, promotion, advertising, and discussion. They have arrived, and they are here to stay and evolve. If there is a cost-effective and powerful medium to disperse content quickly, then it is social media. And people in prime positions are exploiting them.

If this is said and done, then it may be considered an irresponsible way of battling for the Internet-based media. Presently, there may not be even a single politician, lawmaker, or policymaker in India or in any technologically advanced country who has no presence on social media platforms. But the moot question is how they have been put to use. How many are aware of the pluses and minuses of using the platforms? Of course, no technology is bad. It is the usage that makes it work positively or negatively. In today's networked world, both are happening.

In the context of India, we are seeing both mindful and mindless usage of digital platforms. This is not akin to India. It is difficult to say that Internet-based media does not influence at all on all people because we are witnessing integrated media houses now. The walls in newsrooms between conventional and digital media have been done away with. We have crossed the stage of debating or thinking about whether digital media should be used or otherwise. The challenge is how to make the best use of it for the betterment of society. It is time to deliberate on global norms that can reduce fake content dispersion and data theft.

We are seeing truths, half-truths, negatively biased content, and commissioned content besides the deepfakes. Sieving information in the maze of content is a challenge for content consumers. It is even more challenging for journalists who believe in ethics. Politicians, who used to digitize their earlier pamphlet form of spreading information, are now spending time on countering half-baked news reports and allegations by their opponents on social media.

On the positive side, India has adopted e-governance. It is also making the right noise over the use and misuse of artificial intelligence. It is now setting aside a budgetary allocation for Indigenous manufacturing of electronic gadgets like smartphones and laptops.

A recent development is the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology launching the Digital Brand Identity Manual (DBIM). It provides a toolkit for a uniform identity, Gov.In CMS for streamlined management, and Central Content Publishing System (CCPS) for centralized content and social media guidelines. This is to standardize communication and digital presence across all ministries and platforms. That means we will have standardized government websites to help people access essential government services. In addition, the CCPS is making key government policies, schemes, and initiatives readily available, improving transparency and public engagement.

While the stated objectives are laudable, security issues in digital governance have to be debated. Creating an awareness regarding the possible pitfalls if precautions are not taken is the

Dr Asha Krishnaswamy
-Journalist & Media Trainer

responsibility of an elected government. Unfortunately, it is not taking place to the extent it should have been. The Indian Parliament and state legislative bodies are not paying attention to the digital security issues and the evolving technical communication space to the extent they should. Questions can be raised; apprehensions can be addressed provided politicians, legislators, and policymakers apply their minds to understand various dimensions of technology-driven platforms. Politicians and lawmakers have to undergo training sessions to understand the evolving technologies that are touching the lives of millions. While using tech-driven platforms and electronic gadgets, blind faith should have no room.

Indian courts have been raising concerns over the issuance of fake identity cards in the name of Aadhar. In January 2025, the Delhi police cracked down on illegal immigrants from Bangladesh who had illegal ID cards with Aadhaar features. A racket issuing such cards was busted. Uttar Pradesh and Maharashtra have spoken in terms of eliminating bogus ID cards.

Aadhar, which has incorporated biometric features, was conceived in 2001 and implemented in 2010. Since then, it has been facing authentication issues. Already, 99% of Indian adults have the ID cards. This is a matter of serious concern as it involves the safety of crores of people's data. Reports suggest that foreign companies are involved in developing the R&D and imaging technology. However, elected representatives have failed to maintain transparency in this regard. Citizens are forced to share their biometric ID card even to check into a private building. We are living in a coerced voluntary world. It has become the unwritten norm to link an Aadhar-PAN-KYC –Bank account to a smartphone.

The public distribution system under which the below-poverty-line families get rations is also linked to the Aadhar cards. A monthly ratio can be drawn using UID and fingerprints. If there is an authentication error due to various reasons, then the deserving people would be denied their ration quota. The fact is rural teledensity is about 52%. Brainstorming sessions on security issues should not be confined to boardrooms and star hotels.

India witnessed extensive usage of social media in the 2014 Lok Sabha elections. From then on, it has seen an upward growth. There is a significant shift in political campaigning. Digital platforms, AI, and social media have made it into the political landscape. India ranks next to China in terms of usage of the Internet. Politicians have no alternative but to use platforms like FB, X, Instagram, and WhatsApp to connect with voters. Misinformation campaigns using deepfakes using AI have been posing a serious challenge to politicians. Parallel verification is not accessible to all.

Virtual Reality, Augmented Reality, Extended Reality, Mixed Reality, and more are used in the poll campaigns. These tech-driven reality platforms are developing a wall between politicians and voters? It is a debatable issue.

Does any of this technology help to cleanse the political system? Have they been able to strengthen the democratic system by using technology? Lawmakers must discuss these issues on the floor of Parliament. If this has to happen, then the media has to play a pivotal role in creating awareness about issues that matter most to people.

PANEL 2

Title	Resource Persons
Media Economics in the 21 st Century Digital Inclusion and Economic Development	Prof. Usha Raman Prof. Shashidhar Nanjundaiah Prof. Sundeep R Muppidi Prof. Mira K Desai Prof. A.S.Balasubramanya

New formations, new imaginations: how can we understand the media business today?

Perhaps every generation thinks of contemporary developments as “unprecedented” and “disruptive”—words that have become so commonplace as to be devoid of content. But there is no doubt that every new generation of has challenged analysts and regulators, who have attempted to first fit newer media into existing regulatory and organizational frameworks, trying to grasp and accommodate evolving and shifting modes of production, distribution and consumption in frameworks that seem to break even as they are constructed. Over the past twenty years, those who study media economics have been bringing a range of insights that help us understand new media formations and legacy media transformations, pushing us to think about the multiple moments in the media business in more expansive ways. This has meant that we take cognizance of many new actors and processes within this space—one that is now redefined in many places as “the media and creative industries”—and the organizational and financial logics they force, or engender. This presentation will offer short provocations on two distinct but not unrelated media trends that have emerged in the past decade or so. The first is the persistence of podcasting, a late 20th century media form that was not expected to survive (and certainly not thrive) in the age of digital video. The second is the expansion of media properties in ways that turn cultural phenomena into content, the case in point being the New York Times Games and Cooking apps, both of which point to a more intensive focus on non-news (or lifestyle-based) engagement to drive the enterprise of news. The first has emerged from the possibilities that the digital opened up for “small media”, while the second represents the age-old trend of integration to build scale and breadth of service. Both however are firmly enabled by digital modes of production and distribution, not to speak of the global diffusion of consumption. How might we as media scholars make sense of these specific trends, and how do they open up (or foreclose) new questions about the shape of the creative industries?

Prof. Usha Raman
Professor, Dept. of Communication,
University of Hyderabad

Presentation, representation, and the economics of the media prosumer”

We live in an age of digital capitalism (Fuchs, 2023) Academic considerations of new media economics have lagged behind the counterparts of cultural, critical, and technological considerations (Ballon, 2014). Nevertheless, whenever we invoke critical theory or cultural theory, we are really talking about media economics. The contours of the economics of our interactive and so-called “democratized” nature of our contemporary media can include the policies of technology, the cultural influences of social media content, the ethics of AI aesthetics, and so forth.

The age of media prosumerism

The economics of the new media are in a churn. To understand new media economics, especially as it is to be governed by the new burst of artificial intelligence, it is important to recognize its elements—which remain the same, i.e., message-making and meaning-making. These have at once expanded and collapsed into prosumerism—the portmanteau word for producer+consumer, whose functions are not guided by modern institutions but by suggestions by technological affordances of social media. We are witnessing an emergence of the media prosumer. The differentiation between the producer and the consumer will continue to get fuzzier as this new media makes further inroads. What this could mean in reality is that while we can still recognize the processes of production, consumption, and use (I use the last two terms in distinct ways) without necessarily humanizing each of them. This is because they could all be the same person, this individual in society who at once consumes, processes, and produces or reproduces.

On one hand, more people around the world than ever before have cut the cord, or stopped consuming news, than ever before, making the economics of legacy media less certain than before and raising questions about its future. On the other, there is now a media prosumer community, whose operations may be compared with those of media communities in general. While living physical lives, these communities also live parallel virtual, participatory, interactive, global-local, hypercommunicative lives.

The age of presentation and representation

While legacy media have presented to us the claim that they represent the publics, forms of presentation in the age of the media prosumer have taken on an additional form of self-representation, and the method of auto-ethnography is supremely relevant today.

In particular, the arrival of alternative media—alternative to the so-called mainstream or legacy media—has heralded the kind of unfettered freedoms that we did not see in the earlier media. But by no means are alternative media independent of slant or bias. Therefore, independence does not automatically herald objectivity, so much so that most critical scholars today do not believe objectivity can exist in the media. However, the value of alternative media discourse is not objectivity but the production of a narrative that often questions or even runs counter to curated and influenced narratives of the mainstream. Thus, a narration of truth is split

into a narration of opinions. The idea that truth lies in an undisputed realm is thus challenged. Fake news can result as an extreme version of this realm.

The economic success of the new media lies in big data and mass movements online. Consider what happened in Boolgarhi, just outside the town of Hathras, in 2020. Local youth recorded the victim's last words and uploaded the video on YouTube. It was poorly produced, the voice was feeble, and above all, the police discredited the video as fake news. The video received only three likes and about 100 views overall.

Beauty and truth: What we see

The poet John Keats drew our attention first to the dialectical nature of the relationship between beauty and truth. Even in the age of the media prosumer, the tension continues. Here we must understand aesthetics and beauty not exactly as Keats described it but as the prepared story, made for our acceptance. The ugly can therefore be beautiful in the neoliberal sense—imagine an accident in which nobody died but it's dramatic—an aeroplane flips on the runway. It gets you more clicks and views than another tragedy in which a farmer may commit suicide from economic distress. So our new media logic is such that aesthetics and acceptability go together.

Forms of invisibilization of truth are found in presentation of information, of voices, and of social conditions. It is a strategic aesthetic manoeuvre. In this strategy, you shine the light over a spot, creating what we may call a streetlight effect. Axel Honneth, the German scholar on visibility and recognition, argues that recognition is problematic because of what he calls the streetlight effect. The streetlight here may also represent a system that is unavoidable and static, like a regulatory or media ownership.

However, how do we account for something that is far more insidious, hidden, invisible? The invisible hand that twists, so to speak. Imagine a fabric surface that is seemingly smooth. If you look underneath, you might find that it is actually a tapestry of patches that is sewn—or sutured—together. That represents a newspaper, a newscast, or even a news story. The tailor is of the media, but who is the owner who directs how to suture? This tapestry is made to appear smooth, with specific spots of light. But now as we move into the digital media age, we may witness specific spots of darkness. It is not as though the digital age has illuminated the entire fabric. However, my reason that we should not discard the name alternative media for our independent digital media is because they flip what legacy media do: If legacy media visibilize a beautified surface, the alternative media show the underbelly of the fabric, all the sutures and stitchings showing. It is ugly and unseemly.

The creation of new myths lies in the hands of the prosumer that I briefly mentioned earlier. Let me end with a case study: When Donald Trump visited India in 2020, Ahmedabad was decked up to receive him, cheer for him, show bonhomie all around, celebrate, hide darker realities, etc. After all the spiritual call of Atithi devobhava and of course the eternal vasudhaiva kutumbakam must be invoked and honoured at such times! If we parse and analyse just the visuals of what happened, the well-to-do sections of the city was on the streets in beautiful attires, smiling, cheering, and hiding what's behind them. Prime Minister Modi even took Trump to

Gandhi's Sabarmati Ashram and taught him the art of weaving. This was a theatre of the encomium, the mutual display. If you cut to 2025 and PM Modi's recent visit to Washington, a different story awaited. But on social media and on legacy media, of course, you will find a strong voice that tries to suppress those critical moments.

Beauty is important in the production of truth(s), but the sutured display of beauty is more important—beauty must be shown as continuous and ugliness must be hidden.

References

Adorno, T. W. (1997). *Aesthetic theory*. (G. Adorno & R. Tiedemann, Eds.) (R. Hullot-Kenor, Trans.) University of Minnesota Press. (Original work published 1970)

Ballon, P. (2014). Old and new issues in media economics. In K. Donders, C. Pauwels, J. Loisen (Eds.), *The Palgrave handbook of European media policy*. Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137032195_5

Benkler, Y. (2006) *The wealth of networks: How social production transforms markets and freedom*. Yale University Press.

Fuchs, C. (2017). The information economy and the labor theory of value. *International Journal of Political Economy*, 46(1), 65-89.

Fuchs, C. (2021). The Digital commons and the digital public sphere: How to advance digital democracy today. *Westminster Papers in Communication and Culture*, 16(1), 9–26. <https://doi.org/10.16997/wpcc.917>

Honneth, A. (2001). Invisibility: On the epistemology of 'recognition'. *Aristotelian Society*, 75(1), 111-126.

Honneth, A. & Margalit, A. (2001). Recognition. *Proceedings of the Aristotelian Society, Supplementary Volumes, Volume 75* (pp. 111-139). Oxford University Press.

Margolin, D. B. & Wang, Y. S. (2025). Creating a cost to spread misinformation on social media. *International Journal of Communication*, 19, 998-1018.

Tapscott, D. & Williams, A. D. (2007). *Wikinomics: How mass collaboration changes everything*. Penguin.

Media Economics in the 21st Century: Digital Inclusion and Economic Development

Digital platforms, especially social media and online content have dramatically altered the fundamentals of media economics and will continue to shape the future of the media industries in the 21st century. The ease of content production, consumption, and access have created significant challenges for traditional media industries while creating new opportunities and challenges, for digital producers, consumers and other stakeholders. Technology companies have overshadowed legacy media companies with the rise of digital convergent technologies. For example:

Dr. Sundeep R. Muppidi, Ph.D.
Professor of Digital Media and Journalism
University of Hartford, USA.

Platforms like Google, Facebook, Amazon, and Netflix have become major players in media distribution, impacting advertising revenue and traditional media business models. Legacy newspapers and magazines face significant challenges due to migration of audiences towards online news consumption. This fall in legacy subscribers has led to reduced advertising revenue and decline in traditional subscription models.

The prevalence of such free online content, including user-generated content, has also impacted the traditional model of paying for media access. These are often characterized by issues like data-driven advertising, niche subscription models, and a fragmented media landscape. As such, traditional media companies have been struggling to adapt to new revenue generation models in the digital age and have tried experimenting with e-papers, online websites, pay walls and other subscription models but with mixed results. Meanwhile, platforms like YouTube have empowered individuals to create and distribute content, influencing the media landscape leading to a proliferation of content creators, social influencers, and targeted subscribers. So much so that many digital media companies are transitioning to subscription-based models, offering exclusive content to subscribers through Patreon, Substack, and other services. While the migration to online platforms has been nothing short of phenomenal, it has its own set of challenges. Targeted advertising based on user data has become a primary revenue stream for digital media companies, raising several concerns about such audience profiling. Data collection practices by digital platforms, intent on optimizing one-to-one marketing strategies, increasingly profile users through targeted algorithms, and raise concerns regarding surveillance and user privacy.

The wide variety of online content available, mostly for free, across platforms has also led to a fragmented media landscape, making it harder for audiences to distill good from bad information. This overabundance of content has also led to the spreading of misinformation on online platforms, without any checks and balances, and poses a significant challenge to democratic societies and a vibrant civil society as audiences increasingly latch onto conspiracies and populate echo chambers.

Digital media also allows for easy content distribution across borders, impacting international media markets. Governments, across the world, are also grappling with regulating the power of large technological companies and struggling to ensure fair competition. At the same time, access to digital media and technology has become fundamental to economic participation. Rural and underserved communities often face significant challenges in digital connectivity. Global socio-political changes, rise in right-wing nationalism, cybersecurity, and digital fraud are also big concerns. While inequalities in internet access and digital literacy create barriers to economic advancement, mobile technology, especially in Asian societies, has emerged as a critical tool for bridging economic gaps, especially in developing regions.

Media Economics in 21st Century India: Case of Connected TV

Indian television, as a public service broadcaster Doordarshan since its inception in 1959 and subsequent developments of going colour in 1982 and going commercial in nineties, remained state supported medium. Though advertising entered Indian television in 1976 as black&white, the big push was with advertiser supported soap opera in 1982. It is only in October 1992 when commercial broadcaster in form of Zee and subsequently STAR TV and many others that made the question of television media economics crucial because prior to that television was State supported medium. Advent of Cable and Satellite (C&S) television and Direct To Home (DTH), subsequently making television fully digital with Set Top Box (STB) Digital Access System (DAS) by the State in twentieth century changed the economic equations. From creation cost born by State and Advertisers, the era of distribution costs falling on viewers begun due to C&S, DTH and STB television.

Prof. Mira K. Desai
University Department of
Extension & Communication
SNDT Women's University, Juhu Campus, Mumbai
(mkdesai@extensionedu.sndt.ac.in)

Twenty first Century Indian television witnessed beginning of 'Connected TV'- CTV (smart television set that is connected with Internet). In 2023, nine in 10 American households had at least one internet-enabled TV device. In India the number is estimated to be 45 million households out of 217 million TV households. By definition CTV is a device connected directly with internet, can stream through smart TV, gaming console, media streaming devices, and internet enabled set top boxes. It is here to transform traditional TV scenario, providing access to advertisers to the point of purchase while allowing viewers to experience products, challenge digital spaces and in the times to come reach with clear estimation of actions taken by the

viewers. It is reported that 91 percent of all television shipments in first half of 2023 were smart TVs and there has been 72 percent increase in fixed line broadband in three years between 2020 to 2023. Interestingly 50 to 55 percent of these TV Sets are made by local manufacturers.

The traditional economics of television in India was public service broadcasting which was supported by advertisers. With the C&STV and DTH led to removing free riders and recurring cost for distribution/reception of television impacting TV economics. However, STB system made it mandatory to provide for Free To Air (FTA) channels especially by government broadcaster (now Prasar Bharti) which led to some commercial broadcasters also offering FTA fare to reach audiences. CTV is shifting television economics from creation (supported by State or advertisers) to distribution and consumption as viewer need to spend for using internet data unlike older model of Doordarshan times. The revenue models for broadcasters also shifted from advertising to subscription which is set to transform again with CTV.

With the advent and growth of CTV, broadcasters serve sections of the audiences to advertisers with transparency and measurability of outcomes and direct sales opportunities. It may also impact digital media economics and may lead to individualised media consumption shift back to family consumption of television. Indian audiences are value conscious markets so in that context CTV may push telecom sectors also to rethink their strategies leading to changed audience behaviours. With regional language media consumption on rise, the economics may also become more regional rather than 'national'. CTV also adds additional revenue streams like SMS/Voice voting, product placements, syndications and show integrations, and so on. At the end of it the viewer will benefit as well as bear the costs and government will make more money through taxes from telecom, broadcasters, Multi-System Operators and television set manufacturers.

References

Marg ERP Ltd (2023) Bridging the Television Divide: Exploring the Indian Government's Set-Top Box Scheme, June 21, 2023. URL: <https://margcompusoft.com/m/indian-government-set-top-box-scheme/>

Elavarthi Satya Prakash & Sunitha Chitrapu (2022) Media Economics and Management, Routledge, New York.

PANEL 3

Title	Resource Persons
AI and Contemporary Media Promises and Challenges of harnessing AI in digital landscape	Prof. Usha Raman Prof. Sundeep R Muppidi Dr. Arpan Yagnik, Prof. Ujjwal K Chowdhury Prof. Vandana Pednekar Ms. Malavika Melkote

AI and Contemporary Media: Promises and Challenges of harnessing AI in digital landscape

The contemporary media landscape continues to evolve rapidly with technological advancements and shifting cultural practices. Increasingly, digital media platforms cater to most audience needs for information, entertainment, education, and communication. In the last decade, advances in technologies of content creation, distribution, and access have facilitated the rise and proliferation of several digital media platforms, websites, mobile apps, streaming services, podcasts, blogs, newsletters, epublications, social media sites, gaming systems, virtual and augmented reality and other immersive technologies. In recent years, generative, predictive and content moderation AI technologies, have simplified and automated content generation processes while also blurring the real and fictional worlds.

Dr. Sundeep R. Muppidi, Ph.D.
Professor of
Digital Media and Journalism
University of Hartford, USA.

This proliferation of AI technologies holds a lot of promise but also comes with a set of challenges. Generative AI technologies enable dynamic content generation while also assisting with editing, optimization, and content distribution. Specified algorithms can also tailor content to individual user preferences, through intuitive cross-platform experiences, increasing engagement and creating an enhanced user experience. This can also include automated captioning, language translation, and other services to increase accessibility of content. AI can also help process large data sets to identify trends and patterns in user data and consumption habits. This helps to optimize policy and content generation decision making through real time analytics, all of which hold a lot of promise for media industries.

At the same time, the challenges are many. Legacy media have struggled to keep up with the fast-paced evolution of digital forms and platforms. This has had an adverse impact on media jobs and traditional content creation roles. AI tools that can create content quickly and cheaply threaten traditional media business models and the livelihood of creative professionals. Many media companies are struggling to adapt their revenue structures to these fast-paced changes in the media world.

AI-generated text, images, audio, and video can create convincing fake content that's increasingly difficult to distinguish from authentic media. Thus, the automated nature of such content generation lacks the checks and balances especially when it comes to countering misinformation and deepfakes. Advanced AI tools may also be primarily available to well-resourced media organizations, creating or widening disparities in who controls the media narrative. This threatens trust in media institutions and complicates fact-checking. It also raises questions of content quality, integrity, and authenticity as also the loss of human creativity.

AI systems trained on copyrighted media raise complex questions about fair use, intellectual property rights, proper attribution, and compensation for original creators. The sheer volume of content being produced also requires AI-powered moderation, which struggles with nuance, context, and cultural variations, leading to both over-moderation and under-moderation issues. AI recommendation systems can therefore limit exposure to diverse viewpoints and create information silos, potentially increasing polarization and reducing shared media experiences.

AI-powered analytics can track media consumption in increasingly invasive ways, raising questions about surveillance and user autonomy. The collection of user data and analytics also raises several privacy and ethical concerns as also algorithmic bias.

As authentic and synthetic content become more difficult to distinguish, building media literacy and maintaining audience trust becomes increasingly challenging. These challenges are reshaping how media is produced, distributed, and consumed, requiring new frameworks for ethics, regulation, and media literacy.

AI and Contemporary Media: Promises & Challenges of Harnessing AI in a Digital Landscape

We are all aware of the immense positive impact of speed, efficiency, volume of content, etc, which has been brought into the domain of media through the use of artificial intelligence. However, alongside there are challenges of factual accuracy, deep fakes, Western bias depending upon the content sources of the AI tool, gender bias, etc. The note below looks at several areas of benefits of AI in contemporary media, explains them with one Indian and one foreign case, and also notes the challenges therein.

Prof Ujjwal K Chowdhury
Director-General, MSEED, Mumbai,
Vice President, GMEC

I. Content Creation & Automation:

1. AI-Generated Content:

- **Promise:** AI can generate high-quality content quickly and efficiently, enabling new forms of storytelling and expression.
- **Indian Example:** WION uses AI to generate news summaries, increasing content output and freeing up journalists for more in-depth reporting.
- **Foreign Example:** The Washington Post's Heliograf writes news articles, particularly for sports and finance, allowing for broader coverage.
- **Challenge:** Maintaining creativity and originality, ensuring ethical use, and addressing potential job displacement in the creative industries.

2. AI in Journalism:

- **Promise:** AI can assist in investigative journalism by analysing large datasets and automating fact-checking, enhancing efficiency and accuracy.
- **Indian Example:** The Quint uses AI for data journalism, uncovering hidden patterns and insights from complex data.
- **Foreign Example:** Reuters' Lynx Insight tool helps journalists analyse financial data and identify trends.
- **Challenge:** Ensuring accuracy and avoiding misinformation, maintaining journalistic ethics, and balancing automation with human oversight.

II. Audience Engagement & Personalization:

3. Personalized Media Consumption:

- **Promise:** AI can tailor content to individual preferences, enhancing user experience and engagement.
- **Indian Example:** Hotstar's recommendation engine suggests content based on user viewing history, increasing user satisfaction and platform stickiness.
- **Foreign Example:** Netflix's personalized content suggestions cater to individual tastes, driving viewership and subscriber retention.
- **Challenge:** Risk of creating echo chambers and reinforcing biases, limiting exposure to diverse perspectives and potentially contributing to polarization.

4. AI in Advertising:

- **Promise:** AI can optimize ad targeting and improve ROI, delivering personalized ads to the most receptive audiences.
- **Indian Example:** Flipkart's AI-driven ad platform targets users based on their browsing and purchase history, increasing conversion rates.
- **Foreign Example:** Google's AI-powered ad services analyse user data to deliver highly targeted ads, maximizing ad revenue.
- **Challenge:** Privacy concerns and data security, potential for manipulation and exploitation of user data, and the need for transparency and user control over data usage.

III. Accessibility & Inclusion:

5. Enhancing Accessibility:

- **Promise:** AI can enhance media accessibility for people with disabilities through features like AI-powered translation, transcription, captioning, and audio description.
- **Indian Example:** Use of AI-powered translation and transcription tools to make regional language content more accessible in India, bridging linguistic barriers.
- **Foreign Example:** YouTube's auto-translate feature breaks language barriers in global content, making videos accessible to a wider audience.
- **Challenge:** Ensuring inclusivity and addressing potential biases in AI systems, adapting to diverse accessibility needs, and promoting equitable access to technology and resources.

IV. Ethical & Legal Considerations:

6. Algorithmic Bias & Representation:

- **Challenge:** AI-driven content curation can perpetuate existing biases, leading to skewed representation and limited diversity in media.
- **Indian Example:** News aggregators in India prioritizing content based on popularity, potentially marginalizing regional voices and minority perspectives.
- **Foreign Example:** Facial recognition algorithms used by law enforcement in the US showing higher error rates for people of colour, impacting media coverage and public perception.
- **Promise:** Developing and implementing AI systems with fairness and inclusivity in mind, promoting diverse representation in media content and mitigating algorithmic bias.

7. Deepfakes & Misinformation:

- **Challenge:** AI's ability to create realistic deepfakes poses a significant threat to media credibility and public trust, potentially fueling misinformation and manipulation.
- **Indian Example:** Deepfake videos used to spread political misinformation during elections, leading to social unrest and polarization.

- **Foreign Example:** Deepfake videos of political leaders in the West used to manipulate public opinion and undermine democratic processes.
- **Promise:** Developing AI tools for deepfake detection and verification, promoting media literacy and critical thinking skills to identify manipulation, and fostering collaboration between technology companies and media organizations to combat misinformation.

8. Copyright & Intellectual Property:

- **Challenge:** AI's ability to generate creative content challenges existing copyright laws and raises questions about ownership and authorship.
- **Indian Example:** AI-generated music and art being used in advertising and entertainment in India, leading to debates about copyright infringement.
- **Foreign Example:** AI-generated art platforms like DALL-E and Midjourney facing legal challenges regarding copyright and intellectual property rights.
- **Promise:** Establishing clear legal frameworks for AI-generated content, balancing the rights of creators and innovators, and fostering collaboration to develop ethical and sustainable models for AI in the creative industries.

9. Data Privacy & Surveillance:

- **Challenge:** AI-powered media platforms collect vast amounts of user data, raising concerns about privacy and potential misuse for surveillance.
- **Indian Example:** Data collection by Indian OTT platforms and social media companies, with limited transparency about data usage and security.
- **Foreign Example:** The use of facial recognition and surveillance technologies by governments and corporations in China, raising concerns about privacy and civil liberties.
- **Promise:** Implementing robust data protection regulations, promoting transparency and user control over data, and developing ethical guidelines for AI development and deployment to safeguard privacy and civil liberties.

V. Regulation & Future Trends:

10. Ethical Frameworks & Regulation:

- **Challenge:** The rapid advancement of AI in media requires the development of ethical frameworks and regulatory guidelines to ensure responsible innovation.
- **Indian Example:** The ongoing debate about data protection and AI regulation in India, with the need for clear guidelines for media companies.
- **Foreign Example:** The European Union's AI Act, aiming to regulate the development and use of AI technologies, including in media.
- **Promise:** Fostering international collaboration on AI ethics and governance, promoting responsible AI development and deployment, and ensuring that AI technologies serve human well-being and societal progress.

AI in the Digital Frontier

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the media landscape has brought about a paradigm shift. As AI technologies continue to advance, their influence on media production, distribution, and consumption will be increasingly profound. There are foremost challenges, and the list is long.

AI-generated content blurs the lines between reality and fiction, making it difficult for audiences to distinguish between genuine and manipulated media. Concerns about misinformation and AI's use in spreading false narratives are already widespread. Public trust in media sources is undermined.

Further, the use of AI in creating content, such as music, art, and writing, raises questions about ownership and copyright. Determining who holds the rights to AI-generated works can be complex, especially when multiple parties are involved in the creation process. Addressing this issue necessitates the development of new legal frameworks.

AI algorithms used in media perpetuate existing biases if they are trained on biased data. This can lead to unfair representation and discrimination in media content, affecting how different groups are portrayed and perceived.

Most important, in the realm of political miscommunication, AI has served as an important tool in the hands of state actors. New media are more vulnerable to state control and manipulation than legacy media ever were. As Nicholas Carrⁱ explains, “In the bewildering media landscape, AI generated content on social media promotes lies and antipathy more effectively than truth and empathy. The result is “an information environment conducive to authoritarian movements and cults of personality.”

While these are pressing challenges, AI promises opportunities. AI is increasingly seen as a powerful tool for writers, researchers and media creators by automating routine tasks of transcription, translation, data analysis freeing up time to focus on the creative aspect. This can lead to increased productivity and innovation in the media industry. Emerging features such as 'text to video generation' in newer generative AIⁱⁱ promise to revolutionize film making by democratizing the movie making business. Indeed, in fields from podcasting to video games to advertising, AI-powered tools can simplify editing, save time and lower barriers to entry.

In my presentation, I will elaborate the socio-political challenges posed by AI, not without some optimism about its potential in our digital environments.

**Dr. Vandana Pednekar -
Magal, Ph.D.**
Georgia State University, USA

ⁱ Nicholas Carr, *Superbloom: How technologies of connection tear us apart*. Norton

ⁱⁱ For example 'Runway' from a startup company in New York.

AI Contemporary Media – Promises & challenges of harnessing AI in digital landscape

As the internet democratized information over 30 years ago, AI is making intelligence widely accessible at a cheaper, faster rate and at scale. Human insight, in the form of knowledge, expertise, experience is no longer scarce, expensive or difficult to access. You can consult dozens of experts anytime you like, operate AI agents to get outcomes driving organizations to rethink how they innovate, operate, how they approach learning, research and decision-making. For academics, R & D organizations, the recent release of the AI tool Deep Research, shows how for a given research question it will formulate a research plan and consult a variety of sources to provide a research brief, in minutes. This is indeed a milestone in how we access and manipulate knowledge. AI enables constant refinement and enablement of ideas and solutions at a pace not seen before.

Ms. Malavika Melkote,
Director, AI & Analytics
Industry Expert, USA

AI has the potential to democratize content creation by providing creators with advanced tools that were previously accessible only to large media corporations. Independent artists, journalists, and filmmakers can now leverage AI to produce professional grade content, thereby leveling the playing field and fostering a more diverse and inclusive media landscape.

However, the integration of AI in media also presents several challenges. One of the primary concerns is the ethical implications of AI-generated content. The use of AI to create deepfakes—realistic but fake videos of images—has raised significant concerns about misinformation and the potential for malicious use. The ability of AI to manipulate media content poses a threat to credibility of information and can undermine public trust in media sources.

Another challenge is the potential for bias in AI algorithms. AI systems are trained on large datasets, and if these datasets contain biased information, the AI can perpetuate and even amplify these biases. This can lead to unfair representation and discrimination in media content, which can have far-reaching social implications. Ensuring that AI systems are trained on diverse and representative datasets is crucial to mitigating this risk. Quoting Apple's Tim Cook, “Technology is morally neutral until we apply it. It is up to us to align AI with our values and ethics”.

The digital landscape across domains, from healthcare to manufacturing, media & entertainment are learning fast and investing in leveraging the power of AI. While technology and AI models are evolving at an exponential pace, it is the adoption of these capabilities that organizations are trying to keep pace with. What this means for the future of work, and the current and future workforce, is to understand how best to leverage AI in life and at work. Knowing how to use AI requires a shift in skillsets, the ability to think critically, collaborate with AI assistants to amplify your capabilities. This quote from an AI expert captures what's ahead - “As intelligence becomes practically free, our real constraint is no longer accessing brainpower but knowing what to do with it”. Another expert says “Promise of AI is to free people of not doing what they don't like to do”.

We are only at the beginning of this transformation that is going to impact every walk of life work, and society. The ultimate potential of AI is to influence, enable humans to drive positive change in the world. With the sophistication of models, the promise of AGI

PANEL 4

Title	Resource Persons
Media Ethics in the digital sphere Ethics and Regulations in the 21st Century	Prof. Mohan Dutta Prof. Mira K. Desai Prof. B.P. Sanjay Prof. Usharani Narayana Prof. Niranjana Vanalli

Media Ethics in the Digital Sphere in India: An Indecent Proposal?

Ethics and media ethics cannot be seen as separate domains since something that an individual should not do applies to media as well contextually. However, role of media in democracy has far reaching impact on the governance and public good. Role of media in providing unbiased and quality information in democracy does not need any debate nor it is in the purview of this abstract. It also needs to be recognized that digital sphere is connected with the physical spheres of the society.

Indian digital sphere has expanded with estimated 900 million internet users making India second in the world after China. As per economic times September 2024 estimates seven in ten Indian are shopping online. However, in terms of digital divides, only 14.9 percent rural and 42 percent urban households have internet connections suggesting that most of them connected through mobile phones. With national average of 51 percent broadband penetration, rural penetration is 29 percent indicating miles to go before India goes digital.

Information Technology Act of 2000 was the first attempt to deal with ecommerce and cybercrime, mostly linked to financial crimes. With the growth of social media, as early as July 2018 that Rajya Sabha called for attention motion for misuse of social media and spreading of fake news. Subsequent to that after number of attempts, Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules were notified in February 2021. Under these Rules as per Rule 2(1)(i) Digital Media are “digitised content that can be transmitted over the internet or computer networks, including content received, stored, transmitted, edited or processed by an intermediary; or a publisher of news and current affairs content or a publisher of online curated content”. The Rules does not define intermediary but as per S. 2(1)(w) of the IT Act, intermediary, is any person who on behalf of another person receives, stores or transmits that record or provides any service with respect to that record and includes telecom service providers, network service providers, internet service providers, web-hosting service providers, search engines, online payment sites, online-auction sites, online-market places and cyber cafes.

Part II of IT Rules 2021 challenges online privacy and freedom of expression by enhanced government control over digital platforms. The acknowledgment to digital sphere came publicly with Prime Minister Narendra Modi honoring content creators with first ever national creators' awards in 2024. General election of 2024 also highlighted role of digital content creators. And this is the same time when IT Rules 2021 are being challenged by multiple petitions across the country. With the legacy television (TV) becoming connected TV, marketers desperately trying

Prof Mira K. Desai

University Department of
Extension & Communication
SNDT Women's University,
Juhu Campus, Mumbai
(mkdesai@extensionedu.sndt.ac.in)

to reach its consumers through influencer marketing, with any publicity is good publicity and influencers in news for all wrong reasons, political sphere has interjected to digital sphere, are ethics in digital sphere a proposal, not a very decent one? The question awaits the answer which lies in the time.

References

Garg Medha (2024) Constitutional Challenges to the IT Rules, 2021: Arguments Set to Begin, October 17, 2024, URL: <https://internetfreedom.in/dhc-it-rules-2021-hearing/>

Press Information Bureau (2024) PM's interaction with the winners of first-ever National Creators Awards, March 8, 2024 URL: <https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaseIframePage.aspx?PRID=2012637>

Singh S V and Suhan S (2021) Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code: Shifting Paradigm of Social & Digital Media Platforms, September 9, 2021

URL: <https://www.foxmandal.in/intermediary-guidelines-and-digital-media-ethics-code/>

Media Ethics in the Digital Age: Regulation and Self-Regulation in Indiaⁱ

The rapid proliferation of digital media in India has transformed the communication landscape, presenting both opportunities and challenges. This paper/presentation examines the status and spread of digital media in India, highlighting explicit ethical concerns, the need for regulation, and the ongoing debate over self-regulation. It also explores the scope and limitations of media literacy in curbing aberrations in user-generated content.

Status and Spread of Digital Media in India

India has witnessed exponential growth in digital media usage, driven by increased internet penetration, affordable smartphones, and the popularity of social media platforms. This digital revolution has democratized access to information and enabled diverse voices to be heard. However, it has also led to the proliferation of misinformation, hate speech, and obscene content, raising significant ethical concerns. The macro dynamics of macro issues that touch upon the moral and religious landscape need to be recognised as well.

Ethical Concerns in Digital Media

The ethical landscape of digital media in India is fraught with challenges. Issues such as privacy violations, cyberbullying, and the spread of fake news have become more pronounced. The anonymity provided by digital platforms often emboldens individuals to engage in unethical behaviour without fear of repercussions. Additionally, the commercialization of digital media has led to content that prioritizes sensationalism over accuracy, further exacerbating ethical dilemmas.

Need for Regulation

Given the ethical challenges, there is a growing consensus on the need for robust regulation of digital media in India. The Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital

Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021, represent a significant step towards regulating digital content. These rules aim to establish accountability among intermediaries and digital media platforms, ensuring that they adhere to ethical standards and remove harmful content promptly. The Supreme Court of India has also emphasized the necessity of such regulations, particularly in the context of obscene content.

Clamour for Self-Regulation

While regulation is essential, there is also a strong advocacy for self-regulation within the digital media industry. This self-regulation is an extension of the traditional or legacy media attitude where the overall freedom of the press (media) has been invoked. Proponents argue that self-regulation allows for greater flexibility and responsiveness to ethical issues. Industry bodies and digital platforms have initiated various self-regulatory measures, including content moderation policies and community guidelines. However, the effectiveness of self-regulation remains a subject of debate, with critics pointing out its limitations in addressing deep-rooted ethical concerns.

Scope and Limitations of Media Literacy

Media literacy is a crucial tool in mitigating the ethical challenges posed by user-generated content. Educating users about responsible digital behaviour, critical thinking, and the verification of information can significantly reduce the spread of misinformation and unethical content. The larger concern of platforms' attitude toward fact check has come about as a crucial factor in the recent past. However, the scope of media literacy initiatives in India is limited, and there is a need for comprehensive programs that reach diverse demographics. Enhancing media literacy can empower users to navigate the digital landscape ethically and responsibly.

Conclusion

The ethical concerns surrounding digital media in India necessitate a balanced approach that combines regulation, self-regulation, and media literacy. While regulatory frameworks provide a necessary foundation for accountability, self-regulation and media literacy initiatives can complement these efforts by fostering a culture of ethical digital behaviour. As India continues to embrace the digital age, addressing these ethical challenges will be crucial in ensuring a responsible and inclusive digital media ecosystem.

ⁱ Invited paper and presentation for Two-Day international conference Reimagining Communication

In the 21st Century: Sociological, Political, and Economic Perspectives, Postgraduate Department of Journalism and Mass Communication St. Philomena's College (Autonomous) Mysuru, March 20-21. 2025.

Digital technology is a new member of media family. It is continuously evolving and the technological part is overwhelming. Integration of Artificial intelligence with big data has heralded the arrival of neo digital revolution. It is a platform integrating science and social sciences touching on emotions and philosophy of mind besides providing value addition services that has changed the way we live and work. Trillions of users are hooked to the information machines through Internet causing profound implications on human life. The significant feature of digital communication is participation of users in technological process. The digital technology has changed the social structure. This paper reiterates the premise that digital technology has disrupted human communication and is facing huge ethical challenges and dilemmas.

Prof. Usha rani Narayana

Former Professor & Director,
University of Mysore, Karnataka

The core issues are Navigating privacy, data security, and misinformation which require strong ethical frameworks. Globally new ethical norms for digital media are being debated to minimize the social disruptions. Undoubtedly digital media has invaded privacy where personal information which is the right of every individual is being collected, shared and used in gross violation of ethical and legal norms. Many countries including India have implemented data privacy laws to regulate the use of personal data but that has not checked the abuse of personal data. Social media networks are the most vulnerable domains for invasion of privacy. Data security is the threat posed by digital media where countries are implementing stringent regulations to protect digital information from theft. Data security involves working on both hardware and software for protecting digital information from unauthorized access. To a common man, banking is the most targeted sector where data integrity is compromised paving way for cyber crimes.

Misinformation underlines the need to develop skills to differentiate facts from fake messages. The absence of foolproof control is scaring. It is the motive behind misinformation that is the dividing line between entertainment and information. Misinformation about elections raises concerns because of important issues that are at stake. Human values are getting relegated to the background. We can't blame the digital tools but the intentions are creating havoc in the society. Today audience is vulnerable, caught in the web of algorithms and echo chambers. Their interest depends on social or political narratives that capture their hopes, dreams, anxiety and disappointments. Narratives may not be accurate but audiences are not bothered. The disruption it causes in social structure has minimized the space for different perspectives. Hate speech, online news portals, and reels operating in the guise of digital freedom reflects social media manipulation eroding ethical norms. Digital literacy, information literacy, and AI literacy are the fundamental skills which along with ethical norms can support human thinking abilities and are the core for establishing digital dignity.

Keywords: *Privacy, data security, misinformation*

References

1. Russell, S. J. (2019). Human compatible: Artificial intelligence and the problem of control. <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BB29043924>
2. Safiya Umoja Noble (2018), Algorithms of Oppression: How Search Engines Reinforce Racism
3. Beever, J., McDaniel, R., & Stanlick, N. A. (2019). Understanding Digital Ethics: Cases and contexts. <https://philpapers.org/rec/BEEUDE>

Media ethics in the digital Sphere: Ethics and Regulations in the 21 century

The technology may change; the people who handle the technology may change from time to time. But ethics are those principles that are universal and remain relevant forever. What is good and what is bad for humanity- this concept cannot be changed because of time and space. That is an eternal value. Values should not change as people change over the years. That is an expectation. But changes are bound to happen is reality.

We are in the digital sphere. Gone are those days when they used to compose text using hands. That was called hand composing. We have come a long way from the era of hand composing. Now everything is at our fingertips. Digital printing has brought in total change in printing technology and media houses as a first step in newspaper offices proofreaders post was abolished and proofreaders were sent home. Then sub editors were asked to learn page design and now there are no more designers in newspaper offices. The reporters and sub editors must do it wherever they are. Now a reporter is not enough if he is proficient in writing, and he knows what news is. It is expected that he should be techno savvy also. Now there is no entry for those who are not proficient in digital technology. The fact we are forgetting is that technology can be learnt in days but the proficiency in language, literature, and the abilities of a journalist cannot come over night. There is a lot of difference in having the knowledge at fingertips and having it in our personality. Unless knowledge becomes wisdom, it is of no use. My concern is, in the name of digital sphere people should not become too much dependent on technology forgetting human values and human essentials.

Recently a thing happened to caution us how AI can be dangerous in the society. It was the days when Kumbha Mela was in full swing. A photo was circulated in all media showing senior actor Prakash Raj taking a dip in Thriveni Sangam of Prayag Raj. For those of us who have followed the actor for long, it was clear that it was a creation of Artificial Intelligence and Prakash Raj might not have gone to the Thriveni Sangam. On enquiry it was found that Prakash Raj was very much in Kerala, and he had not gone to Kumbha Mela at all. This is wholly unethical for the media to misuse digital technology for showing what they want.

Though technology has changed in the 21st Century, media ethics should not change, is my firm belief. The rules and regulations are done by the society for the sake of the society. They also cannot change according to the whims and fancies of the people in power, disrespecting the opinions of the larger community. Digital technology should not make fun of democratic values and should not demean democracy. But if carelessly used it may become dangerous to democracy itself.

That is why I as a media academic support the cause of a system where digital sphere grows but not at the cost of ethics and values of the society.

Prof. Niranjana Vanalli
Professor of Communication
University of Mysore, Karnataka

PANEL 5

Title	Resource Persons
Media and Sociological Transformation Cultural Hybridization and Communication trends for social change	Prof. Srinivas Melkote Prof. Vinod Pavarala Prof. Biswajit Das Prof. B.P. Sanjay Dr. Dhiman Chattopadhyay

MEDIA AND SOCIOLOGICAL TRANSFORMATION

In my discussion, I would like to present a brief historical background to the present scenario we witness today, i.e. the domination of the information scape by social media and the emergence of AI in media information and entertainment. In a mere 45 years since the 1980s, we have seen media systems transform from predominantly national systems to a truly global landscape where the media are multicultural and global in character. How did this transformation occur? While the reasons may be many, I will focus on the changes in media technology as a prime mover and influencer. For most of the 20th Century, people and their cultures were boxed in by their dominant media channels and sources in a information world where top-down communication flows from a dominant source to a passive public prevailed. I will briefly describe how the impressive developments in media technologies, starting in the 1990s, laid the groundwork for a multicultural and global mediascape. The world of the 21st century is no longer such that ideas and products can readily be 'imposed' on other cultures without considerable collaboration and 'glocalization.' Further, the role of the nation state and international trade is changing with the globalization of markets, increased dispersion of cultural interests, and hybridization of content.

I acknowledge the complexity of analyzing media in the context of globalization, characterized by the convergence of various media; the “shrinking” of physical space; the ready circulation of information via digital and social networks; the 'glocalization' of foreign forms to fit local needs and interests; the invention of ever-newer information and communication technologies (ICTs); the rise of mobile and social media, plus their ever-increasing flexibility and accessibility. These realities pose both challenges and opportunities for social change, empowerment and social justice.

**Panel: Media and Sociological Transformation:
Cultural Hybridization and Communication Trends for Social Change**

Cultural hybridization, technological convergence, and shifting communication frameworks are some of the features of the rapid sociological transformation that we are witnessing in the contemporary global media landscape. Processes of urbanisation, migration, transnational flows of people, money, media, and culture (Appadurai 1996) drive these shifts globally as well as in India. These transformations no doubt pose considerable challenges to traditional modes of communication, but simultaneously, they draw attention to the significant role of communication for social change, especially through alternative and community media. I would like to argue in this presentation that despite changes in social structures and cultural flows on a global scale, communication for social change remains indispensable in addressing socio-economic inequalities, fostering participatory democracy, and amplifying marginalized voices. It is in this context that community media, rather than being rendered obsolete, play an increasingly critical role in navigating through the complexities of hybridized cultural and social identities, providing a localized counterpoint to globalized narratives (Rodriguez, 2001).

Prof. Vinod Pavarala,
Senior Professor & UNESCO
Chair on Community Media, UOH
University of Hyderabad

Many sociological transformations in our contemporary society seem to be driven by globalization, digital connectivity, and massive restructuring along the lines of neoliberal economics. A central characteristic of these changes is the process of cultural hybridization, a process where global and local cultural elements merge to form new cultural expressions (Pieterse, 2001). In India, the intersection of traditional and digital communication platforms has led to the coexistence of older cultural practices with newer global media influences. This transformation is visible in linguistic shifts, entertainment preferences, and knowledge-sharing practices, all of which reflect a fusion of globalized digital culture and localized lived experiences (Chadha & Kavoori, 2015).

As Appadurai has pointed out, patterns of migration and transnational labour markets contribute to the diffusion of ideas and communication styles across different socio-economic classes, reshaping how communities interact and engage with media. The increasing penetration of digital platforms has, in many cases, resulted in the commodification of culture, raising concerns about media homogenization (Tomlinson, 1999). However, rather than leading to cultural erasure, these processes often produce hybridized communication forms that integrate traditional oral storytelling, local dialects, and digital content distribution models.

However, despite the digital turn, the central role of communication for social change remains key to fostering awareness, mobilization of marginalised communities, and their empowerment. Theories of participatory communication (Freire, 1970) emphasize the need for horizontal, community-driven approaches to social change rather than top-down, state/market-controlled mechanisms. Digital platforms may have expanded the possibilities for participatory engagement, but the core principles of dialogue, local ownership, and collective action remain integral to effective communication strategies for social change (Gumucio-Dagron, 2001).

In India, grassroots communication forms, such as street theatre, community radio, and folk songs, continue to coexist with the apparent ubiquity of digital technologies, offering a multi-layered approach to addressing issues like gender inequality, caste discrimination, and environmental sustainability (Pavarala & Malik, 2007). The challenge today is ensuring that digital transformations do not silence the voices of those without access to digital resources. Communication strategies that integrate both offline and online methodologies, where possible, could create more inclusive and impactful social change movements.

Community media, particularly community radio, participatory video, alternative print media, and grassroots journalism, play a crucial role in negotiating the tensions between global digital influence and localized communication needs. Unlike corporate media or social media platforms driven by profit motives, community media prioritize collective narratives, local storytelling, and social advocacy (Rodriguez, 2001).

Community radio in India, for example, has been instrumental in democratizing information access for marginalized communities, particularly in rural and semi-urban areas. Community radio stations like Sangham Radio in Telangana, Radio Kotagiri in the Nilgiris, and Radio Dhimsa in Koraput, Odisha strive to facilitate participatory dialogue, preserve indigenous knowledge systems, and serve as platforms for social mobilization (Malik and Pavarala, 2020). Similarly, alternative print media and citizen journalism networks contribute to cultural and political discourse by providing counter-narratives to mainstream news, ensuring that diverse voices are represented in public debates, thereby expanding the possibilities for alternative public spheres.

In an age when we are seeing unprecedented levels of concentration of media ownership and content delivery based on algorithms, community media potentially could function as the bulwark against digital colonialism and for maintenance of local cultural identities. Rather than see the widespread adoption of digital tools as a threat to traditional media, it is prudent to see these technologies as further strengthening the resilience of community media, as community radios have now appropriated new formats such as podcasting, digital storytelling, and hybrid media to effectively combine offline community engagement with online dissemination (Vincent, 2020).

Even as we witness the acceleration of various sociological transformations, communication for social change remains indispensable in addressing systemic inequalities and fostering inclusive development. The processes of cultural hybridization and digitalization present both opportunities and challenges, but rather than rendering community media obsolete, these transformations highlight their continued significance. By embracing both traditional and digital forms of engagement, community-driven communication platforms continue to play a vital role in shaping participatory and democratic media landscapes. Ensuring their sustainability amid digital disruption is imperative for maintaining a diverse, inclusive, and socially conscious media environment.

References

- Appadurai, A. (1996). *Modernity at Large: Cultural Dimensions of Globalization*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Chadha, K., & Kavoori, A. (2015). *Mapping Digital Media: India*. Open Society Foundations.
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. Bloomsbury.
- Gumucio-Dagron, A. (2001). *Making Waves: Stories of Participatory Communication for Social Change*. Rockefeller Foundation.
- Malik K. K. & Pavarala, V., eds. (2020). *Community Radio in South Asia: Reclaiming the Airwaves*. Routledge.
- Pieterse, J. N. (2001). *Globalization and Culture: Global Mélange*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Rodriguez, C. (2001). *Fissures in the Mediascape: An International Study of Citizens' Media*. Hampton Press.
- Tomlinson, J. (1999). *Globalization and Culture*. University of Chicago Press.
- Vincent, R. C. (2020). *Community Media: International Perspectives*. Routledge.

Media and Sociological Transformation in India: Balancing the Transmission Model with Broader Societal Influencesⁱ

The transformative power of media in India has undergone significant evolution since the 1950s, initially framed within the media-centric and modernization paradigm often referred to as the dominant paradigm. This paradigm posited that media could drive societal transformation through the dissemination of information and modern values. However, in the Indian context, the transformative potential of media was constrained by structural issues related to access and equity. The transmission model of information, which emphasized one-way communication from media to the audience, proved inadequate in addressing the diverse and complex needs of Indian society.

Prof. Sanjay Bharthur
Senior Professor,
Manipal Institute of
Communication, MAHE

Experiments such as the Satellite Instructional Television Experiment (SITE) in the 1970s aimed to leverage media for educational and developmental purposes, but the outcomes fell short of expectations. The limitations of the transmission model highlighted the need for more participatory approaches in communication, where the audience is actively engaged in the process. This shift towards participatory communication marked a significant departure from the dominant paradigm, recognizing the importance of inclusivity and affirmative approaches in driving sociological transformation.

Sociological transformation in India has been more effectively realized through continuous efforts towards inclusivity and affirmative action, which the media gradually adopted. These transformations have been identified in tangible terms such as urbanization and migration and intangible such as caste fluidity and individual vs erstwhile community orientation. This transformation encompasses various dimensions, including the empowerment of marginalized communities, the promotion of gender equality, and the fostering of social cohesion. Media has played a crucial role in raising awareness about social issues, mobilizing public opinion, and advocating for policy changes. The advent of the digital ecosystem further promised transformative changes, offering new opportunities for participatory communication and greater access to information. Measurement of such changes poses a complex challenge given the magnitude and diversity of the country.

However, this digital transformation is not without challenges. Issues such as monopolies in communication platforms, agenda setting, and the engineering and moulding of public opinion pose significant obstacles. These challenges underscore the need for vigilance and regulation to ensure that the transformative potential of media is not undermined by concentrated power and biased narratives. Additionally, the digital divide remains a critical issue, with disparities in access to digital technologies and internet connectivity affecting the equitable distribution of information and opportunities. Despite these advancements, gaps persist, and the cycle of inclusion remains a topic of debate in larger academic and policy circles.

The modernization paradigm in India has been characterized by a complex interplay between tradition and modernity. While modernization has driven economic growth and technological advancements, it has also led to significant social changes, including urbanization, industrialization, and shifts in cultural norms. India's cultural diversity, encompassing various languages, religions, and traditions, adds another layer of complexity to the sociological transformation. This diversity has both enriched the media landscape and posed challenges in ensuring equitable representation and access.

Telecom and media monopolies in India have further complicated the landscape. The concentration of power in a few large corporations has led to issues of agenda-setting and opinion moulding, where the interests of these entities can influence public discourse and policy decisions. The lack of inclusion in media sector jobs remains a significant challenge, with marginalized communities often underrepresented. Efforts to promote diversity and inclusion in the media workforce are ongoing, but progress has been slow and uneven.

In conclusion, while the media-centric paradigm of the 1950s laid the groundwork for understanding the transformative potential of media, it is the participatory and inclusive approaches that have driven meaningful sociological transformation in India. Tangible and intangible sociological transformations have not necessarily impacted economic inequity as the recent Oxfam report indicates the chasm between the small percentage that owns the bulk of the nation's wealth and many others who do not. The digital ecosystem presents both opportunities and challenges, necessitating a nuanced approach to harness its transformative power effectively. The ongoing sociological transformation in India highlights the dynamic interplay between media, society, and technology, and the need for continuous adaptation to address emerging challenges and leverage new opportunities.

¹ Invited paper and presentation for Two-Day international conference Reimagining Communication In the 21st Century: Sociological, Political, and Economic Perspectives, Postgraduate Department of Journalism and Mass Communication St. Philomena's College (Autonomous) Mysuru, March 20-21. 2025.

**Panel: Media and Sociological Transformation:
Cultural Hybridization and Communication trends for social change**

Cultural hybridization is transforming journalism, and all related communication – blending global and local influences to reshape how news is consumed, produced, and shared. Today's youth, especially college students, are at the forefront of this shift, navigating a media landscape that fuses traditional mass communication with digital storytelling, social media, multilingual content and AI-generated content. Platforms like TikTok, YouTube, and even student-run media outlets exemplify this hybridization, integrating global perspectives into campus journalism and blending generational and other forms of culture to communicate in ways not seen before. In other areas such as politics and social activism, hybrid media and communication styles are being used such as livestreams, hashtags, and podcasts, to drive social change.

Prof. Dhiman Chattopadhyay
Associate Professor,
Shippensburg University, USA
Former Editor, TOI & Mid-Day.com

Of course, like with any powerful tool, we must be mindful of challenges such as misinformation, and ethical dissemination of content. Journalists and communication professionals in general play a pivotal role in shaping our understanding of the world. Among other things, this panel will explore how hybridized content is redefining information sharing, storytelling, and what this means for the broader media landscape in an era of rapid digital and cultural convergence.

FIRST DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

**DAY 1 - VENUE: ROOM NO - 52, 2nd Floor PG Block
20th Thursday, March 2025, 04:30 PM Onwards**

**Sociological Perspective
Media Representation and Identity**

**Moderator - Dr. Nithya Prakash
Associate Professor, Jindal School of Psychology & Counselling, Haryana**

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	"The Representation of Cross-Cultural Communication in Contemporary OTT Platforms"	Amaljith N.K (Assistant Professor, Department of Visual Communication, Kalasalingam Academy of Research and Education, Krishnan Kovil, Tamil Nadu) amaljithravi245@gmail.com	Dr. Gnana D Hans Assistant Professor, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu	NIL
2	"Representation of Queerness in Media: The Effect of Identity and Gender Roles in LGBTIQ Spaces"	Ameya Das Student of BA (Hons) Media and Communication Nitte Institute of Communication, Nitte (Deemed to Be University)" ameyadas07@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
3	"Portrayal of Women In Bollywood Horror Films In The Last Five Years"	ANWESHA SINGHA, Student, Department of Media and Communication Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore. anvesha.singha@mamcs.christuniversity.in	Vikash Chauhan, Assistant Professor, CHRIST (Deemed to be University) Bangalore Central Campus	NIL
4	"Male-saviour complex as a central narrative in the depiction of sexual violence against children and women: An analysis of the movies Chitha and Maharaja"	Epciba I Ph.D. Scholar Mass Communication Affiliation: Pondicherry University, Puducherry epcibloom@pondiuni.ac.in krithika_ks@yahoo.co.in	Dr. K.S. Krithika Associate Professor Visual Communication Affiliation: Pondicherry University Community College, Puducherry"	NIL
5	"Portrayal of Sex Workers in South Indian Cinema"	Roshni Rajagopal, Research Scholar, Christ University, Bangalore sc24pmac003@mahindrauniversity.edu.in	NIL	NIL
6	"Gender Dynamics in K Balachander's Telugu Cinema- An empirical study"	S. Sujatha, Research Scholar, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, Osmania University, Hyderabad. Sujathaphdfilmstudies@Gmail.Com	NIL	NIL
7	"Web of Lies: New Media's Role in Propagating Misinformation Explored through Qualitative Analysis"	J. Karpagaraj I Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli. karpagarajikraj@gmail.com , vsundararaman@gmail.com	Dr V. Sundararaman Assistant Professor, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli.	NIL
8	"Wicked Women and Moral Dilemmas: Characterization of Antagonist Female Characters in Malayalam Cinema"	Soumya P, School of Digital Media and Communication, Mahindra University, Hyderabad soumyaraj189@gmail.com algalbin14@gmail.com	Alga Albin, School of Digital Media and Communication, Mahindra University, Hyderabad	NIL

FIRST DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

DAY 1 - VENUE: ROOM NO - 54, 2nd Floor PG Block

20th Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards

**Sociological Perspective
Digital Media, Culture, Youth & Society**

**Moderator - Dr. Prashanth Venugopal
Head of the department, Journalism & Mass Communication, St. Pauls College, Bengaluru.**

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	"Integration of Digital Platforms in Mobile Theatre of Assam"	Darshana Das Ph. D. Research Scholar, Department of Electronic Media and Mass Communication, Pondicherry University, Puducherry. Email: darshudas143@pondiuni.ac.in	NIL	NIL
2	"Role of New Media (OTT Platforms) in Cultural Hybridization"	Lagashetti Priyanka Chandrakant Research Scholar Dept. of Mass Communication, P.A.H. Solapur University, Solapur, Maharashtra. lagashettipriyanka@gmail.com rbchincholkar@gmail.com	Dr. Ravindra Chincholkar Research Guide Former Head of Dept. of Mass Communication, P.A.H. Solapur University, Solapur, Maharashtra	NIL
3	"Exploring Cultural Identity through Vehicles Graffiti among the youth in Tirunelveli"	M. Benny, I MA Student, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli. benny2720@gmail.com	S. G. Veeralakshmanan, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli.	Dr. G. Balasubramania Raja 3, Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli.
4	"Cultural Flaunt: A Study on The Cultural Expressions Through New Media Among Tirunelveli's Youth"	S.G. Veeralakshmanan Research Scholar Department of Communication Manonmaniam Sundaranar University Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India. Mail Id: sgveera96@gmail.com , Mail Id: gbs_raja@yahoo.com	Dr. G. Balasubramania Raja Professor and Head Department of Communication Manonmaniam Sundaranar University Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India	NIL
5	"The Role of New Media in Cultural Hybridization: Transforming Lifestyles"	Tamizhanban R. M. Ph.D. Scholar Department of Communication Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu tamizhanban1721@gmail.com gnanadhans@msuniv.ac.in	Dr. Gnana D Hans Assistant Professor Department of Communication Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu	NIL
6	"The Impact of Internet and Digital Media on Reading Habit of Degree Students"	Suvarna Kambi Assistant Professor JSS College of Arts, Commerce and Science Ooty Road, Mysore, Karnataka, India. suvarnakambi007@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
7	"Selective use of digital media Technology for life and living, on Nomadic Communities Study on Intrinsic and extraneous factors contributing to selective use of technology among narikuravar community"	V. Venkatesh Doctorial Research Scholar Department of Communication Manonmaniam Sundaranar University Tirunelveli-627011 Tamil Nadu venkatvijaykumar05@gmail.com	Dr. Gnana D Hans, Assistant professor, Department of communication Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli-627011 Tamil Nadu	NIL
8	"Visual Content Analysis of Advertising Messages of Indian FMCG Brands with Special Reference to Emami, Patanjali, and Dabur"	Sakshi Agarwal Postgraduate Student, (M.A. Media and Communication Studies) CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru sakshi.agarwal@mamcs.christuniversity.in	Dr. Shantharaju S, Associate Professor, Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru	NIL
9	"Anti-Hero Attraction Among Kerala's Youth: Analysis of Aavesham"	SYAM C, M.A. Mass Communication, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur svamc2000@gmail.com	Dr. Shamala Ramappa, Assistant Professor, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur.	NIL

FIRST DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

**DAY 1 - VENUE: ROOM NO - 56, 2nd Floor PG Block
20th Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards**

**Sociological Perspective
Health and Well-being**

**Moderator - Prof. Mamatha N
Chairperson, Dept, of Journalism & Mass Communication, University of Mysuru**

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	"Emotional Well-being in Pregnancy in Malayalam Cinema: Media Impact on Public Perception and Maternal Health-Seeking"	Aparna Jayabal P Registration Number: 2337214 Under the Supervision of Professor Dr. Melio Thomas Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to Be University), Bengaluru aparnajayabal12@gmail.com	Melio Thomas, Professor, Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru	NIL
2	"User Generated Content's impact on Health Communication Misinformation"	Ishanvi Sharma Assistant Professor, NMKRV College For Women, Jayanagar ishanvirsharma@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
3	"The psychological and emotional challenges faced by women with PCOS, along with potential ways media could provide support and education"	Madhurima Basak Department of Media and Communication Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to Be University) Bangalore Central Campus madhurimabasak378@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
4	"Bangalore Psychoeducation: Comparing Individual and Group Approaches Across Mental Health and Academic Settings"	Rupsa Roy, Student, Department of Media and Communication Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore. rupsaroypg@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
5	"Understanding the nuances of information overload with respect to personal health and social well-being"	S. Augustin Jesuvadian Research Scholar mailto:augustinaj05@gmail.com	Dr. Gnana D Hans, Assistant Professor, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu	NIL
6	"AI in Emotional Support: why do youngsters seek emotional support from AI chatbots?"	Preethika S., M.A. Mass Communication, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavur. preethikasambantham@gmail.com	Gondi Surender Dhanunjay, Research Fellow, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavur.	Dr. Shamala Ramappa, Assistant Professor, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavur.
7	"Dopamine Loops and Player Retention: A Study on Reinforcement in Free-To-Play Games"	Sarvajith Kumar J N, Assistant Professor, Department of Management, Cresta First Grade College, Mysuru, Karnataka – 570028. sarvajithjn@gmail.com	Manohar N, Assistant Professor, Department of Journalism, Government First Grade College for Women, M G Road, Hassan, Karnataka	NIL
8	"Information abundance in digital era"	Ishika Ladda, MA Media Governance, Sem IV at Centre for Culture, Media and Governance, Jamia Millia Islamia University, Delhi mailto:ishikaladdawork@gmail.com	NIL	NIL

FIRST DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

DAY 1 - VENUE: ROOM NO - 57, 2nd Floor PG Block

20th Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards

**Economic Perspective
Economic Development and Inclusion**

**Moderator - Dr. Navitha Thimmaiah
Professor in Economics & Chairperson, University of Mysuru**

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	"Corporate Social Responsibility in Mitigating Perception of Company Crisis: Understanding Corporate and Public Perception"	Anindita Bhattacharya, Student, Department of Media and Communication Studies, CHRIST (Deemed-To-Be University), Bangalore. anindita.bhattacharya@mams.christuniversity.in	Dr Suparna Naresh, Associate Professor, Department of Media Studies, School of Arts and Humanities, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore	NIL
2	"Corporate Social Responsibility in Sustainable Agriculture Through the Lens of The Stakeholders"	Gouri S Dev, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore. sdevgouri@gmail.com	Jayaprakash C R, Associate Professor and Head, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore."	Nithyanandhan S, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.
3	"The Impact of Digital Inclusion on Economic Development"	H. S. Chandrashekhara Kale Assistant Professor, Department of Economics Government First Grade College Navanagar, Bagalkot. chandrashekhara.kale@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
4	"From Digital Adoption to Economic Dominance: India's Path to Vikasit Bharat"	Madhu G R Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Shri Siddeshwara Government First Grade College and P G Studies Centre, Nargund, Gadag, Karnataka. madhu.rajgowda01@gmail.com , pkduragesh@gmail.com	Duragesh Pujari Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Shri Siddeshwara Government First Grade College and P G Studies Centre, Nargund, Gadag, Karnataka.	NIL
5	"Direct Benefit Transfer: A Catalyst for Digital and Financial Inclusion in India"	Kempe Gowda G N, Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Government First Grade College for Women, Byrapura, T Narasipura Mail: gowdak94@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
6	"Communication in Financial Literacy and Economic Development"	Rudrappa K.M M. A. M.Phil. B. Ed Associate Professor. GFGC Davangere Email: rudrappakm65@gmail.com	Prof. Veerabhadrapa B.P M.A. Ph.D. Former Vice-Chancellor. Kuvempu University Shivamogga. Karnataka	NIL
7	"The Role of Strategic Communication in Advancing the Bioeconomy: A Socioeconomic Perspective"	Satya Prasad Professor & Head of Institution Nitte Institute of Communication NITTE Deemed to be University archan.mitra@nitte.edu.in	Dr. Archan Mitra Assistant Professor Nitte Institute of Communication NITTE Deemed to be University	NIL
8	"Investigating Consumer Trust and Purchase Intentions in Influencer Marketing of Health Products on Instagram"	Rishika V. Bujurke Student, Department of Media Studies Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore rishika.bujurke24@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
9	"Can the flipped classroom be used as a reiterative method to promote learners' learning engagement?"	Dr. Shilaja, Assistant Professor, Department of English, Stella Maris College, Chennai shilaja@stellamariscollege.edu.in , jevapriva@stellamariscollege.edu.in	Jeyapriya U, Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science, Stella Maris College, Chennai	NIL

FIRST DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

**DAY 1 - VENUE: ROOM NO - Glass Room (Food & Nutrition), 3rd Floor PG Block
20th Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards**

**Political Perspective
Political Communication, Media, and Public Opinion**

**Moderator - Dr. Shamala Ramappa
Assistant Professor, Media & Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu**

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	"Topical Preference in The Tweets of Indian Political Leaders: A Case Study of Lok Sabha Elections, 2024"	Ashwini Ramesh Faculty, Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, Bengaluru City University Karnataka, India. ashwini.ramesh95@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
2	"Role of Social Media in Setting Political Agenda: An Overview"	Hemalatha R., Assistant Professor, DOSR in Journalism and Mass Communication, Karnataka State Open University, Mysuru -06 nallahalli.@gmail.com, paswan.adarsh@gmail.com	Mr. Adarsh Paswan, Research Scholar, DOSR in Journalism and Mass Communication, Karnataka State Open University, Mysuru -06	NIL
3	"Youtube's Algorithms and Caste-Based Political Polarization Among Urban Voters in Samastipur During The 2024 Lok Sabha Elections"	Kumari Shikha, M.A. Mass Communication, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvaur. Shikhavadav7667@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
4	"The Influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-Generated Content on Misinformation Dissemination During Parliamentary Election Campaign (2024)"	Madhan K. Teaching Assistant Department of Visual Communication & Electronic Media P.S.G. College of arts and science Coimbatore madhan@psgcas.ac.in hodvisualcommunicationua@psgcas.ac.in	Dr Radha G. Associate Professor & Head of Department Department of Visual Communication & Electronic Media P.S.G. College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore	NIL
5	"Uncovering Agendas: Critical Discourse Analysis of UAPA Narratives in Indian Online News Portals"	Sarang K, Research scholar, Department of electronic media and mass communication, Pondicherry University mailto:cmrdsarane999@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
6	"Cultural Sensitivity in Political Communication"	PRERANA SINGH, Student, Department of Media and Communication Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore. prerana.singh@mamcs.christuniversity.in, thepreranasingh@gmail.com	Dr Naresh Rao, Professor, Department of Media Studies, School of Arts and Humanities, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore	NIL
7	"Navigating the Digital Frontier: Insights into Voter Perception and Campaign Strategies in The 2024 Lok Sabha Elections"	Priya Evangeline Freelance Content Creator Mysuru, Karnataka. mailto:priyaevangeline56@gmail.com	Dr. Vagdevi H S Assistant Professor, Dept. of Post Graduate Studies and Research in Journalism and Mass Communication, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Mysuru, Karnataka."	NIL
8	"India's Stance on The Tibetan Crisis: Insights from Parliamentary Debates"	Shreeraj Gudi, Assistant Professor, Manipal Institute of Communication, MAHE Manipal shreeraj.gudi@manipal.edu srijankishor@pondiuni.ac.in srijankishor@gmail.com	Dr Padma Rani, Professor and Director, Manipal Institute of Communication, MAHE Manipal padma.rani@manipal.edu,	Dr Nanda Kishor, Professor and HOD, Department of Politics and International Relations, Pondicherry University
9	"A Typology of The Roles Assigned to Civil Society Organisations as News Sources"	Varsha M. Joseph Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru varsha.joseph@res.christuniversity.in aasita.bali@christuniversity.in	Dr. Aasita Bali Associate Professor, Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru	NIL

FIRST DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

DAY 1 - VENUE: ROOM NO - MBA Conference Hall, 2nd Floor PG Block

20th Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards

Political Perspective

Community, Development, and Environment

Moderator - Prof. Sapna M S

Director - EMRC, Professor, Dept. of JMC, University of Mysuru

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	“Social Inclusion and Poverty Eradication Under Targeted Public Distribution System in India”	Basavanagowda T, Academician, Sri D Devaraj urs first grade College, Davangere basudvg2012@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
2	“Assessing the Role of New Media in Creating Awareness on Effective Waste Management among Rural Populations”	Iswarya K Research Scholar, Reg. No: 241140109002 Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu iswaryakarthiskeyankdm@gmail.com gbs_rajaa@yahoo.com	Dr G Balasubramania Raja Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu	NIL
3	“Addressing Climate Change Through News Media: Local Events Matter”	Jayaprakash. C.R, Associate Professor & Head, Dept. of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. Email: jayaprakash@psgcas.ac.in	Nithyanandan, Research Scholars, Dept. of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.	Gouri S. Dev, Research Scholars, Dept. of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.
4	“Digital Media and Interactive Storytelling: A New Paradigm for Communicating and Achieving Socioeconomic Change”	Jebakumar M Assistant Professor, Department of Visual Communication, St. Xavier’s College (Autonomous), Palayamkottai – 627002, Tamil Nadu, India jebakumarm@gmail.com .	NIL	NIL
5	“Impact of E- Governance in Scheduled Tribes in Telangana-Study”	Komraiah Palamakula, Senior Research Scholar, Department of Public Administration, Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana, India, Email: palamakulakomuraiah@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
6	“Toward Inclusive Radio Journalism in India: A Case for Democratizing News in India”	Mochish Ks, Academician, Flame University, Pune mailto:mochish@flame.edu.in	NIL	NIL
7	“Communication Strategies During Disaster by Community Radio”	Mousami Jena, Research scholar, Dept. of Electronic Media & Mass Communication, Pondicherry University jena.mousami@pondiuni.ac.in	NIL	NIL
8	“Upholding Culture, Empowering the Community: Exploring ‘Agroforestry’ as a Development Model for Dongria Kondh in Niyamgiri, Odisha”	Sanskar Behera AJK MCRC, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi MA Development Communication behera.sanskar2019@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
9	“Social Media as a Catalyst for Grassroots Activism in E-Waste Management: Exploring Communication Strategies”	Sharada T Assistant Professor, NMKRV College for Women, Jayanagar, Sharada.nmkrv@rvei.edu.in	NIL	NIL

SECOND DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

DAY 2 - VENUE: ROOM NO - 52, 2nd Floor PG Block

21st Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards

**Sociological Perspective
Communication, Perception, and Influence**

**Moderator - Dr. Nithya Prakash
Associate Professor, Jindal School of Psychology & Counselling, Haryana**

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	“Communication Strategies Employed During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Karnataka.”	Abhisheka. M.P Assistant Professor & HOD, Dept. of Social Work. Bharathi College – PG & RC, Bharathinagara abhimswns30@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
2	“Decoding the AI Hype Cycle Through LinkedIn: A Social Listening Analysis of Industry Narratives and Public Perception”	Allan Harold Rex Research Scholar, School of Media Studies, Mahindra University Email ID: allanharoldrex@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
3	“Media as a tool in Nation-building”	Anand C, Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science, St. Philomena’s College (Autonomous), Mysore-15 anandc@stphilos.ac.in	NIL	NIL
4	“Communicating Sustainability through Green Advertising: Analysing its Effectiveness in Shaping Consumer Perception”	Anjali Rai Research Scholar Nitte Institute of Communication Nitte (DU) Email id: anishakumaran@nitte.edu.in	Anisha Associate Professor Nitte Institute of Communication Nitte (DU) Email id: anjairai99@gmail.com	NIL
5	“Public Trust in The Age of User-Generated Content: Analysing Digital News Credibility”	Garima Gunawat Assistant Professor, NIMCJ, Ahmedabad, Gujarat. Garimagunawat24@gmail.com	Dr. Shirish Kashikar, Director, NIMCJ, Ahmedabad, Gujarat	NIL
6	“Emotion-Driven Engagement: A Sentiment Analysis on How Emotion Works in Sustainability Instagram Influencers’ Posts”	Nithiyandhan Soundarajan, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore. 22pmcf01@psgcas.ac.in	Jayaprakash C R, Head, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.	Gouri S Dev, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.
7	“Real-Time Challenges in The Appropriation and Actualisation of Information in Digital Media Applications”	Sanjai R, Post Graduate Student, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu sanjai31sanjay@gmail.com	Veeralakshmanan G, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu	Tamizhanban R M, Research Scholar Dr G Balasubramanian Raja, Professor and Head Dr Gnana D Hans, Assistant Professor Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu
8	“Understanding Information Consumption Behaviour and Media Selection Among Millennial and Gen-X In The 21 st Era: A Comparative Study”	Swarnali Dutta, Supervisor – PR, Fortis Hospital Anandapur, Kolkata. swarnalidutta.sdutta@gmail.com , venugopalgowdamk@stphilis.ac.in	Dr. Venugopal Gowda M K, HOD, Assistant Professor, Post Graduate and Research Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, St. Philomena’s College (Autonomous), Mysuru, Karnataka.	NIL

SECOND DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

**DAY 2 - VENUE: ROOM NO - 54, 2nd Floor PG Block
21st Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards**

**Sociological Perspective
Audiences, Ethics, Digital Life and Fact-Checking**

**Moderator - Dr. Shamala Ramappa
Assistant Professor, Media & Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu**

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	“One Joke, Many Lives: Examining the Digital Transformation of Stand-Up Comedy Through Multi-Platform Performance Analysis”	Anthony Christon J Research Scholar, Christ university, Bangalore anthony.christon@res.christuniversity.in	NIL	NIL
2	“Understanding the Audience of Mano Community Radio in the Digital Age”	Eramani Surya M Research Scholar, Reg. No: 2421401092001 Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu. eramanisuryam0209@gmail.com gbs_raja@yahoo.com	Dr. G. Balasubramania Raja, Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu.	NIL
3	“Exploring the Devotion, Participatory, and Promotional Fan Culture of Thalapathy Vijay Makkal Iyakkam (ஜயமக்கள் இயக்கம்) in Thiruvarur District, Tamil Nadu.”	Harini Dineshkumar, M.A. Mass Communication, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur. harinidineshkumar3015@gmail.com	Gondi Surender Dhanunjay, Research Fellow, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur.	Dr. Shamala Ramappa, Assistant Professor, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur.
4	“The Impact of YouTube & User-Generated Content: Analysing Children’s Viewing Habits and Parental Mediation”	Kokhila R Research Scholar Department of Communication Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli kokhila22896@gmail.com gbs_raja@yahoo.com	Dr. G. Balasubramania Raja Professor and Head Department of Communication Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli	NIL
5	“From Creators to Consumers: How User-Generated Content shapes College Students’ Purchase Intention”	Rajeshwari N Research Scholar, Mother Teresa Women’s University. rajeshwari.n26@gmail.com vesnaj20@gmail.com	Dr. Lourdu Vesna J, Asst Prof. of Visual Communication Dept, Mother Teresa Women’s University.	NIL
6	“Digital Media Ethics: A Note on Indian Legal System”	Rangaswamy D. Assistant Professor of Law Karnataka State Law University Karnataka, India ksludrdrswamy@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
7	“Proliferation of Crime-Narratives in Indian Podcast: A Qualitative Analysis of Two National and Two Regional Podcast Channels Narrating True Crime Stories”	Reetuparna Bhattacharjee, Research Scholar, Mahindra University sc24pmac003@mahindrauniversity.edu.in	NIL	NIL
8	“A Study on Online Privacy Awareness Among Adolescents”	S Ajantha Thamayanthi Baylis, Assistant Professor (T), Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu ajanthasanjit@gmail.com gbs_raja@yahoo.com	Dr G Balasubramania Raja, Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu	NIL

SECOND DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

**DAY 2 - VENUE: ROOM NO - 56, 2nd Floor PG Block
21st Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards**

**Sociological Perspective
New Arenas and New Scapes: Redefining Media**

**Moderator - Prof. Shirish Kashikar
Director, NIMCJ, Ahmedabad, Gujarat**

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	“Redefining Heroines: The Women of Mani Ratnam's World”	Maduvanathi. S, Postgraduate Student, SATHYABAMA UNIVERSITY, Chennai srividhyamadu5@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
2	“Portrayals of Housewives: The Paradox in Contemporary Indian Web Series”	Dr. Malavika Sunil Karippara, Assistant Professor, Department of Visual Communication, Kumaraguru College of Liberal Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu malavikasunilk@gmail.com , francis@cutn.ac.in ,	Dr. Francis P. Barclay, Assistant Professor, Department of Media and Communication School of Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu	NIL
3	“Reporting Climate Change in West Bengal: A Comparative Study of Anandabazar Patrika and Bartaman In 2023”	Sirsha Chakraborty, Postgraduate Student, Department of Media and Communication Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), India sirsha.chakraborty@mamcs.christuniversity.in	NIL	NIL
4	“Representation Of Desires and Intimacy: Cinematic Characterisation of The Disabled”	Dr. Devika P. Assistant Professor, Kumaraguru College of Liberal Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. malavikasunilk@gmail.com , vikram.devikal@gmail.com ,	Dr. Malavika Sunil Karippara Assistant Professor, Kumaraguru College of Liberal Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.	NIL
5	“The Impact of Legacy Media: Creative Posters to Foster Youth Mental Health and Social Responsibility”	R. Vasantharaj, Research Scholar, Dept. of Electronic Media & Mass Communication, Pondicherry University vasantharaj.scholar@pondiuni.ac.in	Dr. V. Shanthi Siri, Dept. of Electronic Media & Mass Communication, Pondicherry University	NIL
6	“Medium Is the Message: Revisiting Marshall McLuhan”	Dr. Poarkodi Natarajan Academician, Srmist, Kattankulathur, Chennai poarkodi@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
7	“Legacy Media: Navigating the Challenge of Disengagement and Distrust in News in The Digital Age”	Dr. Swati Bakshi, Researcher (Independent), Centre for Research and Education in Art and Media (CREAM), University of Westminster, United Kingdom swatibakshi11@gmail.com ,	NIL	NIL
8	“Location Specific Content: A Crucial Tool for Climate Action Communication at Grassroots Level”	Sirasani Anilkumar, Ph.D. Scholar in Mass Communication, School of Media and Communication, Pondicherry University, Puducherry anilvarma771@pondiuni.ac.in ,	NIL	NIL

SECOND DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

**DAY 2 - VENUE: ROOM NO - 57, 2nd Floor PG Block
21st Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards**

**Economic Perspective
Digital Economy, Labor Dynamics, and Consumer Behaviour**

**Moderator - Dr. Navitha Thimmaiah
Professor in Economics & Chairperson, University of Mysuru**

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	“Measuring How Blockchain Ai-Powered Communication Technologies Affect the Productivity of Distant Workers Economically”	HARINI.S II MCA Student, St. Philomena’s College, Mysore, India. Harinipreethi686@Gmail.Com	NIL	NIL
2	“Digital Transformation and Employment Shifts: A Study on India's Gig Economy Evolution”	Manasa H, Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Maharani’s Arts College for Women, JLB, Road, Mysore Mail: Manasacoll03@Gmail.Com	NIL	NIL
3	“Delivery Gig Workers: A Study on Instagram Representation”	K Nighil Nandhaa Master’s Student Department of Media Studies CHRIST (Deemed to Be University), Central Campus, Bangalore, India Email: Nighilnandhaa@Gmail.Com	NIL	NIL
4	“The Gig Economy, Digital Communication and Economic Challenges in India: Examining Quick Commerce”	Samriddhi Srivastava, Student, BA in Communication and Psychology, Department of Media Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore Yeshwanthpur Campus, Bangalore. Divyakumari.Kp@Christuniversity.in	Tanya Shukla, Student, Ba in Communication and Psychology, Department of Media Studies, Christ (Deemed to Be University), Bangalore Yeshwanthpur Campus, Bangalore	Dr. Divya Kumari K P, Assistant Professor, Department of Media Studies, Christ (Deemed to Be University), Bangalore Yeshwanthpur Campus, Bangalore,
5	“Agricultural Labourers in Karnataka – Trends and Problems”	Nagarathamma. K. S., Asst. Prof. Department of sociology, KRCEs’s GGD Arts, BMP Commerce & SVS Science College, Bailhongal – 591102 Rani channamma University, Belagavi. prashanth101089@gmail.com	Dr. M. Prashanth, Faculty, Department of Sociology, Maharaja’s College, University of Mysore, Mysuru	NIL
6	“An Exploratory Study on Voice Assistants Technology in Digital Payment Apps: A Cross-Sectional Study Among Retail Merchants in Bangalore”	Vamsha Shetty A, Ph.D. Research scholar, Department of Electronic Media, Bangalore University, Bangalore. Email: vamshashetty0103@gmail.com vahinias@gmail.com	Dr. Vahini Aravind, Associate Professor, Department of Electronic Media, Bangalore University, Bangalore.	NIL
7	“A Holistic Analysis of Gender Inequality And Pay Gap In Indian Cinema And Media”	Mythili Nair Postgraduate Student Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed To Be University) Bengaluru. mythilimadan.nair@mamcs.christuniversity.in	Dr. Vikas Chauhan, Postgraduate Student Media Studies, Christ (Deemed to Be University) Bengaluru.	NIL
8	“Indian Cinema and Hegemony: An Analysis Of Labour Narratives In Post-Colonial India”	Vikas Pathe Symbiosis International (Deemed University), Pune, India Pathe.Vikas@Gmail.Com	NIL	NIL
9	“The Evolution and Significance of Film Organizations: Analysing the Historical Perspective and Assessment of Merging Institutions Under the Umbrella of NFDC with the New Film Policy Focusing on Film Division Particularly.”	Pushkar J, Department of Media Studies Christ (Deemed to Be University), Bangalore summerrainpictures@gmail.com	NIL	NIL

SECOND DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - OFFLINE)

DAY 2 - VENUE: ROOM NO - MBA Conference Hall, 2nd Floor PG Block

21st Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards

**Political Perspective
Governance, Law, Socio-Economic Change, and Political Discourse**

Moderator - Dr. Shantharaju S

Associate Professor, Department of Media Studies, Christ University, Bengaluru

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	“Unity, Nationalism, And Controversy: A Study of Political Communication on Twitter by Indian Politicians During India-Pakistan Cricket Encounters (2019-2024)”	Spandan Khimani, Postgraduate Student, Department Of Media and Communication Studies, Christ (Deemed to Be University), Bangalore. Khimanispanan.Parthbhaj@Mamcs.Christuniiversity.In	NIL	NIL
2	“Unmasking The Face: Political Face-Work Of Regional Actors Through Emerging Forms Of Media”	Sourav Karthikeyan, Research scholar, Department of English and Cultural Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore sourav.karthikeyan@res.christuniversity.in arya.aiyappan@christuniversity.in	Dr Arya Aiyappan, Associate Professor, Department of English and Cultural Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to Be University), Bangalore	NIL
3	“Exploring Misinformation And Disinformation In The 2024 Lok Sabha Elections: A Qualitative Study Surrounding BJP And INC”	SHERIL A Student of MA Media & Communication Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University) BENGALURU. sheril.a@mamcs.christuniversity.in	Dr Melio Thomas Assistant Professor Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to Be University) BENGALURU	NIL
4	“Digital Media in Public Administration in India: A Critical Review”	Somashekara C L, Working Professional, University of Mysore, Mysuru shekargowda.c.l.2012@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
5	"The Influence of Social Media Content on Public Perception of Political News"	Shwetha P.B, Assistant Professor, NMKRV College For Women Shwethavibhareddy@Gmail.Com	NIL	NIL
6	“Effective Communication Strategies for Socio-Economic Change”	Sundresh K C, Assistant Professor & HOD, Department of Sociology, Bharathi College, (Autonomous), Bharathinagara. Email: Sundreshgowda86@Gmail.Com	NIL	NIL
7	“From Tradition to Digital: Transmitting Jogatti Folk Narratives Through Digitalstorytelling in the 21st Century.”	Sanjana Suukyi M P, PhD Scholar at IIT Dharwad. hs24dp001@iitdh.ac.in , ridhima@iitdh.ac.in	Dr. Ridhima Tewari, Associate Professor, IIT Dharwad.	NIL
8	“Analysing The Development of A Resilient Fact-Checking Ecosystem: Understanding Collaborative Approaches To Fact-Checking For Analysing Efforts To Combat Information Warfare”	Y Sravan Kumar, Research Scholar, IGNOU, New Delhi. ssravan.mahi@gmail.com , glen4dsilva@gmail.com	Glen D’silva, Research Scholar, Mahindra University, Hyderabad, Telangana.	NIL

SECOND DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - ONLINE)

DAY 2 - ROOM NO - Glass Room (Food & Nutrition), 3rd Floor PG Block

20th Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards

**“Media, Communication, and Society in the Digital Age:
Interdisciplinary Perspectives on India”**

Moderator - Prof. Mamatha N

Chairperson, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication , University of Mysore

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
1	“Analysing The Influence of Instagram on Food Culture and Dietary Habits Among Young Students in Higher Academics in West Bengal”	Ruma Saha, Assistant Professor, Department of Media Science and Journalism, Brain Ware University, Kolkata, India ruma.saha.kolkata@gmail.com	Debabani Mukherjee, Assistant Professor, Department of Media Science and Journalism, Brainware University, Kolkata, India.	Smita Singh, Doctoral Research Scholar, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, Manipal University Jaipur, Rajasthan, India
2	“Examining The Tamil Cultural Context: A Qualitative Study of Genz from The State Of Tamil Nadu”	Akshaya Sri S, Postgraduate Student, Flame University, Tamil Nadu Akshaya.Sri@Flame.Edu.In	NIL	NIL
3	“The Power of Memes in Digital Communication: Bridging Humour, Emotion, and Social Activism in Online Communities During Election”	Dr P Sri Jothi, Assistant Professor, Department Of Media Sciences, CEG Anna University, Chennai. Tamilnadu. India.Srijothidms@Gmail.Com	Dr M Thulasi Bharathy, Assistant Professor, Department of Animation, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies. Chennai. Tamil Nadu. India.	NIL
4	“Education without Boundaries: Breaking Socioeconomic Barriers to Inclusion”	Radha Gupta Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Shri Ratanlal Kanwarlal Patni Girls’ College, Kishangarh (Raj.) radhagupta2000@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
5	“Political Information as Political Currency: Redefining Political Engagements on Cyberspace”	Namit Vikram Singh Faculty, Delhi School of Journalism, University of Delhi," Nams.Namit@Dsj.Du.Ac.In , Drdurgeshtripathi@Ipu.Ac.In	Prof. (Dr.) Durgesh Tripathi Head, University School of Mass Communication GGSSIP University,	NIL
6	“Exploring The Role of Online Platforms in Building Learning Communities: A Case Study of Krishna Kanta Handiqui State Open University”	Trisha Dowerah Baruah Assistant Professor Bhupen Hazarikia School Of Mass Communication Krishna Kanta Handiqui State Open University Guwahati-781022 Trishabaruah@Kkhsou.In	NIL	NIL
7	“A Walk Through the Sacred Grove in Northeast India: Oral Narratives and Environment Conservation”	Monalisha Medhi, Assistant Professor, The Assam Royal Global University Mmedhi1@Rgu.Ac	NIL	NIL
8	“The Power Play: Political Influence and The Erosion of Media Freedom”	G Vasanth Associate Professor & Head Department of Visual Communication D G Vaishnav College, Tamil Nadu Drvasanthgopal@Gmail.Com	NIL	NIL

SECOND DAY PAPER PRESENTATION (MODE - ONLINE)

DAY 2 - ROOM NO - Glass Room (Food & Nutrition), 3rd Floor PG Block

20th Thursday, March 2025 04:30 PM Onwards

**“Media, Communication, and Society in the Digital Age:
Interdisciplinary Perspectives on India”**

Moderator - Prof. Mamatha N

Chairperson, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication , University of Mysore

Sl. No	Title of the paper	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3
9	“A Study on Social Media Usage Patterns Among Rural Female Students in Urban Educational Institutions”	Sharmila Christy. S, Research Scholar, Central University of Tamilnadu, Thiruvavur. Christyphd2020@Gmail.Com	NIL	NIL
10	“From Taboos to Awareness: Media’s Impact on Menstrual Hygiene in Rural and Urban Areas of Udupi & Chamarajanagar Districts”	Dhanya S Bhat, Media Communication and Logistic Expert, Hope for the Children Foundation, Pune, Maharashtra dhanyabhats@gmail.com , venugopalgowdamk@stphilis.ac.in	Dr. Venugopal Gowda M K, Hod, Assistant Professor, Post Graduate and Research Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, St. Philomena’s College (Autonomous), Mysuru, Karnataka.	NIL
11	“Media Interventions in Health Communication and Behavioural Change Among Women in Mysuru and Chamarajanagar: A Comparative Analysis”	Pema Dechan, Intern, Central Tibetan Administration, Himachal Pradesh Pema8001@Gmail.Com	Dr. Vagdevi H.S. Assistant Professor, Post-Graduation Department of Studies and Research in Journalism and Mass Communication St. Philomena’s College (AUTONOMOUS)	NIL
12	“Cultural Hybridization AND Communication Trends IN Ott Platforms: An Observation”	Vidyashree C. Halkerimath, Research Scholar, DOSR In Journalism and Mass Communication, Karnataka State Open University, Mysuru -06 Vidyahalakerimath@Gmail.Com , Nallahalli.1@Gmail.Com	Dr. Hemalatha R., Assistant Professor, DOSR In Journalism and Mass Communication, Karnataka State Open University, Mysuru -06	NIL
13	“Need For Rethinking Communication Flow in Global Era”	Ganesh S. Guest Lecturer, Tamil Nadu ganeshsubbarayanmedia@gmail.com	NIL	NIL
14	“Machismo and Masculine Authority: A Gender Analysis of Mani Ratnam’s Bombay & O Kadhal Kanmani”	R Hemalatha, M.Sc. Visual Communication, Department of Visual Communication, Sathyabama University, Chennai. poojaseervi239@gmail.com	Dr. N. Nazini, Head of the Department, Department of Visual Communication, Sathyabama University, Chennai.	Dr. A.R. Vimal Raj, Assistant Professor, Department of Visual Communication, Sathyabama University, Chennai.

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES EMPLOYED DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN KARNATAKA

Abhisheka. M.P , Assistant Professor HOD, Dept. of Social Work, Bharathi College – PG & RC, Bharathinagara. e-mail: abhimswnss30@gmail.com

A planned communication strategy is a vital resource for managing disasters. The aim of this study was to examine the communication strategy employed during the COVID-19 pandemic in Karnataka state, India, focusing specifically on 10 taluks of Tumkur district. This entailed the activities-based analysis report and field-level work experience. This research is included in the “Accelerate Promotion of COVID-19 Appropriate Behaviors (CAB) for Karnataka”

initiative, serving as a technical partner to UNICEF Hyderabad field office. with prior outcomes not being published. Even though communication for DM is strategically important, the recent COVID-19 pandemic has brought to light numerous deficiencies in the global communication strategy. Evidence exists in certain contexts of communications that might have aided the virus & spread. The textual corpus was examined using a method that incorporated qualitative data analysis. Alongside the qualitative analysis, statistical models such as principal component analysis and hierarchical cluster analysis were employed. Five categories of effective communication methods were identified and structured: i) Early communication means, ii) Information and communication framework, iii) Management of the quality of both communicator and communication, iv) Enhancement of CAB awareness, and v) Unification of stakeholders. Pavagada and Madhugiri were primarily correlated with CAB communication in this study. Additionally, other 08 taluks were linked to communication during the COVID-19 pandemic. During the COVID-19 pandemic, communication was effectively incorporated into disaster planning with the assistance of the district's SBCC Coordinator communication plans.

Key Words: *Pandemic, COVID-19, COVID-19 Appropriate Behaviors, Social and Behavioral Change Communication, UNICEF*

EXAMINING THE TAMIL CULTURAL CONTEXT: A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF GENZ FROM THE STATE OF TAMIL NADU

Akshaya Sri S, PG Student , Flame University, Pune, e-mail: akshaya.sri@flame.edu.in

This study examines the interactions between Tamil Nadu's Generation Z and their linguistic and cultural heritage in the digital age, with a particular emphasis on the points where language use, media consumption, and cultural identity converge. Understanding how this generation interacts with their Tamil heritage is crucial for understanding cultural dynamics in a society that is quickly globalising, as digital technology is reshaping traditional behaviours. Using a qualitative research approach, sixteen participants from various backgrounds will be interviewed in-depth to learn about their opinions on Tamil language, culture, and media. Important research topics include how Gen Z creates and consumes cultural legacy on the internet, how the Tamil language shapes their identity, and how cultural components affect how they interact with advertisements in the Tamil language. Through an analysis of these variables, the research seeks to fill in the gaps in the body of knowledge on language and media consumption while shedding light on the intricacies of cultural identity among young people in Tamil Nadu. The results are anticipated to help preserve and promote Tamil cultural legacy in the

digital sphere by providing marketers, educators, and cultural policymakers with information about the values and preferences of this group. In the end, this research hopes to contribute to the conversation on Generation Z's changing identities and how technology affects engagement with and transmission of culture.

Keywords: *Generation Z, Tamil Nadu, media consumption, Meme culture, community*

DECODING THE AI HYPE CYCLE THROUGH LINKEDIN: A SOCIAL LISTENING ANALYSIS OF INDUSTRY NARRATIVES AND PUBLIC PERCEPTION

Allan Harold Rex, Research Scholar, School of Media Studies, Mahindra University
e-mail: allanharoldrex@gmail.com

Discussions about artificial intelligence (AI) on social media platforms like LinkedIn present a striking contrast. On one hand, the majority of corporate messaging portrays AI as a revolutionary force, On the other, AI professionals engage with these posts, frequently voicing skepticism. This study explores how AI narratives develop and spread within professional communities on LinkedIn, by analysing the interplay between enthusiastic promotion and cautious critique. Specifically, the study aims to address two research gaps: (1) How does AI discourse evolve within professional social networks among technology professionals? and (2) What role does LinkedIn play in amplifying narratives that hype technology? By employing a qualitative approach, this study relies on social listening and observational analysis to examine patterns in AI-related discussions. Using a qualitative methodology, this research combines LinkedIn data scraping, social listening, and observational analysis. By analyzing linguistic choices, engagement dynamics, and sentiment shifts, the research identifies recurring themes and trends across different industries, roles, and regions that could be leading to these AI hype cycles. The findings seek to provide insights into how AI narratives are shaped by professional hierarchies, economic incentives, and platform-specific engagement mechanisms.

Keywords: *Media studies, Communication, AI narratives, LinkedIn, professional social networks, technology hype, discourse analysis.*

THE REPRESENTATION OF CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN CONTEMPORARY OTT PLATFORMS

Amaljith N.K, Assistant Professor, Department of Visual Communication, Kalasalingam Academy of Research and Education, Krishnan Kovil, Tamil Nadu. e-mail: amaljithravi245@gmail.com

Gnana D Hans, Assistant Professor, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu

With the rise of Over-the-Top (OTT) platforms such as Netflix and Amazon Prime, contemporary media consumption has become increasingly global, fostering cross-cultural communication and diasporic narratives. These platforms serve as dynamic spaces where cultural identities are represented, negotiated, and redefined across borders. This study examines

how cross-cultural communication is portrayed in contemporary OTT content, with a focus on diasporic experiences, linguistic hybridity, and cultural mediation. Through a qualitative content analysis, this research explores selected streaming productions, including *Money Heist* (2017–2021), *Sacred Games* (2018–2019), *Delhi Crime* (2019 -), *Narcos* (2015 -2017) and, investigating how these narratives depict cultural adaptation, identity conflict, and globalization. The study is grounded in Homi Bhabha's (1994) concept of hybridity and cultural negotiation, which explores how cultural identities evolve in transnational contexts. Also, Stuart Hall's (1997) Representation Theory is employed to analyze the portrayal of cultural differences and identity in global media. The methodology follows a two-fold approach: Textual and visual analysis of the selected content, examining narrative structures, character interactions, and cinematographic elements that reflect cross-cultural dialogues. Findings from this study aim to highlight the evolving nature of cultural identity formation, linguistic diversity, and mediated communication in the digital streaming era. The results contribute to discussions on globalization, media representation, and digital storytelling, emphasizing how OTT platforms act as contemporary sites for cross-cultural exchange.

Keywords: Cross-cultural, Communication, OTT Platforms, Mediation

REPRESENTATION OF QUEERNESS IN MEDIA: THE EFFECT OF IDENTITY AND GENDER ROLES IN LGBTQ SPACES

Ameya Das, Student of BA (Hons) Media and Communication Nitte Institute of Communication, Nitte (Deemed to be University). e-mail: ameyadas07@gmail.com

The study necessitates the need to explore the portrayal of queer identity using a qualitative research approach. Using content analysis as well as interview discussions, the study examines the intersection of queer identities and gender roles with respect to queer representation in the selected media texts. The study further explores the influence of media in the creation of self-identity, societal perceptions, and interactions within queer spaces. This is significant because media plays a crucial role in shaping cultural attitudes and the reinforcement of stereotypes internally and externally. The study integrates both explanatory and exploratory research methods, analysing media portrayals while also conducting in-depth, semi-structured interviews with queer individuals. Exploratory methods are used to understand the participants & personal experiences and insights, while explanatory analysis provides a deeper understanding of the social dynamics reflected in media portrayals. This dual approach provides a comprehensive understanding of the media's influence on LGBTQ identities and community interactions. The analysis of *Heartstopper* highlights the issues within the queer community that explore the societal tendency to impose assumptions about sexual orientation. Additionally, an examination of *Modern Family* reveals how the reversal of parenting roles in same-sex relationships simultaneously challenges and reinforces conventional gender norms. Interviews with LGBTQ individuals further reveal concerns about the limited diversity in queer representation, particularly the dominance of privileged, Western, predominantly white and MLM (men-loving-men) narratives. Participants talk on how the lack of authentic and varied representation affects LGBTQ individuals as well as broader societal perceptions of queerness. This study emphasises the significance of accurate and inclusive media representations and advocates for greater variety in representation in order to foster understanding and inclusivity within LGBTQ spaces.

Keywords: *Queer Representation, Gender Roles, Identity, Queer Theory, Sexuality*

MEDIA AS A TOOL IN NATION-BUILDING

Anand C, Assistant Professor in Political Science, Department of Political Science, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Mysore. e-mail: anandc@stphilos.ac.in

Indian media has historically played a vital role in nation-building, from its contributions to the freedom struggle to its efforts in promoting social and religious reforms⁵. Today, encompassing print, television, and digital platforms, the media landscape continues to shape public discourse and national identity. As the &fourth pillar of democracy &, media plays a crucial role in nation- building, particularly in a diverse context like India. Democracy is 'Government by People's Voice'. 'Vox populi Vox Dei' convey the message that 'Voice of the people-Voice of God'. Media & Press have the power to reach out and directly influence the minds of average people. This paper investigates the complex role of Indian media in fostering social cohesion, promoting democratic participation, driving economic development, and preserving cultural heritage. This study is crucial since the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 16, aims to promote peaceful and inclusive societies. While a free and responsible Media can facilitate the cause of Nation-building, but it is plagued by challenges. These include life- threat, political pressure, the spread of misinformation, and ethical dilemmas. India's decline in the World Press Freedom Index, signals an alarming deterioration of Media independence. This paper analyses the interplay between media, society, and the state in India, identifying strategies to harness media;s power for Nation-building.

Key words: *Media, Democracy, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Nation-building, World Press Freedom Index.*

COMMUNICATING SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH GREEN ADVERTISING: ANALYZING ITS EFFECTIVENESS IN SHAPING CONSUMER PERCEPTION

Anjali Rai, Research Scholar, Nitte Institute of Communication, Nitte(DU), e-mail: anjalirai99@gmail.com

Anisha, Associate Professor, Nitte Institute of Communication, Nitte(DU).

In the face of climate change and ecological imbalances, brands increasingly employ green advertising to promote environmental sustainability and attract conscious consumers. However, consumer scepticism toward greenwashing where environmental claims are exaggerated or falsified threatens the credibility of these advertisements. This study assesses the effectiveness of green advertisements in fostering consumer trust and influencing sustainable behaviour. Adopting a qualitative, consumer-centric approach, this research gathers insights through focus group discussions with participants from diverse age groups and backgrounds. Advertisements from brands featured as top 50 in Forbes Fortune 500 and The Economic Times (2015–2025) is analysed. After viewing the advertisements, participants answer structured questions to evaluate the credibility of environmental claims. The study integrates content analysis through the rhetorical framework of ethos, pathos, and logos. Ethos (credibility) examines brand authenticity and ethical commitment, pathos (emotional appeal) explores narratives evoking responsibility or urgency and logos (logical appeal) assesses the use of facts and statistics supporting sustainability claims. Findings reveal how effectively green advertisements resonate with consumers and whether they genuinely influence sustainable choices. This research also identifies strategies for brands to strengthen environmental communication, mitigate scepticism

and build consumer trust. The study provides recommendations for brands to enhance their reputation and contribute meaningfully to environmental sustainability through credible and impactful green advertising.

Keywords: *Green Advertisements, Environmental Sustainability, Sustainable Communication, Consumer Awareness and Consumer Perception*

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY IN MITIGATING PERCEPTION OF COMPANY CRISIS: UNDERSTANDING CORPORATE AND PUBLIC PERCEPTION

Anindita Bhattacharya, Student, Department of Media and Communication Studies, CHRIST (Deemed-to-be University). e-mail: anindita.bhattacharya@mamcs.christuniversity.in ,

Suparna Naresh, Associate Professor, Department of Media and Communication Studies, CHRIST

(Deemed-to-be University), email: suparna.naresh@christuniversity.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is gaining more and more significance in the business world, not only just as a social accountability, but also as a tool to create positive brand image for companies. With CSR being such an important aspect of corporate management today, it is leveraged for more than just enhancing brand image, but also to enhance their credibility, maintain consumer trust, and have greater brand loyalty. This study examines the efficacy of CSR in crisis management, with a particular focus on its influence on public perception, consumer confidence, and long-term brand loyalty. It also explores whether a strong CSR record prior to a crisis mitigates reputational harm, reduces negative media coverage, and reinforces take holder trust. Employing a mixed-methods research design, this study integrates survey data assessing public perceptions with expert interviews conducted with corporate professionals to gain deeper insights into CSR; strategic role in crisis mitigation. The findings indicate that firms with proactive and well-integrated CSR initiatives demonstrate greater resilience in the aftermath of crises, as consumers perceive them as more socially responsible and committed to ethical business practices. However, the study also reveals a perceptual gap between corporate communication professionals; views on CSR effectiveness and external stakeholders; interpretations of such initiatives. This difference of opinion creates the necessity for organizations to align CSR strategies more closely with stakeholder expectations to enhance credibility and trust. By providing empirical evidence on the role of CSR in crisis management, this research contributes to the field of corporate communications and crisis response strategies. It offers practical implications for businesses seeking to strengthen their crisis resilience and sustain a positive corporate reputation in an increasingly complex and accountability-driven business environment.

Keywords: *Corporate Social Responsibility, Crisis Management, Corporate Communication, Public Perception*

ONE JOKE, MANY LIVES: EXAMINING THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF STAND-UP COMEDY THROUGH MULTI-PLATFORM PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Anthony Christon J, Research Scholar, Christ university Bangalore. e-mail: anthony.christon@res.christuniversity.in

This study examines the metamorphosis of stand-up comedy as it goes across from live performance spaces into diverse digital platforms, the artform relay upon real-time audience feedback to shape its delivery. However, in the digital age, the same joke takes on different lives across multiple platforms, each with distinct constraints and audience engagement patterns. This study explores how humor transforms as it moves from the stage to digital spaces, using my own stand-up performances as a qualitative case study. By analyzing a single joke across three formats: a full-length live performance (YouTube), a short-form clip (Instagram), and audience discussion (YouTube comments) this study examines the shifts in timing, theatricality, and audience perception. In live settings, laughter, claps, and silence dictate comedic rhythm, while digital spaces offer asynchronous engagement through likes, shares, and written feedback. The study also highlights how platform constraints shape humour storytelling, with Instagram enforcing shortness and YouTube allowing long-form expression. Additionally, it investigates misinterpretation and liveliness, exploring how humor is received when stripped of its original performance context. Furthermore, this study examines misinterpretation and virality, analyzing how humor evolves when separated from its original performance context. A joke that is effective in a live setting may be received differently when edited, shared, or commented on online. By blending sociology, performance studies, and digital media research, this study offers a dynamic exploration of how stand-up comedy is reimagined in cross-media storytelling.

Keywords : *Stand-up comedy, Cross-media storytelling, Audience engagement, Performance analysis, Platform constraints.*

PORTRAYAL OF WOMEN IN BOLLYWOOD HORROR FILMS IN THE LAST FIVE YEARS

Anwasha Singha, Student, Department of Media and Communication Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore. e-mail:anwasha.singha@mamcs.christuniversity.in

Vikash Chauhan, Assistant Professor, CHRIST (Deemed to be University) Bangalore Central Campus

If we talk about Cinema, especially in a country like India, it is more than art; it mirrors societal views, values, and changing cultural dynamics. Indian films, especially Bollywood, have long depicted women in traditional roles, with recent years showing a shift toward stronger female characters in romantic dramas, action films, and comedies. Gap: There is an immense deficit in understanding how these recent horror films actually represent shifting views about gender and women;s empowerment within Indian society. The primary goal of this study is to explore how Bollywood horror films depict women and whether these depictions have evolved or not. Methodology: My study examines the representation of women in Bollywood horror films from the past five years in OTT platforms mainly Netflix and Amazon prime to understand how horror films in India reflect or challenge societal attitudes toward gender and empowerment using a qualitative methodology and the tool used is multimodal discourse analysis. Previous

studies have largely overlooked the different ways horror films represent women. Most research touches only lightly on the topic, without delving into the visual and audio techniques like camera angles, lighting, and costume design that shape the portrayal of female characters. Key findings: Suggest a shift in Bollywood horror films, where female characters increasingly embody themes of empowerment and resilience, moving beyond typical victim roles. Based on the analysis I could see there is a metamorphosis that has happened and also helped revive the genre. Outcome: For instance, Bulbbul uses mythological motifs to portray its female lead as a symbol of feminist power, subtly critiquing patriarchal injustices. Together, these films show how Bollywood horror can be a platform for challenging traditional female portrayals.

Keywords : *Films, Gender studies, Women representation, Bollywood, Horror*

EMOTIONAL WELL-BEING IN PREGNANCY IN MALAYALAM CINEMA: MEDIA IMPACT ON PUBLIC PERCEPTION AND MATERNAL HEALTH-SEEKING

Aparna Jayabal P., postgraduate student, Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru. e-mail: aparnajayabal12@gmail.com

Meljo Thomas, Professor, Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru

Malayalam cinema plays a significant role in shaping public discourse, yet its portrayal of maternal mental health remains largely overlooked. This study investigates how emotional well-being during pregnancy is depicted in Malayalam films and how these portrayals influence public perception and maternal health-seeking behaviors. Using qualitative content analysis, three films—Kalimannu (2013), Makalkku (2005), and Wonder Women (2022)—were examined through recurring themes such as psychological struggles, support systems, healthcare portrayal, cultural attitudes, and health-seeking behaviors. The findings reveal contrasting portrayals of pregnancy-related mental health. Kalimannu depicts emotional isolation following the loss of a partner, emphasizing physical health while neglecting psychological care. Makalkku highlights the stigma surrounding unwanted pregnancy, reinforcing societal judgment and the lack of mental health support. In contrast, Wonder Women presents a progressive representation, showcasing strong support systems and access to therapy, encouraging a more open discussion on maternal well-being. Grounded in Social Cognitive Theory, Stigma Theory, and the Health Belief Model, this study demonstrates how cinematic narratives shape societal attitudes toward maternal mental health. While certain portrayals perpetuate stereotypes and discourage help-seeking behaviors, others foster awareness and empathy. The research underscores the potential of Malayalam cinema as a medium for advocacy, emphasizing the importance of responsible storytelling in reducing stigma and promoting maternal health awareness. Future research can explore a broader selection of films and incorporate audience reception studies to assess the real-world impact of these portrayals. By bridging the gap between clinical insights and cinematic representation, this study highlights the need for more sensitive and informed portrayals of maternal mental health in Indian cinema.

Keywords : *Malayalam cinema, maternal mental health, pregnancy, stigma, media influence*

TOPICAL PREFERENCE IN THE TWEETS OF INDIAN POLITICAL LEADERS: A CASE STUDY OF LOK SABHA ELECTIONS, 2024

Ashwini Ramesh, Faculty , Department of Mass Communication and Journalism
Bengaluru City University Karnataka, India. e-mail: ashwini.ramesh95@gmail.com

This study examines the evolving role of social media in Indian politics, specifically the platform X, as an important tool for electoral campaigns and public discourse. Despite India's media literacy challenges, the rapid advancement of digital platforms has deeply influenced its public sphere, marking a shift in political communication that is direct, large-scale, and continuous. Previous research has explored how social media impacts the political landscape, focusing on echo chambers (Colleoni et al., 2014), political polarization (Bruns & Highfield, 2013), self-promotion (Jaidka & Ahmed, 2015), and voter engagement (Ahmed et al., 2017). Building on these studies, this research analyses the tweet frequency, topic preferences, and sentiment of India's top-followed political leaders during the critical 2024 Lok Sabha elections. By employing Python's BERTopic, the study identifies thematic clusters, offering insights into political leaders' issue prioritization, narrative framing and agenda-setting strategies on X. Sentiment analysis with BERTweet captures polarity in tweets to reveal the tone and emotional impact of leaders' messaging. This approach highlights the interplay between media hybridization, unique role, and the heightened sensitivities surrounding India's prime ministerial elections, revealing the platform's significant impact on political discourse and voter engagement in contemporary Indian democracy.

Keywords: *X and Lok Sabha elections 2024, political leaders and India, sentiment analysis, topics and tweets, Narendra Modi, BERT*

A STUDY ON GENDER DIFFERENCES IN FINANCIAL LITERACY AND INVESTMENT ATTITUDES

Ashwini. K.J, Assistant Professor, PG Department of Economics, St. Philomena's College
(Autonomous), Mysore. ashwinikj@stphilos.ac.in

Nandeesh H K, Assistant Professor & HoD, Assistant Professor, PG Department of Economics, St.
Philomena's College (Autonomous), Mysore

The current study emphasizes the relationship between savings, investment, and economic indicators over time, with a focus on gender differences in financial literacy and awareness. It finds a significant positive correlation between savings and investment, with a notable upward trend in investments from 2000 to 2022, despite fluctuations due to global economic events. The study is based on both primary and secondary data and a simple random sampling technique is adapted. To analyse the data suitable statistical techniques such as tables, charts descriptive statistics trend analysis and chi-square is employed. The study reveals that there is a significant gender differences in spending patterns, financial knowledge, and investment behaviours. Men exhibit a higher propensity for specific expenditures and hold more savings accounts, whereas women show greater knowledge of post office savings rates and exhibit a higher preference for long-term financial objectives. Despite these differences, both genders possess similar levels of risk perception in financial decision-making. The findings highlight the need for tailored

financial products and services that address these diverse needs, emphasizing the importance of customized financial planning and gender-specific educational programs to enhance financial literacy and investment strategies.

Keywords: *Investment, Saving, Financial Literacy*

SOCIAL INCLUSION AND POVERTY ERADICATION UNDER TARGETED PUBLIC DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM IN INDIA

Basavanagowda T, Academician, Sri D Devaraj urs first grade College ,Davangere.
e-mail: basudvg2012@gmail.com

Social inclusion is enabling all citizens to participate in decision-making of policies and programs that impact their lives. The idea of 'a society for all' is represented by social inclusion, in which each person has rights as well as obligations and can actively participate in society and therefore, social inclusion may take place only when poverty is eradicated or poverty eradication can bring social inclusion. There are some challenges in the path of social inclusion and poverty eradication. These include factors such as inequality, cultural diversity, demographic governance, and geographical diversity. However, it is important to note that inequality is often the underlying factor that leads to poverty and social exclusion. The chances and capacities of excluded groups to engage in society are improved via social inclusion. In India, there have been numerous initiatives aimed at eradicating poverty that attempt to give the poor access to essential amenities including housing, health care, education, and job. Here are a few of these programs: MGNREGA, IRDP, NRLM SARY, PDS, and TPDS etc. The present research paper does descriptive analysis that examines the Targeted Public Distribution System scheme (TPDS), which was launched in 1997 under the Food Security Scheme Public Distribution System (PDS). The purpose of TPDS is to identify the poorest among the poor so that the selected group having food security has a demographic dividend and can contribute in the progress of social and economic activities. TPDS is one of the most significant and extensive poverty eradication programs in India that improves the socio economic welfare of the people and has helped bringing about social inclusion.

Keywords: *Social Inclusion, Poverty Eradication, TPDS*

INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN MOBILE THEATRE OF ASSAM

Darshana Das, Ph. D. Research Scholar, Department of Electronic Media and Mass Communication, Pondicherry University , Puducherry. e-mail: darshudas143@pondiuni.ac.in

Dr. T. Balasaravanan, Associate Professor, Department of Electronic Media and Mass Communication, Pondicherry University, Puducherry

This study explores the integration of digital platforms in the mobile theatre scene of Assam, examining how these traditional performance groups leverage modern technology to expand their reach and enrich their art form. Mobile theatre in Assam has a rich cultural heritage, traditionally relying on physical performances and local word-of-mouth for audience engagement. However, the advent of digital platforms from social media to streaming services has transformed these dynamics. This research investigates the strategies employed by mobile

theatre groups to apply digital tools for promoting their shows, engaging with audiences, and enhancing the overall theatrical experience. Through qualitative methods, including interviews with key stakeholders/ participants, analysis of digital content, and case studies of prominent theatre groups, the study provides insights into the opportunities and challenges faced in this digital transition. Additionally, the study highlights how digital integration can preserve and grow the cultural narratives inherent in Assamese mobile theatre to a global audience. The research underscores the necessity for capacity building and digital literacy among performers and suggests policy recommendations to support this digital evolution. By bridging traditional art with modern technology, mobile theatre groups in Assam can sustain their cultural relevance and appeal to new generations of theatre enthusiasts.

Keywords: *Mobile theatre, digital platforms, social media, cultural heritage, audience engagement*

FROM TABOOS TO AWARENESS: MEDIA'S IMPACT ON MENSTRUAL HYGIENE IN RURAL AND URBAN AREAS OF UDUPI & CHAMARAJANAGAR DISTRICTS

Dhanya S Bhat , Media Communication and Logistic Expert, Hope for the Children Foundation, Pune, Maharashtra. e-mail: dhanyabhats@gmail.com

Venugopal Gowda M K, HoD, Assistant Professor, Postgraduate and Research Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, St. Philomena`s College (Autonomous), Mysuru, Karnataka.

Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM) is essential for the health and dignity of menstruating individuals, yet significant disparities persist in awareness and adoption of proper menstrual hygiene practices (MHP) across urban and rural populations. Socio-cultural norms, economic constraints, and educational disparities shape these differences, particularly in underdeveloped and developed regions. Media serves as a crucial tool in breaking taboos, disseminating information, and promoting hygienic menstrual practices. This study examines the awareness of MHM and the influence of media interventions on MHP adoption among urban and rural females in Karnataka's Udupi and Chamarajanagar districts, selected based on their Human Development Index (HDI) classification as developed and underdeveloped regions, respectively. Using a descriptive quantitative approach and simple random sampling, the study surveyed 300 menstruating individuals across diverse socio-economic backgrounds. Findings reveal that urban respondents exhibit greater awareness and adherence to hygienic menstrual practices due to enhanced access to education, media, and menstrual products. Media interventions, including digital and traditional campaigns, have effectively increased menstrual health awareness in urban settings. Conversely, rural respondents experience restricted media exposure due to socio-economic barriers and persistent taboos, limiting the effectiveness of awareness initiatives. While media interventions have improved knowledge in both regions, their outreach remains a critical challenge in rural areas.

Keywords: *Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM), Menstrual Hygiene Practices (MHP), Media, Rural, Urban, Developed, Underdeveloped Woman.*

MALE-SAVIOUR COMPLEX AS A CENTRAL NARRATIVE IN THE DEPICTION OF SEXUAL VIOLENCE AGAINST CHILDREN AND WOMEN: AN ANALYSIS OF THE MOVIES CHITTHA AND MAHARAJA

Epciba I, Ph.D. Scholar, Mass Communication, Pondicherry University, Puducherry
e-mail:epcibloom@pondiuni.ac.in

K. S. Krithika, Associate, Professor, Visual Communication, Pondicherry University Community College, Puducherry. e-mail:krithika_ks@yahoo.co.in

Tamil cinema has recently witnessed an increase in the number of movies centered on sexual violence against women and children. Although these films portray sexual violence against women and children, it is debatable whether the narrative is presented from the victim's perspective. The research paper analyses the movies, Chittha (2023) and Maharaja (2024) directed by S.U. Arun Kumar and Nithilan Saminathan respectively. These films are analysed using Stuart Hall's Representation theory and the Feminist film theories of Laura Mulvey and Bell Hooks. These theoretical frameworks enable us to read the movies from a critical perspective and challenge these movies; claim of addressing gender based violence while simultaneously reinforcing traditional gender roles by emphasising on male-led justice, and not acknowledging enough the struggles of a victim of sexual abuse. This study uses narrative analysis methodology to assess how both the films prioritize the male protagonists; agony and emotional struggle over those of the actual victims. The analysis shows that though both the movies Chittha and Maharaja appear to be centered on women's suffering, they ultimately focus more on the male protagonists' trauma, reinforcing the male saviour complex, undermining the female victim's experiences. The power dynamics between the assaulter and the victim are used primarily to evoke emotional responses from the audience. While the movie Chittha briefly portrays the struggles of the victim in the climax, most of the screen time is devoted to the emotional journey of the male protagonist. Both the movies have failed to portray the aftermath of a sexual violence, like PTSD, further marginalizing the survivors' experiences.

Key words: *Agency, assault, power, sexual violence, gender bias, feminism and film.*

UNDERSTANDING THE AUDIENCE OF MANO COMMUNITY RADIO IN THE DIGITAL AGE

Eramani Surya M, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu. e-mail:eramanisuryam0209@gmail.com

Balasubramania Raja, Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu. e-mail:gbs_raja@yahoo.com

Community Radio (CR) is a medium that ensures audience engagement at the grassroots level. It plays a key role in disseminating localized information on education, health and wellness, women empowerment, and social building even in the areas where mainstream media is unreached. However, in the digital age, changing media consumption habits have affected audience engagement with traditional radio formats. This study aims to understand the audience of Mano Community Radio at Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu by understanding their awareness, engagement, and program preferences. Using a qualitative research approach, the study will conduct in-depth interviews with 10 participants, including

students, staff, community members, working women, and homemakers within a 10 km radius. By using Uses and Gratification approach the study's objective is to gather insights about their awareness of Mano Community Radio, how frequently they engage with its content, and what types of programs they find most relevant. Additionally, the study will explore the challenges they face in accessing community radio and their suggestions for improving its reach and impact in the digital era. The findings from the study will provide a deeper understanding of audience behavior and expectations, helping identify strategies to increase awareness about CR, community participation, and engagement. This study will also highlight how community radio can integrate digital tools, such as social media, podcasts, and mobile platforms, to stay relevant in today's media landscape. By understanding its audience, Mano Community Radio can create more inclusive and engaging content, solidifying its position as a trusted and accessible community platform. The study's insights will enhance the broader discourse on the adaptation of community radio in the digital age.

Keywords: *Community Radio, Audience Engagement, New Media, Program Preferences, Media Consumption*

NEED FOR RETHINKING COMMUNICATION FLOW IN GLOBAL ERA

Ganesh S, Academician, Guest Lecturer media Chennai, e-mail: ganeshsubbarayanmedia@gmail.com

It has been a long time of 40 years since the communication flow has been a topic of US UK and rest of the world ago and it has changed now because new issues have come up With New media coming into play and development of social media things have changed as technology has become important factor in most situations More countries are on development path with PM Modi of India making headlines every day with new innovation this topic assumes Importance now more than ever and the World is affected with Covid -19 some badly like India America and the west This time the same vigor what was found 40 years ago is a need for discussion on global news flow LSU professor Dr John C Merrill says US is not guilty of cultural imperialism and India's Indira Gandhi and Rajiv Gandhi participated in this debate particularly Mrs Gandhi once said we know of small poets and scholars of Europe and America but not of Asia and Africa Non Aligned Movement NAM was strong during Rajiv Gandhi and US UK pulled out of UNESCO during Reagan presidency saying it is under Marxist influence. With the changing context this debate assumes importance today India is more closer ideologically to right governments than anything else Also communism has gone in Russia and Ukraine war and other things all complicate the situation This paper will analyse the changing context of the debate past issues threats to free flow Current status of flow as cold war between two super powers is on and where is the debate at present in changing times as Trump Putin relationship delays confrontation This paper will suggest remedies for poor information flow cultural domination and freedom of speech and information and continuing question of balancing information flows in today's work

Key words: *North south debate US UK ideologies cultural domination NAM UNESCO*

PUBLIC TRUST IN THE AGE OF USER-GENERATED CONTENT: ANALYSING DIGITAL NEWS

Garima Gunawat, Assistant Professor, NIMCJ, Ahmedabad, Gujarat,
e-mail:Garimagunawat24@gmail.com

Shirish Kashikar, Director, NIMCJ, Ahmedabad, Gujarat

User-generated content (UGC) has transformed news dissemination, audience engagement, and media credibility. This study examines the impact of user-generated content on journalism, focusing on its influence on public discourse and trust in digital news. Theoretical framework is Uses and Gratifications Theory, this research explores audience motivations and shifts in media control, highlighting how decentralised content creation affects news consumption. A quantitative research methodology is employed in this study. Data will be gathered through structured audience perception surveys distributed across selected online news forums, where user-generated content significantly contributes to information dissemination. The surveys assess audience trust in User Generated Content-based news, patterns of engagement, and perceived credibility of user-generated reporting. Statistical tools will be used to analyse responses, identifying trends in misinformation perception and the role of UGC in shaping public discourse. The study aims to assess user-generated content's role in shaping public discussions and evaluate audience trust in user-generated content-based news. Findings will indicate that while user-generated content enhances participatory journalism and media pluralism, it also raises concerns about credibility, misinformation, and ethical standards in digital news environments. The study will underscore the importance of digital literacy initiatives and regulatory frameworks to ensure responsible content creation and consumption.

Keywords: - User-Generated Content, Journalism, media ethics, digital news, credibility.

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY COMMUNICATION IN SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE THROUGH THE LENS OF ITS STAKEHOLDERS

Gouri S Dev, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore. e-mailsdevgouri@gmail.com

Jayaprakash C R, Associate Professor; Head, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

Nithiyanandhan S, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

In the industrial world, almost every business firm focuses on maintaining its brand image and reputation by portraying itself as socially responsible. They recognize the benefits of engaging in sustainability-related activities for brand building and economic progress. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a key way for organizations to connect with the public and contribute to their well-being. India is the first country to mandate CSR activities under Section 135 of the Companies Act 2013, requiring high-profit companies to spend at least 2% of their profits on CSR initiatives. Consequently, companies invest their CSR funds in various sectors, often in collaboration with the government or NGOs. This paper explores the perception of organic farmers on CSR activities in sustainable agriculture. The study investigates organic farmers'

awareness and knowledge of CSR funding, their trust towards CSR activities and significance of CSR communication between farmer and CSR sponsors in sustainable agriculture by employing a situational case study. Interviews with active practitioners of sustainable farming revealed that most farmers are unaware of CSR initiatives in sustainable agriculture. Additionally, companies should enhance their media strategies for better coverage of their sustainable CSR activities. Also, interviews with corporate sponsors and media personnel on the issue of limited funding in CSR activities for sustainable agriculture and their ideologies on the concept of corporate voluntarism and green washing were added to get an objective view on the topic. The paper provides insights for corporates in the Agri sector to better understand farmers' needs and support them through effective CSR strategies, based on Stakeholder and Agenda-Setting theories.

Keywords: Brand Image, Brand Reputation, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Organic farming, Sustainable agriculture, Corporate Voluntarism, Green Washing.

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL INCLUSION ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

H. S. Chandrashekhara Kale, Assistant Professor, Department of Economics

Government First Grade College Navanagar, Bagalkot. e-mail: chandrashekhara.kale@gmail.com

Digital inclusion—the equitable access to and use of digital technologies—is a critical driver of economic development. This paper explores the impact of digital inclusion on economic growth, employment, and poverty reduction. Using data from global economic reports, digital adoption indices, and case studies, we analyze how improved digital access correlates with GDP growth, job creation, and financial inclusion. The findings indicate that higher digital inclusion leads to significant economic benefits, but challenges such as the digital divide and infrastructure gaps persist. Policy recommendations include investment in digital infrastructure, digital literacy programs, and public-private partnerships to enhance digital access.

Keywords – Digital Inclusion, Economic Development, Digital Divide, Financial Inclusion

MEASURING HOW BLOCKCHAIN AI-POWERED COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AFFECT THE PRODUCTIVITY OF DISTANT WORKERS ECONOMICALLY

Harini. S, II MCA Student, St. Philomena's college, Mysore , India. e-mail: harinipreethi686@gmail.com

This article examines the growing influence of communication technologies powered by artificial intelligence (AI) on remote workers; productivity. Effective communication is crucial as more and more companies adopt remote work models. This study examines the ways in which AI-powered tools—like intelligent assistants, automated messaging systems, and sophisticated video conferencing capabilities—affect important facets of remote team effectiveness. By analysing both direct effects—such as time savings in communication-related tasks and increased productivity—and indirect effects—such as improved employee engagement, enhanced collaboration, and accelerated innovation—the study creates a framework for

measuring the economic impact of these tools. As artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly integrated into communication platforms, particularly for remote workers, ensuring security, privacy, and data integrity becomes more complex. Traditional AI-powered communication platforms are vulnerable to cyberattacks, unlawful access, and data breaches because of their dependence on centralized servers. This study explores the use of blockchain technology as a decentralized, impenetrable security layer for communication systems driven by artificial intelligence. By using distributed ledger technology (DLT) and smart contracts, blockchain enhances end-to-end encryption (E2EE) and ensures transparent, secure, and trust less AI interactions. The proposed approach dynamically authenticates users using AI-verified digital signatures and zero-trust architecture, reducing the risk of man-in-the-middle attacks, data manipulation, and undesired monitoring. In order to safeguard remote work environments, the study also examines the financial implications of combining blockchain technology with artificial intelligence (AI), highlighting the potential for organizational security, AI governance, and regulatory compliance. Through simulations and real-world case studies, this study aims to demonstrate how blockchain-enhanced AI communication might revolutionize cybersecurity for distant workers while addressing privacy and scalability problems.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, productivity, economic, end-to-end encryption*

EXPLORING THE DEVOTION, PARTICIPATORY, AND PROMOTIONAL FAN CULTURE OF THALAPATHY VIJAY MAKKAL IYAKKAM IYAKKAM (விஜய் மக்கள் இயக்கம்) IN THIRUVARUR DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU.

Harini Dineshkumar, M.A. Mass Communication, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvapur. e-mail: harinidineshkumar30@gmail.com

Gondi Surender Dhanunjay, Research Fellow, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvapur.

Shamala Ramappa, Assistant Professor, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvapur.

The devotion, promotional culture, and participation of Thalapathy Vijay's followers in Thiruvapur, Tamil Nadu, are documented in this study. The study explores how fan actions converge with cultural, social, and emotional aspects to produce an influence that goes beyond entertainment through the use of narrative analysis. A distinct combination of fan loyalty, collaborative promotional tactics, and social welfare efforts is revealed by semi-structured interviews and field observations with important members of the Thalapathy Vijay Fans Association. The results show how fan culture goes beyond simple appreciation, impacting social integration, and community growth, and providing a forum for civic participation and cultural expression. This study advances our knowledge of fandom as an advanced phenomenon that can influence larger social processes.

Keywords: *Fan Culture, Participatory Culture, Promotional Culture, Thalapathy Vijay, Devotion, Tamil Nadu, Narrative Analysis.*

MACHISMO AND MASCULINE AUTHORITY: A GENDER ANALYSIS OF MANI RATNAM'S BOMBAY AND O KADHAL KANMANI

R.Hemalatha, M.Sc. Visual Communication, Department of Visual Communication, Sathyabama University, Chennai. . e-mail: poojaseervi239@gamil.com

N. Nazini, Head of the Department, Department of Visual Communication, Sathyabama University, Chennai.

A.R. Vimal Raj, Assistant Professor, Department of Visual Communication, Sathyabama University, Chennai

This research paper offers a analysis of O Kadhal Kanmani (2015), Directed by Mani Ratnam, and Bombay (1995), also by Mani Ratnam, exploring their thematic complexity, narrative strategies, and socio-political commentary. The study employs a combination of film theory, female analysis, and to examine how these films address themes of modern relationships and socio-religious conflict. The research shows how Mani Ratnam's sensitive storytelling style and his capacity to deal with difficult socio-cultural topics appear in both films, despite their different focuses. The study offers insights into the importance and effect of societal norms in modern cinema and advances our understanding of how O Kadhal Kanmani and Bombay address and challenge them. So that I have to find how Maniratnam portray the female character and the analysis based on the movies Bombay i and oh kadhal Kanmani . Then see the difference how the females are been Categorized and lived.

Keywords: *Indian Cinema, Mani Ratnam, Emotion , Women Portrayal, stereotypes , Gender norms*

ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN SETTING POLITICAL AGENDA: AN OVERVIEW

Hemalatha R, Assistant Professor, DOSR in Journalism and Mass Communication, Karnataka State Open University, Mysuru. e-mail: nallahalli.1@gmail.com

Adarsh Paswan, Assistant Professor Research Scholar, DOSR in Journalism and Mass Communication, Karnataka State Open University, Mysore. e-mail: paswan.adarsh@gmail.com

In recent years, social media has become a pivotal force in shaping political agendas in India. With the rapid growth of internet access and mobile usage, platforms like Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp have transcended traditional media, offering a direct line of communication between politicians, political parties, and the electorate. These platforms allow for real-time engagement, faster information dissemination, and targeted messaging, all of which play a major role in influencing political opinions and mobilizing voters. Social media also significantly impacts how political issues are framed, influencing national and regional debates. Trending hashtags, viral campaigns, and influential figures often prioritize certain topics, effectively steering public discourse and setting the political agenda. In a country as diverse as India, social media has become a space where a wide array of political issues—from economic policies to social justice—are debated and contested. Despite its potential, social media role in politics comes with challenges. The spread of misinformation, echo chambers, and online manipulation are persistent concerns. Nonetheless, social media remains a crucial tool for political engagement and agenda-setting, reflecting the evolving landscape of political

communication in India democracy. This paper explores the dynamic role of social media in Indian politics, examining its opportunities, challenges, and impact on shaping political discourse in the digital age through analysis of secondary data.

Key Words: *Social Media, Political Agenda, Political Discourse, Digital Communication, Political Engagement, Public Opinion, Online Mobilization.*

SOCIAL MEDIA AS TOOL OF COMMUNICATION IN INDIA: CRITICAL STUDY OF INSTAGRAM

Hemant Rawate, Assistant Professor, MGM University College of Journalism and Mass Communication , Aurangabad. e-mail:hemant.rawate@gmail.com

Social media has revolutionized communication in India, providing a platform for individuals, businesses, and political entities to engage with diverse audiences. Among various social media platforms, Instagram has emerged as a crucial tool for digital communication, driven by its visual-centric approach, interactive features, and AI-powered algorithms. This research critically examines Instagram's role as a communication tool in India, analysing its impact on personal interactions, influencer marketing, political discourse, and information dissemination. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study incorporates content analysis, user surveys, and case studies of Indian influencers, political figures, and businesses. Findings suggest that Instagram is widely used for brand promotions, activism, and real-time engagement. Influencer marketing has particularly grown in India, with brands leveraging Instagram's reach to connect with younger demographics (Jain & Kumar, 2021). Additionally, Indian politicians have increasingly used Instagram to shape public perception, bypassing traditional media (Chakraborty & Bose, 2022). However, concerns regarding misinformation, algorithmic bias, and the mental health impact of curated online personas persist (Gupta & Sharma, 2020). The study highlights how Instagram has transformed digital communication in India, offering opportunities for engagement while also posing challenges related to privacy, authenticity, and digital well-being. The research contributes to the broader discourse on social media's evolving role in Indian society and provides recommendations for responsible usage.

Keywords: *Instagram, social media communication, influencer marketing, political discourse, misinformation, India, digital engagement*

INFORMATION ABUNDANCE IN DIGITAL ERA

Ishika Ladda, MA Media Governance, Sem IV at Centre for Culture, Media and Governance, Jamia Millia Islamia University, Delhi. e-mail: ishikaladdawork@gmail.com

Through the advent of the internet in the second half of the twentieth century, sharing of information became easier, which caused an explosion and can be named information abundance. The term 'information abundance' refers to a macro-level phenomenon or an external state in which people and society have easy access to a large quantity of information and content. Therefore, there is no inherent benefit or drawback to information abundance. As lucrative and interesting as it may seem, the fact that we overlook is that this information abundance led us to information overload. The pre-existing concerns about 'too much to read' were legitimized by the ubiquitous digital information. The American social scientist Bertram Gross coined the term

'information overload' in 1964 to describe the situation in which a system's capacity to process information is exceeded by the amount of information it receives (Bawden and Robinson, 2020). There has been plenty of research in this area by many theorists. Technology has been related to the cause of both information abundance and information overload but the extent to which the reasons “owners” have wanted this information to be available to people is less explored. Furthermore, the study does not make extensive use of postmodernism and explains the abundance of information as a part of capitalism and globalisation as the information is commodified.

Keywords: *Information abundance, information overload, technology, digital era, post-modernism*

USER GENERATED CONTENT'S IMPACT ON HEALTH COMMUNICATION MISINFORMATION

Ishanvi Sharma, Assistant Professor, NMKRV College for Women, Jayanagar
e-mail:ishanvirsharma@gmail.com

This study investigates how fitness and diet influencers on social media are reshaping health communication and how artificial intelligence can help understand public reactions to the flood of health advice online. The main objective of this paper is to figure out how these online influencers have not only democratized health tips but also, sometimes unintentionally, spread misleading information that can affect people's choices about diet and exercise. To address these questions a mixed-methods methodology is employed. A qualitative content analysis of a well-curated sample of posts from the social media platform Instagram is conducted. Through creating a simplified coding system, themes and patterns are observed. Further, a quantitative sentiment analysis with AI tools is performed. This aids in measuring how the public is responding to these posts—whether individuals are cheering them on, being sceptical, or even getting confused. By combining qualitative and quantitative methods, this study will shed light on the terrain of online health advice, providing insight into both the hope and the dangers of our cyber age. This study addresses the growing influence of UGC on health communication, particularly how fitness and diet misinformation can shape public perceptions and behaviours. By focusing on UGC, this research highlights a critical gap where unregulated and often unverified health advice circulates widely on social media, potentially leading to harmful consequences.

Keywords: *UGC, Health Communication, AI, Sentiment Analysis*

ASSESSING THE ROLE OF NEW MEDIA IN CREATING AWARENESS ON EFFECTIVE WASTE MANAGEMENT AMONG RURAL POPULATIONS

Iswarya K, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu. e-mail: iswaryakarthiskeyankdm@gmail.com

G Balasubramania Raja, Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu. e-mail:gbs_raj@yahoo.com

The proliferation of new media platforms presents a significant opportunity to raise awareness and educate rural populations about effective waste management practices. This study aims to assess the role of new media platforms in disseminating information and promoting sustainable

waste management behaviors among rural communities. Using the Diffusion of Innovations Theory, this research explores how new media serve as communication channels in the diffusion of waste management practices among rural populations. The main objective of this study is to evaluate the current level of awareness and knowledge of waste management practices among rural populations. It also seeks to determine the effectiveness of new media content in promoting sustainable waste management practices in these areas. This study employs a mixed-methods approach to gather data on the role of new media in waste management education. A structured survey will be administered to a representative sample of rural residents to collect data on their access to new media, awareness of waste management practices, and in-depth interviews will also be conducted to understand the role of new media content on shaping their waste management behaviors. The study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of new media in creating awareness about waste management practices among rural populations. The findings will inform strategies to leverage new media for enhancing waste management education and promoting sustainable behaviors in rural communities.

Keywords: *New Media, Waste Management, Rural Population, Awareness, Community Engagement, Digital Education*

WEB OF LIES: NEW MEDIA'S ROLE IN PROPAGATING MISINFORMATION EXPLORED THROUGH QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

J. Karpagaraj, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli. e-mail: karpagarajkraj@gmail.com

V. Sundararaman, Assistant Professor, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli. e-mail: vsundararaman@gmail.com

New media has become a powerful tool for accessing news and information, especially in countries like India, where internet usage is growing rapidly. With its easy accessibility and low cost, it becomes the primary source of news for many people, particularly in rural areas. However, along with its benefits, new media also comes with a major drawback—the spread of misinformation. The way people receive and believe news today has changed drastically, with short and engaging content often gaining more attention than well-researched facts. Unfortunately, this has led to the rise of fake news, influencing public opinion and creating confusion on important issues. Using qualitative research methods, it examines fake news stories that went viral on Tamil social media, analyzing data from two well-known fact-checking platforms, Fact Crescendo and Newschecker. The research highlights how the misinformation created and which of themes it had. It also discusses the challenges governments face in controlling false news while balancing freedom of expression. The findings of this study emphasize the urgent need for better media awareness, especially in rural areas, where people often rely on forwarded messages and social media posts for news. By understanding how misinformation works, we can take steps to improve digital literacy and create a more informed society. This research aims to contribute to the ongoing discussion on tackling fake news and promoting responsible news consumption in the digital age.

Keywords: *Fake News, Digital Media, Social Media, Fact-Checking, Online Misinformation*

ADDRESSING CLIMATE CHANGE THROUGH NEWS MEDIA: LOCAL EVENTS MATTER

Jayaprakash. C. R., Associate Professor, Head, Dept. of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. e-mail: jayaprakash@psgcas.ac.in

Nithiyandan. S., Research Scholars, Dept. of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Gouri S. Dev, Research Scholars, Dept. of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

January 2025 has recorded itself as the warmest January faced by humans on earth. Yet there are disparities at a global level on addressing Climate Change. People are found to be affected with heatwaves, severe floods and droughts which are related to Climate Change. Some coin these issues as Climate Crisis or even Climate Disaster. News Media as a source of information on Climate Change has found better trust with citizens while compared with politicians, government, charities, celebrities, energy companies and even citizens at an individual level. It's only the environmental activists and scientists who have a better standing of trust on their works. Studies also indicate that local events connect citizens to their concern on climate change. A focus group study of farmers, activists and, media persons operating around the concept of Climate Change is done to identify the reasons for the concern of common people on the above topic. The suggestions and findings will be of use to the media in enhancing news on Climate Change. Inconsistency in weather pattern, increasing human-animal conflicts, urbanization, automation, unexpected disasters and health issues end up in reducing the potency of human capital. As news media continues to be the primary way people access Climate Change information, orienting them on sustenance-based events with a better public engagement strategy in relation to progress, risk and uncertainty frames, pluralistic ignorance, emotions will help media tackle the climate change issue on problems, causes and, solutions.

Key words: *Climate Change, Global Warming, Human-Animal Conflict, Frames, Environmental Communication.*

DIGITAL MEDIA AND INTERACTIVE STORYTELLING: A NEW PARADIGM FOR COMMUNICATING AND ACHIEVING SOCIOECONOMIC CHANGE

Jebakumar M., Assistant Professor, Department of Visual Communication, St. Xavier College (Autonomous), Palayamkottai –Tamil Nadu, India. e-mail: jebakumarm@gmail.com

This study explores the transformative potential of digital media and interactive storytelling in driving socioeconomic change through innovative communication strategies. This study employs a theoretical-conceptual framework to analyse the convergence of digital communication technologies, participatory storytelling methods, and social change mechanisms. This study examines how digital media and interactive storytelling can create awareness and support social movements. It looks at case studies and existing research to understand their impact. The study also explores how these tools help communities engage and participate in socioeconomic change. This study proposes a comprehensive theoretical framework that integrates transmedia storytelling, digital communication, and social change

theories to understand the dynamics of digital storytelling in promoting socioeconomic development. The findings suggest that successful digital storytelling initiatives share common elements: authentic narrative engagement, strategic platform selection, community participation, and measurable impact metrics. This study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on digital communication for social change by providing practical guidelines for practitioners and theoretical insights for researchers. The study concludes that interactive storytelling through digital media represents a powerful paradigm for achieving sustainable socioeconomic change when strategically implemented with consideration of cultural context and community needs.

Keywords: *Digital media, interactive storytelling, socioeconomic change, transmedia communication, communication strategies, social change, media studies*

DELIVERY GIG WORKERS: A STUDY ON INSTAGRAM REPRESENTATION

K Nihil Nandhaa, Master's Student, Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Central Campus, Bangalore, India. e-mail: nihilnandhaa@gmail.com

The gig economy has witnessed rapid expansion, with delivery services becoming indispensable, particularly during the COVID-19 lockdowns. Social media platforms like Instagram have emerged as spaces where delivery gig workers narrate their experiences, shaping public perceptions and worker identities. However, the extent to which these representations impact societal attitudes remains underexplored. This study investigates how Instagram portrayals influence perceptions of gig workers and their professional standing. The research employs a quantitative content analysis approach, grounded in Social Representation Theory and Media Framing Theory. Data was collected through an online structured survey with 141 respondents, examining themes such as the frequency of posts, dominant narratives, and public engagement with gig worker content. The study aims to assess whether these portrayals align with reality and their effect on workers' self-perception and job satisfaction. Findings reveal that while Instagram representations contribute to the normalization of gig work, they also reinforce stereotypes. Positive narratives highlight flexibility and financial autonomy, whereas struggles related to job insecurity and societal undervaluation persist. Only 31.2% of gig workers perceive Instagram's portrayal as accurate, indicating a significant gap between media representations and lived experiences. Furthermore, outsider-driven content often dominates, leading to an underrepresentation of authentic worker perspectives. This research underscores the need for balanced and inclusive representations that reflect both the opportunities and challenges of gig work. Future studies should explore cross-cultural comparisons and the long-term influence of digital narratives on labor rights and policies. The findings highlight the potential of social media advocacy in improving gig workers' visibility and work conditions.

Keywords: *Gig economy, Instagram representation, delivery workers, media framing, public perception*

DIRECT BENEFIT TRANSFER:

A CATALYST FOR DIGITAL AND FINANCIAL INCLUSION IN INDIA

Kempe Gowda G N, Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Government First Grade College for Women, Byrapura, T Narasipura TQ, Mysore District. e-mail: gowdak94@gmail.com

Digital inclusion refers to the equitable access to digital technologies, including the internet, digital devices, and digital literacy, enabling individuals to participate fully in the digital economy and society. It plays a pivotal role in bridging socio-economic disparities by empowering marginalized communities with access to essential services, information, and financial systems. In developing economies like India, digital inclusion is a critical driver of socio-economic development, fostering financial inclusion, education, healthcare access, and citizen empowerment. To accelerate this process, the Government of India introduced the Direct Benefit Transfer (DBT) scheme in 2013, aimed at transferring subsidies and welfare benefits directly into beneficiary's bank accounts. DBT minimizes leakages, curbs corruption, and enhances transparency by integrating the trinity—Jan Dhan Yojana (bank accounts), Aadhaar (biometric identification), and mobile technology. Digital India initiative indicates significant progress, with over 530 million Jan Dhan accounts and 1.3 billion Aadhaar enrolments enabling seamless DBT transactions. Mobile penetration, reaching approximately 85.4% as of 2024, further strengthens the digital payments ecosystem. Since its inception, DBT has disbursed more than ₹24.8 lakh crore, resulting in savings of around ₹3.48 lakh crore by reducing leakages and ensuring direct delivery of benefits. DBT has not only optimized social welfare delivery but also expanded access to formal financial services among marginalized communities. However, challenges such as digital literacy gaps, last-mile connectivity, and authentication failures persist. This research highlights DBT as a pivotal tool for digital and financial inclusion, advocating for targeted policy measures to address existing barriers and unlock the full potential of DBT in fostering inclusive socio-economic development in India.

Key Words: *Financial Inclusion, Digital Literacy, e-Governance, JAM Trinity*

THE IMPACT OF YOUTUBE & USER-GENERATED CONTENT: ANALYZING CHILDREN & VIEWING HABITS AND PARENTAL MEDIATION

Kokhila R, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli. e-mail:kokhila22896@gmail.com

G.Balasubramania Raja, Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli. e-mail:gbs_raj@yahoo.com

In the digital age, children & exposure to user-generated content (UGC) on YouTube has increased dramatically, largely due to parental use of digital devices. This accessibility exposes children to a vast array of information, often regardless of age appropriateness. Consequently, children may encounter content for which they are not emotionally or cognitively prepared. This includes mature themes, graphic depictions, and complex social issues. For example, they might stumble upon violent imagery, sexually explicit material, or disturbing news reports, leading to anxiety, confusion, and a premature understanding of adult concepts. Such exposure can disrupt their sense of innocence and create a distorted worldview. Furthermore, the limited filters and

age-appropriate safeguards on many social media platforms, particularly YouTube, make children vulnerable to traumatizing and deeply unsettling content. This study will specifically explore these potential distortions through the lens of Cultivation Theory. This theory suggests that prolonged exposure to YouTube & UGC might cultivate a mean world syndrome or other irregular perceptions of reality in children. This study aims to analyze viewing YouTube content of children and to identify effective strategies for parents to mediate and mitigate these risks and to promote their responsible online exploration. To achieve these objectives, this study employs a survey method with parents and educators to gather quantitative data on their experiences and perceptions related to children & exposure to user-generated content on YouTube. The findings will contribute to the development of practical guidelines and educational resources for promoting safe and responsible online practices among children.

Keywords: *YouTube, Children, User-Generated Content (UGC), Parental Guidance, Time Consumption.*

YOUTUBE'S ALGORITHMS AND CASTE-BASED POLITICAL POLARIZATION AMONG URBAN VOTERS IN SAMASTIPUR DURING THE 2024 LOK SABHA ELECTIONS

Kumari Shikha, M.A. Mass Communication, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavur. E-mail: Shikhayadav7667@gmail.com

This study explores the role of YouTube's algorithms in shaping caste-based political polarization among urban voters in Samastipur during the 2024 Lok Sabha Elections. With YouTube becoming a key platform for political content, its recommendation system often amplifies divisive narratives, potentially deepening societal divides. Focusing on urban areas of Samastipur, the research investigates how YouTube's algorithms influence voters' political preferences along caste lines. Using a survey method, the study collects data from urban voters to understand their YouTube usage patterns, the type of political content they consume, and how it affects their views. Preliminary findings suggest that YouTube's algorithms tend to promote caste-based political content, creating echo chambers that reinforce existing biases. This research highlights the platform's impact on political polarization in a region where caste plays a significant role in elections. The study aims to provide insights into the youtube algorithm's influence over democratic processes and suggest ways to promote more balanced political discourse.

Key words: Youtube Algorithms, Political Polarization, Lok Sabha Elections, voters

ROLE OF NEW MEDIA (OTT PLATFORMS) IN CULTURAL HYBRIDIZATION

Lagashetti Priyanka Chandrakant, Research Scholar, Dept. of Mass Communication, P.A.H. Solapur University, Solapur, Maharashtra. e-mail: lagashettipriyanka@gmail.com

Ravindra Chincholkar, Research Guide, Former Head of Dept. of Mass Communication, P.A.H. Solapur University, Solapur, Maharashtra. e-mail: rbchincholkar@gmail.com

The progressive technological advancement paved a way for the development of new media platforms (OTT platforms) which are driven by internet. The popularity of these OTT platforms increased due to several benefits over the conventional media which ultimately leads to the explosion of these platforms in the country. These OTT platforms are enriched and loaded with

wide variety of contents (movies, web series, TV shows, music, podcasts, etc.) showcasing lifestyle, fashion, food, entertainment, language, education, celebration, and social behaviour of different cultures across the world. The accessibility and consumption of global cultural content by Indian audiences, especially the youth, have facilitated a deep integration of modern influences into Indian society. This eventually resulted into the drastic change in the lifestyle, attitude, social behaviour, language use, education, and celebrations of the Indian people representing the cultural hybridization. This sudden cultural shift in the people of Indian society due to the adaptation of the different culture through OTT platforms had significant impact on the Indian societal system. This influence of OTT platforms on young to old age of Indian society greatly contributed to the development of new society with amalgamation of cultures across the world. This research paper examines the role of OTT platforms in shaping cultural hybridization by blending Indian traditions with other modern cultures while critically assessing their social implications. This study also examines the influence of OTT platforms on the youth and on overall Indian society. It also provides the overview of the role of OTT platforms in hybridization of Indian culture with other cultures depicting their pros and cons on the society.

Keywords: *OTT platforms, Indian culture, different modern cultures, cultural hybridization, India, youth*

IMPACT OF E- GOVERNANCE IN SCHEDULED TRIBES IN TELANGANA- A STUDY

Komraiah Palamakula, Senior research scholar, Department of Public Administration, Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana, India.e-mail:palamakulakomuraiah@gmail.com

The present paper deals with the E-governance which means providing public ingress to information via the internet by government departments and their organization. E-governance is widely accepted as an effective tool of service delivery and equated with good governance by all developed countries in general and developing countries like India in particular. National e governance plan was approved in 2006. The purpose of this study is to assess efficiency and effective implications e service centres of Mulugu district, state of Telangana. so many remote and agency areas are there in the state of Telangana, utilizes this centre to fulfil the goals. So, the people of Adivasis are satisfied with the E seva and Me seva centre's in the Mulugu district. The service centre's provides various services i.e. land records, death, birth and caste certificates etc. The response and satisfaction levels of the peoples of Scheduled tribes and their satisfaction towards electronic services. In the present study 80 samples of primary data along with respondents of Mulugu district was collected in state of Telangana. Telangana is 29 the state of our country total population of the state 3,50,03,674, density of population 312, geographical area of the state 1,12,677.01sq.km and Scheduled tribes' population 31,77,940. The sample area of Mulugu district population 2,94,671, in this ratio Scheduled tribe's population 86,352 (29.2) percent, total geographical area 4,126.6 sq.km, density of population 71. Literacy percent of the district 62.3 percent. Mulugu is very smallest district in the state. Majority of students are utilizing services i.e., apply for different recruitment examinations and higher studies. The next priority to farmers receiving the land records, caste, income, and birth certificates etc. Last but not least percent of business or marketing's peoples are utilizing the services.

Keywords: *E-governance, Adivasis, Scheduled tribes, Telangana*

EXPLORING CULTURAL IDENTITY THROUGH VEHICLES GRAFFITI AMONG THE YOUTH IN TIRUNELVELI

M.Benny, I MA Student, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli. e-mail: benny2720@gmail.com

S. G. Veeralakshmanan, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli.

G. Balasubramania Raja, Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli.

Cultural identity is a fundamental aspect of how individuals perceive themselves and interact with the world around them, and in recent years, vehicles have become a significant medium through which youth express their personal and collective cultural identities along Digital media. This research explores the relationship between vehicles and cultural identity, focusing on how young people use cars, bikes, and other forms of transportation as tools for self-expression, social belonging, and cultural storytelling. Through modifications such as custom paint jobs, stickers, decals, and music choices while reversing, youth reflect their heritage, subcultures, and personal narratives. Vehicles often serve as mobile canvases, showcasing a blend of global influences and local traditions, bridging the gap between individual expression and community culture. The study also examines how the youth's engagement with vehicles serves as a reflection of broader societal trends, such as the influence of digital media, globalization, and local cultural movements. By analysing vehicle engagement through Uses and Gratifications Theory, underscores how modern youth consciously select and modify their modes of transportation to meet personal and social needs, reinforcing cultural identity in a era of rapid Globalization, Through In-depth Interview method, Understanding the role of vehicles in youth identity expression offers a deeper insight into how modern youth navigate and negotiate cultural affiliation in a rapidly changing, interconnected world.

Key Word: *Cultural Identity; Adhesive Labelling; Vehicles; Youth; Global Culture*

THE INFLUENCE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI)-GENERATED CONTENT ON MISINFORMATION DISSEMINATION DURING PARLIAMENTARY ELECTION CAMPAIGN (2024)

Madhan K., Teaching Assistant, Department of Visual Communication & Electronic Media, P.S.G. College of arts and science, Coimbatore - 641 014. e-mail: madhan@psgas.ac.in

Radha G., Associate Professor & Head of Department, Department of Visual Communication & Electronic Media, P.S.G. College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore – 641014. e-mail: hodvisualcommunicationua@psgas.ac.in

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is one of the most powerful and useful tools in the digital era. However, AI-powered technologies such as Chat GPT and Gemini can also pose significant risks, making them potentially more dangerous than previous technological advancements. AI is a double-edged sword—it can generate text, images, videos, and audio with remarkable accuracy, reducing human effort. However, AI-generated content is not always 100% accurate. There is a significant possibility that AI can produce misinformation alongside human-created content due to machine learning algorithms & limitations. Misinformation generated by AI can

often be more influential than accurate information, making it easier to spread and be perceived as truthful. As a result, misinformation disseminates rapidly within society, leading people to believe it is correct. This paper focuses on the impact of AI-generated misinformation during Indian parliamentary elections 2024. Analysis of various digital tools involving AI in spreading misinformation among individuals and society will be dealt with.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Misinformation, Dissemination, Parliamentary Election Campaign*

FROM DIGITAL ADOPTION TO ECONOMIC DOMINANCE: INDIA'S PATH TO VIKASIT BHARAT

Madhu G R, Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Shri Siddeshwara Government First Grade, College and P G Studies Centre, Nargund, Gadag, Karnataka. e-mail: madhu.rajgowda01@gmail.com

Duragesh Pujari, Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Shri Siddeshwara Government First Grade College and P G Studies Centre, Nargund, Gadag, Karnataka. e-mail: pkduragesh@gmail.com

India's digital economy has experienced significant growth over the past decade, emerging as a key driver of economic expansion, employment generation, and technological advancement. The State of India's Digital Economy Report 2024 highlights that India ranks as the third-largest digitalised economy globally and 12th among G20 nations in terms of digital adoption at the individual level. The digital economy is projected to contribute nearly 20% of national income by 2029-30, surpassing agriculture and manufacturing. In 2022-23, it accounted for 11.74% of GDP (INR 31.64 lakh crore or USD 402 billion) and employed 14.67 million workers (2.55% of the workforce), with a productivity level nearly five times higher than the rest of the economy. Key drivers include the expansion of digital platforms, artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing, and the rise of global capability centers (GCCs), with India hosting 55% of the world's GCCs. This study employs a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research techniques. An extensive analysis of national accounts data was conducted to estimate the contribution of digital sectors to GDP and employment, alongside a sector-wise breakdown of Gross Value Added (GVA) to assess the role of digital platforms, ICT services, and digital transformation in BFSI, retail, education, logistics, and hospitality. Secondary data from government reports, industry white papers, and market research studies supported projections on digital economy growth, while primary data collection involved stakeholder consultations and industry surveys to gauge digital adoption trends. Structured interviews with digital industry leaders, policymakers, and multinational corporations operating GCCs in India provided insights into AI adoption, cloud computing, and employment impacts, particularly for women. The study finds that digitalisation is progressing unevenly across industries, with retail rapidly adopting omni-channel models and AI-driven inventory management, while BFSI transactions are largely digital, though revenue-generating activities remain offline. The education sector is shifting towards hybrid models, and logistics and hospitality are integrating AI and metaverse applications. The digital economy's expansion, at an anticipated 30% annual growth for digital platforms, is expected to create new employment opportunities, particularly benefiting women and gig workers. As India progresses towards its vision of Viksit Bharat by 2047, a digitally

empowered economy will be fundamental to achieving this goal. The integration of advanced digital technologies across sectors will accelerate financial inclusion, enhance efficiency in governance, and drive innovation-led economic growth. Strengthening digital infrastructure, upskilling the workforce, and ensuring inclusive digital participation will be critical to positioning India as a global digital leader. By fostering a robust ecosystem for digital transformation, India is poised to leverage its digital prowess to build a resilient, sustainable, and inclusive economy—one that aligns with the aspirations of Viksit Bharat.

Key Words: *Digital Economy, Economic Growth, Digital Inclusion*

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL AND EMOTIONAL CHALLENGES FACED BY WOMEN WITH PCOS, ALONG WITH POTENTIAL WAYS MEDIA COULD PROVIDE SUPPORT AND EDUCATION

Madhurima Basak, Department of Media and Communication Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore Central Campus, Bengaluru. e-mail: madhurimabasak378@gmail.com

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a prevalent hormonal problem that affects 5 to 10 percent of women around the worldwide who are of childbearing age. Although there is ample evidence of the physical effects of hirsutism, acne, unpredictable periods, and infertility, but not as much about the mental and emotional ones. Due to changes in weight, hormonal imbalances, and social beauty standards, PCOS women often feel anxious, depressed, and unhappy with their bodies. Concerns about infertility and extended wait times for diagnoses add to mental pain, frustration, and low self-esteem. Many women have feelings of isolation and miscommunication as a result of these difficulties, which are worsened by healthcare providers, peers & lack of awareness. This study looks at how digital media can help people with PCOS deal with their mental health. Digital Platforms, like support groups, educational websites, and social media communities, are very important places to share information, get emotional support, and speak out. One possible way that digital media can help alleviate the emotional impact of polycystic ovary syndrome is by creating a sense of community and shattering negative stereotypes. This study uses a quantitative method to look into how media use affects mental health, how people see themselves, and how well they stick to their treatment plans. Structured surveys and standardized scales are used to measure mental distress, the impact of the media, and how well online support networks work. The results show that digital platforms are very important for reducing false information, improving self-acceptance, and pushing people to take charge of their health. This study shows how important it is to include psychological support in PCOS treatment plans, calling for a more complete approach to care. It also shows how important responsible media coverage is for making people more aware of health issues and better communication about health issues. Digital media can give women with PCOS more power, improve their mental health, and make the healthcare system more helpful by connecting patients and providers.

Key words: *PCOS, mental health, digital media, social support, healthcare communication*

REDEFINING HEROINES: THE WOMEN OF MANI RATNAM'S WORLD

Maduvanthi S., Postgraduate Student, Sathyabama University, Chennai. e-mail: srividhyamadu5@gmail.com

Cinema has a profound impact on society, influencing people's thoughts and worldviews. Directors explore and present difficult concepts using their own methods. Prominent Indian director Mani Ratnam is renowned for fusing regional and international elements to produce films that are compelling and thought-provoking. This study examines the issues and people that Ratnam portrays in his films, with a focus on how he addresses or subverts concepts such as elitism and patriarchy. The goal of the inquiry is to comprehend how cinema may function as a medium for social commentary and as an artistic expression by examining his work. This study looks at how women are portrayed in Mani Ratnam's films and how that addresses or subverts male domination. It focusses on how gender dynamics and cultural expectations are reflected in his characters, narratives, and themes. The study attempts to determine how Ratnam's work either upholds or challenges established gender norms and power structures through a close examination of particular films. The results aim to add to the growing body of knowledge on gender representation in films by demonstrating how Ratnam's works address themes of female struggles and male dominance.

Keywords: *Tamil Cinema, Mani Ratnam, Masochism, Women Portrayal, Story Adaptation.*

PORTRAYALS OF HOUSEWIVES: THE PARADOX IN CONTEMPORARY INDIAN WEB SERIES

Malavika Sunil Karippara, Assistant Professor, Department of Visual Communication Kumaraguru College of Liberal Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. e-mail: malavikasunilk@gmail.com,

Francis P. Barclay, Assistant Professor, Department of Media and Communication School of Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, India. francis@cutn.ac.in,

Indian patriarchy, over hundreds of years, has set conventions for housewives to be submissive feminine figures who are to be subjugated by the males in the family, which includes their husbands, fathers, brothers, male in-laws, and sons. This has translated to media representations. Women have been traditioned to assume domesticated and subdued roles on Indian film screens. They are painted in the media as modestly dressed (often saree-clad), meek, chaste and submissive individuals who spend their lives doing all the household chores and possessing no voices or desires of their own as they sacrifice their entire lives serving their families. Such media portrayals, which are the standard templates in influential storytelling mass media like the silver screen, maintain and propagate such regressive patriarchal norms. This makes it essential to examine media content and create awareness regarding regressive media messages. However, with their distinguished forms and themes, Web series on OTT platforms have opened up an alternative space for contemporary storytelling. The OTT Web series are often applauded by the critiques for their realistic, creative and progressive content, and studying

the depictions of housewives in this medium can help determine whether the same progressive shift towards a more egalitarian direction has taken place in the case of the portrayals of such stereotypical submissive characters. Depictions of more-nuanced characters in the Web series can be material for inspection to study contemporary ideas about gender and Indian culture. Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) of five popular Indian Web series released during 2019-2021 (Panchayat, Aarya, Scam 1992, Tabbar and Gullak) identified two prominent discourses engaged in a discursive struggle while conforming to and contesting traditional gender norms. Both the discourses are characterised in the study using several discourse analyses tools and the paradoxes in them are explicated.

Keywords: *Gender, Critical Discourse Analysis, Patriarchy and Indian Web Series*

REPRESENTATION OF DESIRES AND INTIMACY: CINEMATIC CHARACTERISATION OF THE DISABLED

Malavika Sunil Karippara , Assistant Professor, Kumaraguru College of Liberal Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. email: malavikasunilk@gmail.com

Devika P, Assistant Professor, Kumaraguru College of Liberal Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. e-mail: vikram.devikal@gmail.com

The discourse of relationship between cinema screen and audience has always explained the influences of on-screen representations in the minds of the viewers. The study recognizes that while disability has been a recurrent theme in cinema, the portrayal of the inner desires of disabled individuals has not received adequate attention. This study aims to understand the perceptions of young minds on the cinematic representation of the desires and personal relationships of disabled people. For this purpose, the study employs focus-group discussions and utilises qualitative data collected to critically analyse how young audiences perceive on-screen personal relationships and romances involving disabled characters. The choice of three South Indian movies, namely Cuckoo (2014), Bangalore Days (2014), and Vasanthiyum Lakshmiyum Pinne Njaanum (1999), is purposeful and based on participants; recall sessions. These movies are screened to the focus group, and the subsequent discussions aim to provide insights into the audience reactions, interpretations, and reflections on the representation of romantic relationships involving disabled characters in these films. The study found that social disconnection with the disabled community was the major reason for young viewers accepting the depictions of intimate desires of disabled characters in the movies and taking cinema as a reference point for understanding the same. They opined that they always get connected with the on screen romances of abled characters but were not able to establish any sense of connection when played by disabled characters.

Keywords: *disability, stereotypes, desires and personal relationships, viewer perceptions, south Indian cinema, constructed reality, focus group*

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND EMPLOYMENT SHIFTS: A STUDY ON INDIA & GIG ECONOMY EVOLUTION

Manasa H, Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Maharani's Arts College for Women, JLB, Road, Mysore-570005. e- mail: manasacoll03@gmail.com

The rapid advancement of digital technologies has reshaped global employment landscapes, with the gig economy playing a transformative role in India. This study investigates the employment transition in India & gig economy, driven by digitalization, rising urbanization, and evolving labor market demands. The gig workforce, currently estimated at 8 million, is projected to surge to 90 million jobs by 2030, contributing approximately 1.25% to India & GDP. The research highlights how gig platforms have emerged as key drivers of employment, particularly in transportation, e-commerce, and personal services sectors. Data from the ILO suggests that India holds 20% of the global platform workforce share, making it the largest supplier of gig workers worldwide. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of gig work, with youth participation increasing eightfold between 2019 and 2022. Despite offering flexible income opportunities, the gig economy faces significant challenges, including job insecurity, lack of social protection, and income variability. Research findings underscore the need for comprehensive policy frameworks to enhance worker protections and social security coverage. The study advocates for digital literacy programs, financial inclusion initiatives, and targeted skill development schemes to bridge the skills gap and empower marginalized groups. Institutional collaborations between government agencies, platform companies, and worker organizations are essential to fostering a sustainable and inclusive gig economy. This research contributes to the ongoing discourse on the future of work in India and provides actionable insights for policymakers and stakeholders.

Key Words: *Gig Economy, Digital Transformation, Platform Workforce, Employment Transition*

TOWARD INCLUSIVE RADIO JOURNALISM IN INDIA: A CASE FOR DEMOCRATIZING NEWS IN INDIA

Mochish K S, Academician, FLAME University, Pune, Maharashtra. e-mail: mochish@flame.edu.in

Media in India has experienced a radical transformation in the past few decades. The rapid technological changes and newly emerged ownership patterns in the media system since liberalisation have radically impacted our interactions with the media. At the same time, it has also made an impact on all aspects of media from its production to distribution. The arrival of digital technologies propelled the emergence of numerous social media platforms, which have redefined the content, structure, and accessibility of traditional media across societies all over the world. News and current affairs programmes on radio are vital for the future of any democracy. However, India could be the only democracy in the world where the government still controls news on private radio channels. The government's control over the program content on radio is a major obstacle to achieving an independent media ecosystem. Similarly, the lack of information-related programme content on these platforms could make private FM radio an outdated medium in the years to come. This paper attempts to understand the importance of democratising radio news in India. Further, it also offers an understanding of the discussions on radio news in India and the need for news and current affairs programmes on private FM radio.

Key words: *Radio Journalism, Indian Media, Monopoly, Democracy*

A WALK THROUGH THE SACRED GROVE IN NORTHEAST INDIA: ORAL NARRATIVES AND ENVIRONMENT CONSERVATION

Monalisha Medhi, Assistant Professor, The Assam Royal Global University.

e-mail: mmedhi1@rgu.ac Contact- 7002683269

Sacred Groves in North East India represent a long tradition of environmental conservation by the tribal communities. These are tracts of virgin forests, left untouched by local inhabitants which are significant of their cultural values and religious beliefs. These tribal communities make use of the vast treasure trove of indigenous knowledge for the protection of the groves as well as the thriving biodiversity in the interiors. Serving as the natural habitat for biodiversity, these sacred groves are among the least disturbed forest patches in. Prevailing from generation to generation as the words of mouth, oral narratives are significant to the conservation of these wilder patches. The local deities, religious beliefs, etc. form the crux of these narratives and pose as the sacred elements of these forests. To appease these deities, certain rituals are performed, along with keeping the sanctity of the sacred elements intact. Thus, it prevents local people and anyone from outside from cutting down of it. In this light, this research paper aims to look at the sustainable methods carried out along with traditional practices, rites and rituals in protecting and conserving the sacred groves of by the tribal communities of North East India, with a special reference to the Mawphlang Sacred Groves in Meghalaya. Moreover, it aims to look at the legends prevalent among the local inhabitants, associated narratives and folklore, the possessed threats and exploitation of tribal faith and beliefs, which are also associated with their identities.

Keywords: *Sacred Groves, Traditional practices, Sustainability, Tribal faith and beliefs*

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES DURING DISASTER BY COMMUNITY RADIO

Mousami Jena, Research scholar, Dept. of Electronic Media & Mass Communication, Pondicherry, University, e-mail: jena.mousami@pondiuni.ac.in

Community Radio directs to provide a counter-narrative to mainstream media and eliminate negative sensationalism and commercial interest tendencies. These institutions play a crucial role in social and economic development but often face inequalities that can hinder their overall impact. Recently, a standard code of practice was revised as policy guidelines for community radio by the Ministry Of Information and Broadcasting (2024, Feb13) Revised Policy Guidelines for setting up Community Radio Stations in India. It caused disillusionment with the current policy that restrains maximum transmission radiated power to 250 W, which is to be considered on a case-to-case basis as necessary by the Ministry of Communication. Community Radio acts as an alternative medium and becomes essential in studying the media representation of underprivileged communities in India and the inequality persisting in covering the critical aspects that afflict the hyperlocal medium. Community Radio is one such proxy that demonstrates its functional nature in emergencies for disaster-coordinated relief where all other mediums get disconnected for the marginalised. This study aims to recognize the community radio stations at higher risk in disaster-prone areas and analyse their comprehensive efforts through programs that ensure their continuity during a crisis. The study will thus be undertaken for the CR stations to identify the infrastructural support for the affected community radio stations during natural calamities. The research interest also lies in understanding the policy

guidelines and its expansion to study the long-term programming activities pertaining to relief and recovery that the community demands for the smooth functioning of the medium during disaster.

Keywords: *Community radio, Disaster Communication, Policy Expansion, Resilience, Emergency*

A HOLISTIC ANALYSIS OF GENDER INEQUALITY AND PAY GAP IN INDIAN CINEMA AND MEDIA

Mythili Nair, Postgraduate Student, Department of Media Studies,
CHRIST (Deemed To Be University) Bengaluru. e-mail: mythilimadan.nair@mamcs.christuniversity.in

Vikas Chauhan, Assistant Professor, Postgraduate Student, Department of Media Studies,
CHRIST (Deemed To Be University) Bengaluru.

This literature review examines gender inequality and the persistent pay gap in Indian cinema and media. It explores historical contexts, societal norms, and representation in films and media, highlighting the challenges women face both on-screen and behind the scenes. The scarcity of female representation reinforces harmful gender norms and biased portrayals, perpetuating systemic inequalities. The review critically analyses the marginalization of women, the normalization of sexual harassment in the industry, and the impact of the MeToo movement on workplace safety. It addresses pay disparities and the dominance of men in key industry roles, emphasizing the need for a more inclusive media landscape. Despite some progress, gender disparities persist, requiring further research. Key gaps include the intersection of gender with caste, ethnicity, sexual orientation, and disability in media. Additionally, the role of social media influencers and digital platforms in shaping gender norms is an area needing deeper investigation. This study calls for ongoing efforts to create a diverse and equitable industry. By addressing systemic biases and fostering inclusive practices, meaningful change can be achieved. Continued research is essential to understanding gender dynamics and ensuring progress toward a fairer Indian cinema and media landscape.

Keywords: *Gender inequality, pay gap, Indian cinema, Representation, MeToo movement, intersectionality*

AGRICULTURAL LABOURERS IN KARNATAKA – TRENDS AND PROBLEMS

Nagarathamma.K. S., Asst. Prof., Department of sociology, KRCE's GGD Arts, BMP Commerce & SVS Science College, Bailhongal, Rani channamma University, Belagavi.

M.Prashanth, Faculty, Department of sociology, Maharaja's College, University of Mysore, Mysuru. e-mail:prashanth101089@gmail.com

Agriculture labourers have become the most significant component in Indian agriculture. A little less than half of the total cost of manufacture of field crop is of labour. Economic expansion of any countries leads to structural changes in the work-related allocation. It meant that employment in the agricultural sector declined and it rose in the secondary and tertiary sector. Agricultural labourers naturally work long hours in physically difficult conditions, and their wages may be low down compared to other types of work. They may work on a recurring or

temporary basis, and may be working by individual farmers, agricultural cooperatives, or larger agribusinesses. In spite of the challenges and uncertainties of agricultural labour, it is a vital component of worldwide food production, providing the necessary labour force to hold up the farming and harvesting of crops and livestock. The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the significance of agricultural labourers, who have sustained to work throughout the pandemic to make certain a steady supply of food. However, the pandemic has also uncovered vulnerabilities in the worldwide food system, particularly with respect to issues of food uncertainty and labour rights. In the present study is seeks to understand the trends, problems and prospects of agricultural labourers in Karnataka as well as in India. Present study purely on the basis of secondary data collected for various census reports, journals, government records and related website, result of this study was the percentage of agricultural labourers in Karnataka has increased from 16.65 % to 28.74 % in 1991; gender wise analysis of agricultural labourers showed that the male agricultural labourers were greater than before in both rural and urban areas; The growth in genuine wages for male and female labour at the national level was 0.33 % and 0.45 % during 2014 to 2022 correspondingly.

Keywords: *Agricultural labour, decadal growth rate, agricultural trends, Karnataka*

POLITICAL INFORMATION AS POLITICAL CURRENCY: REDEFINING POLITICAL ENGAGEMENTS ON CYBERSPACE

Namit Vikram Singh, Faculty, Delhi School of Journalism, University of Delhi.
e-mail: nams.namit@dsj.du.ac.in

Durgesh Tripathi, Head, University School of Mass Communication GGSIP University.
e-mail drdurgeshtripathi@ipu.ac.in

The given paper explores the new forms of political engagements shaped through cybermedia through the use of political information as political currency. The traditional forms of political participation involved the mobilization of masses. However, the process of mobilization was based on how the conversion of socio-cultural capital to political capital was taking place in offline spaces. With the advent of digital media and information being the prime currency for exchange, there has been a transformation in the manner people are engaging with one another based on trust, commonality, ideology and many other parameters. The fundamental aspect to be noted is that the volatility associated with the information along with its attributes of converting into a specific type of information exchange, based on context, has redefined the nature of political engagement on digital media. Information having political traits and the capability for exchange are being used as a form of currency for social interactions, digital mobilization and even political action. The fundamental focus of this paper is to understand how cybermedia has redefined political information in becoming a form of currency for digital engagements and what factors are involved in its process of conversion and reconversion. The paper includes certain cases of India to substantiate the given argument. The paper incorporates a mixed-method approach in exploring the qualitative and quantitative dimensions of the study.

Keywords: *Political Capital, Social Currency, Transubstantiation, Political Communication, Social Engagement.*

CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING: A CASE STUDY IN MYSORE CITY

Nandeesh H K, HoD & Assistant Professor, PG Department of Economics, St. Philomena's College Mysuru, India. e-mail: nandeeshahk@stphilos.ac.in

Ashwini K J, Assistant Professor, PG Department of Economics, St. Philomena's College Mysuru, India

The rapid growth of internet purchasing has transformed the global business landscape. Online shopping has gained immense popularity due to its convenience, allowing consumers to compare offers, avoid long queues, and shop from anywhere. In today's fast-paced world, it serves as a practical, time-saving, and user-friendly alternative to traditional shopping. Key advantages include special discounts, 24/7 availability, reduced travel costs, broader market access, and a wider product selection. This study, both descriptive and analytical in nature, employed primary and secondary data. A structured questionnaire was administered to 100 respondents, capturing their socioeconomic profiles, preferences, perceptions, frequency of online purchases, satisfaction levels, and challenges encountered. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS software, employing descriptive statistics, frequency analysis, reliability and normality testing, along with statistical methods such as the Chi-square test, Kruskal-Wallis test, and Mann-Whitney U test. Findings indicate that while online shopping offers numerous benefits, concerns remain regarding convenience, product quality, customer satisfaction, privacy, and security. The study underscores the evolving nature of consumer preferences and the need for technological advancements to enhance secure transactions. It also highlights the increasing significance of e-commerce in everyday life.

Key words: *Consumer Behaviour, Online Shopping, Purchase Preferences, Customer Satisfaction*

EMOTION-DRIVEN ENGAGEMENT: A SENTIMENT ANALYSIS ON HOW EMOTION WORKS IN SUSTAINABILITY INSTAGRAM INFLUENCERS' POSTS

Nithyanandhan Soundarrajan, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore. e-mail: 22pmcf01@psgcas.ac.in

Jayaprakash C R, Associate Professor, Head, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

Gouri S Dev, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, PSG College of Arts & Science, Coimbatore.

Instagram influencers play a crucial role in influencing people to adapt sustainable and pro-environmental behaviours by engaging audiences by creating a personal connection with them. Their reach, engagement, narrative storytelling, and their ability to connect with the audience make them effective agents of sustainability capable of inspiring and mobilising people towards more sustainable lifestyles. This study examines the emotional and thematic content of the posts of 8 famous sustainability influencers. The researchers have used instaloader, a python-based tool to scrape the posts of the influencers. Through a detailed emotional analysis using Text2Emotion tool, fear emerged as the most dominant emotion, followed by happiness. Influencers who often address urgent environmental issues like climate change and plastic pollution motivate their audience to adapt sustainable actions. The higher engagement rates to the fear-based posts show that they are very effective in capturing the attention and interest of the audience. The study also found that happiness is an equally used emotion to promote increased

awareness and proactive engagement in sustainability. The study highlights the significance of emotional appeal in environmental communication, showing that both fear and happiness can be strategically used to foster greater awareness and proactive engagement in sustainability. These findings offer valuable insights for influencers and content creators aiming to enhance their impact on environmental advocacy.

Keywords: *Sentiment Analysis, Instagram, Fear Appeal, Social Media Analysis, Influencers, Sustainability*

THE POWER OF MEMES IN DIGITAL COMMUNICATION: BRIDGING HUMOUR, EMOTION, AND SOCIAL ACTIVISM IN ONLINE COMMUNITIES DURING ELECTION

P Sri Jothi, Assistant Professor, Department of Media Sciences, CEG Anna University, Chennai. Tamilnadu. India. e-mail: srijothidms@gmail.com

M Thulasi Bharathy, Assistant Professor, Department of Animation, Vels Institute of Science, Technology and Advanced Studies. Chennai. Tamilnadu. India. . e-mail: thulasi.smc@velsuniv.ac.in

Memes serve as a common vernacular among online users, facilitating the exchange of concepts, sentiments, and occurrences in a succinct and frequently comical manner. Memes possess the ability to communicate intricate emotions or responses that may prove challenging to articulate through language alone, thereby promoting a feeling of camaraderie and mutual comprehension among virtual societies. The rapid dissemination of information and viral spread: Memes possess the capacity to propagate expeditiously throughout the internet, thereby attaining a vast audience within a brief duration. The potential of this phenomenon to become widespread can be utilised to increase consciousness regarding significant matters, disseminate knowledge, and initiate dialogues. Memes have been employed as a means of engaging in political activism, raising public awareness, and advocating for social causes. The present research comprises of qualitative study adopted discourse analysis method to find its major objective. Multiple memes trolled during Tamilnadu Legislative Assembly elections 2021 where collected from various social media platforms and the same were evaluated with respect to six varied factors of discourse analysis. Thus study entailed to explore the power of memes and its influencing political strategic communication through social media during election.

Keywords: *Social Media Memes, Opinion Leader, Discourse Analysis, Political communication, Impact*

MEDIA INTERVENTIONS IN HEALTH COMMUNICATION AND BEHAVIORAL CHANGE AMONG WOMEN IN MYSURU AND CHAMARAJANAGAR: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Pema Dechan, Post-Graduation Department of Studies and Research in Journalism and Mass Communication, St. Philomena's College (AUTONOMOUS), Mysuru. e-mail: pema8001@gmail.com

Vagdevi H.S., Assistant Professor, Post-Graduation Department of Studies and Research in Journalism and Mass Communication, St. Philomena's College (AUTONOMOUS), Mysuru. e-mail: vagdevihs@stphilos.ac.in

Media interventions play a critical role in shaping health communication and influencing public awareness and health-seeking behaviours. However, limited research has explored how various media platforms affect health communication and behavioural change among women in

both urban and rural contexts, such as in Mysuru and Chamarajanagar districts. This study examines the role of media in health communication among women by analysing media consumption patterns, assessing the influence of media on health-related behavioural changes, and identifying challenges in accessing and trusting health information across different channels. A quantitative research design was employed using structured, in-person surveys administered to 300 women from both urban and rural areas of Mysuru and Chamarajanagar, with non-probability convenience sampling and supplementary secondary data from existing literature and reports. Findings reveal that while digital platforms such as social media, YouTube, and health apps are increasingly used for health communication, traditional media like television, radio, and newspapers remain the most trusted sources, especially in rural areas. The study also highlights challenges such as misinformation, digital illiteracy, and socio-cultural barriers, with urban women exhibiting higher engagement with digital content compared to their rural counterparts who rely more on community-based communication. Overall, media interventions hold significant potential to improve health literacy and empower women to make informed decisions, but addressing issues of misinformation, accessibility, and trust is essential. Future research should focus on developing targeted, evidence-based communication strategies that integrate both traditional and digital media to ensure reliable, accessible, and culturally appropriate health communication for women across diverse socio-economic settings.

Keywords: Media Interventions, Health Communication, Behavioural Change, Digital Media, Women's Health

AI IN EMOTIONAL SUPPORT: WHY DO YOUNGSTERS SEEK EMOTIONAL SUPPORT FROM AI CHATBOTS?

Preethika S, M.A. Mass Communication, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur. E-mail: preethikasambantham@gmail.com

Gondi Surender Dhanunjay, Research Fellow, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur.

Shamala Ramappa, Assistant Professor, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvarur.

This Research paper explores why young people seek emotional support from AI chatbots like ChatGPT and Replica. Many prefer these chatbots because they are always available, offer a judgment-free space, and provide personalized responses. This Research employs a qualitative approach, using in-depth interviews with individuals aged 18–30, and thematic analysis to examine motivations, usage patterns, and emotional reliance on chatbots. And also to know how chatbots help with loneliness, stress, and emotional challenges. While chatbots are a convenient and safe option, they have limits in addressing complex emotional needs. This study provides insights into the role of AI among youngsters and why youngsters seek emotional support from AI chatbots

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Chatbots, Emotional support, emotional intelligence, Youngsters, anonymity, Mental health.

**THE EVOLUTION AND SIGNIFICANCE OF FILM ORGANIZATIONS:
ANALYSING THE HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE AND ASSESSMENT OF
MERGING INSTITUTIONS UNDER THE UMBRELLA OF NFDC WITH THE NEW
FILM POLICY FOCUSING ON FILM DIVISION PARTICULARLY.**

Pushkar J, Postgraduate Student, Department of Media Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University),
Bangalore.e-mail: summerrainpictures@gmail.com

This research paper delves into the dynamic development of film organizations and their vital role in the Indian film industry. It emphasizes the context of history and fundamental change brought about by coming together of significant organizations under the National Film Development Corporation (NFDC) umbrella along with the embracement of the New Film Policy. The study starts with a critical analysis of the historical evolution of Indian film institutions, from their inception in the early years of cinema to the current times. It highlights the significance of these institutions in shaping the Indian film industry, both culturally and financially. In addition, the article analyzes the move to bring under the NFDC many of the film-related agencies, analyzing the reasons, issues, and expected advantages of this consolidation. It attempts to detect the implications of this merger on the functioning and effectiveness of these organizations, along with its general effect on the development and stability of the Indian film industry, through intense analysis. In addition, the study explores the utmost importance of the New Film Policy in triggering this institutional convergence. It examines the most important elements of the policy, demonstrating how they align with global trends and agendas in the film industry. In addition, it appraises the capacity of the policy to drive innovation, enhance partnership, and cultivate new talent in the Indian film industry. In order to give an entire picture of the topic, the research adopts a multifaceted approach, combining historical analysis, policy assessment, and industrial perspectives. It makes its findings and conclusions on the basis of primary data sources, expert interviews, and case studies. Last but not least, this research study adds to better insight into changing dynamics of Indian film organizations and their vital contribution to determining the future of the Indian film industry. It enlightens us as to the probable consequences of consolidating organizations under NFDC, in the light of the New Cinema Policy, and offers valuable inputs for policymakers, industry participants, and film enthusiasts all the same. The interest in knowing about the appeals of different sets of employees in the concerned institutions in times of situations that ultimately resulted in raising it in the market was the motivating factor. The journey of different decisions and the passing of new acts were debated by colleagues over lunch breaks on film sets, which helped me in note-taking and getting a rough idea. While having a deep discussion, the analysis of the contradictions of the stakeholders to the policy in their own words with some key stakeholders from the world of films on the basis of their real-life working experiences within the respective organizations.

Keywords: *Indian Film Organizations, Historical Perspective, Film Division, National Film Archive of India, Children Film Society of India, Directorate of Film Festivals, Indian Documentary, Film Organizations, National Film Policy, Film Unit, Ministry of Information and Broadcasting.*

MEDIUM IS THE MESSAGE : REVISITING MARSHALL MCLUHAN

Poarkodi Natarajan, Academician, SRMIST, Kattankulathur, Chennai. e-mail: poarkodi@gmail.com

Communication theory and communication studies in the “post-McLuhan period” have moved in various directions, but, in most part, has missed/misconceived a key link that Marshall McLuhan professed - “Medium is the Message”. This aphorism and its conception have been variously interpreted in the context of mass media and of late, online media or utmost extended to traditional media and human communication. McLuhan's exposition, however, goes beyond this conventional sense of media and communication. The interchangeability of the terms medium and technology and the notion of media as extensions of man are significant to re-imagine the limited perception of medium as “mediated or non-mediated human communication”. Apparently, McLuhan's examples, wheel, light bulb etc., holds mirror to this broad investment and provides scope for further expansion. Every individual or every work they indulge in can be reinvestigated through McLuhan's lens – for instance, quilt is a medium used by the individual to communicate a “message.” Likewise, embroidery, footwear, carpentry, jewellery, etc. could be a medium. This paper delves deeper into McLuhan's work and attempts to decipher the meanings encoded beyond the conventional communication contexts to which it is applied. This paper attempts to apply the theoretical framework of communication theorist Ravindran Gopalan on the concept of medium beyond the limits of technological media. Further, the paper will visit the works of Baudrillard, Kittler, Kramer and Kellner to understand McLuhan in a broader light.

Keywords : *McLuhan, Medium, Technology, Mediation, Message*

CULTURAL SENSITIVITY IN POLITICAL COMMUNICATION

Prerana Singh, Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru. e-mail: prerana.singh@mamcs.christuniversity.in

Naresh Rao, Professor, Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru.

Social media platforms, especially Facebook, play a key role in modern political communication by enabling direct interaction with voters. This study examines how cultural sensitivity in political messaging affects voter engagement, focusing on the Bharatiya Janata Party's (BJP) Facebook public relations (PR) campaigns in Uttar Pradesh during the Lok Sabha elections. Research suggests that political messages using familiar cultural symbols, language, and traditions can strengthen voter connections, while a lack of cultural awareness may lead to disengagement. The study aims to understand how cultural sensitivity influences political engagement in digital campaigns. It analyzes BJP's Facebook posts using quantitative content analysis, categorizing them based on cultural themes and assessing engagement metrics (likes, shares, comments). Statistical methods are used to measure how effective culturally embedded communication is in engaging voters. Additionally, this study explores how regional differences, and demographic factors impact audience responses to culturally specific messaging. Findings show that posts incorporating cultural symbols and language receive higher engagement than

those that do not. Furthermore, posts that align with regional traditions and identity markers generate stronger voter interest and participation. This highlights the importance of culturally tailored political messaging in connecting with voters and fostering political support. The study contributes to the understanding of digital political communication and provides insights for political strategists on creating effective, culturally sensitive campaigns. Future research can explore how evolving social media trends influence voter behavior over time.

Keywords: *Cultural Sensitivity, Political Communication, Facebook, Voter Engagement, Digital Campaigning, Regional Identity*

NAVIGATING THE DIGITAL FRONTIER: INSIGHTS INTO VOTER PERCEPTION AND CAMPAIGN STRATEGIES IN THE 2024 LOK SABHA ELECTIONS

Priya Evangeline, Freelance Content Creator, Mysuru, Karnataka. e-mail: priyaevangeline56@gmail.com

Vagdevi H S, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Post Graduate Studies and Research in Journalism and Mass Communication, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Mysuru, Karnataka.

The 2024 Lok Sabha Elections in India represented a significant shift in political campaigning, driven largely by the adoption of Generative AI technologies, including deepfakes, chatbots, and AI-generated content (Business Standard, 2023). This study aims to explore how these technologies influenced voter perceptions and campaign strategies, particularly among youth voters in Bangalore and Mysore. It delves into public awareness of AI, ethical concerns surrounding its use, and the potential impact of AI-driven misinformation on electoral outcomes (DGAP, 2023). Voter awareness and perceptions of Generative AI, focusing on its role in shaping election information and influencing decision-making. It evaluates the reliability and credibility of AI-generated content. Through voter's analysis and interviews with political strategists, the research aims to provide insights into AI's evolving impact on electoral processes. Through a mixed-method approach, the research combines quantitative surveys assessing voter behaviour, trust levels, and awareness of AI with qualitative interviews of political strategists. Initial findings indicate that trust in Generative AI varies significantly with educational background; higher education correlates with increased skepticism toward AI-generated news. Additionally, age differences play a crucial role in shaping voter behaviour and perceptions regarding AI-generated content in digital media. Qualitative findings reveal that AI integration into political campaigns enhances voter outreach and data analysis but raises concerns about misinformation and privacy. The collaboration between AI-driven digital platforms and traditional media is reshaping political communication, requiring ethical monitoring to reduce risks while maximizing AI's benefits. The study underscores the urgent need for responsible use of AI to protect democratic integrity in an increasingly complex electoral landscape.

Keywords: *Generative AI, Political Campaigning, Lok Sabha Elections 2024, Misinformation, Digital Media*

THE IMPACT OF LEGACY MEDIA: CREATIVE POSTERS TO FOSTER YOUTH MENTAL HEALTH AND SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

R.Vasantharaj, Scholar, Dept. of Electronic Media & Mass Communication, Pondicherry. University. e-mail: vasantharaj.scholar@pondiuni.ac.in

V. Shanthi Siri, Dept. of Electronic Media & Mass Communication, Pondicherry, University

Youth mental health and social responsibility are critical areas of concern in today's world, with alarming statistics revealing a global crisis. According to the World Health Organization (2024), 1 in 7 youth worldwide face mental health disorders, with suicide ranking as the third leading cause of death among those aged 15-29. In India, the country with the largest adolescent population globally, over 51% of youth are distressed or struggling (The Hindu, 2023). Mental health, a state of well-being, profoundly influences relationships and engagement with society and the environment. Addressing the mental health crisis is crucial to cultivating socially responsible behaviours, including pro-environmental practices essential for sustainable development. Pro-environmental behaviour encompasses actions that minimize harm to the planet, such as reducing energy consumption, conserving water, and promoting sustainable habits. Cultivating such behaviour among youth can play a pivotal role in mitigating environmental challenges. However, innovative and impactful communication tools are necessary to foster these behaviours effectively. Posters, as visual aids, have been recognized as one of the most effective tools for raising awareness and influencing behaviour (Gobind & Ukpere, 2014). They reinforce educational content and encourage positive behavioural shifts, particularly among youth (Dallyono & Sukyadi, 2019). Yet, most awareness posters fail to connect deeply with their audience, often lacking the emotional engagement or personal relevance required for lasting impact (Hidalgo et al., 2014). The study was conducted by exhibiting & YOU ARE LUCKY & posters during the Trust for Youth and Child Leadership (TYCL) mental health exhibition held in Puducherry from October 8–10, 2024. These posters, grounded in Gestalt theory, were designed to emotionally engage adolescents and connect with their personal experiences to encourage pro-environmental behaviours and social responsibility. Survey results from the exhibition indicated that creative, customized posters effectively influenced youth, fostering mental health awareness and inspiring socially responsible actions. This study emphasizes the transformative power of thoughtfully designed visual communication tools, demonstrating the continued relevance of legacy media in promoting positive social change.

Keywords: *Youth Mental Health, Social Responsibility, Pro-environmental Behaviour, Gestalt Theory, Visual communication*

EDUCATION WITHOUT BOUNDARIES: BREAKING SOCIOECONOMIC BARRIERS TO INCLUSION

Radha Gupta, Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Shri Ratanlal Kanwarlal Patni Girls' College, Kishangarh, Rajasthan. e-mail: radhagupta2000@gmail.com

A person life can be changed by education. However, millions of people worldwide still cannot afford schooling. Poverty, a lack of resources, and systematic injustices are socioeconomic barriers that have prevented many adults and children from accessing

educational opportunities. Since education is supposed to be a means of achieving a brighter future for everyone, it shouldn't be a privilege reserved for the wealthy. This study examines how financial difficulties impact education and, more importantly, outlines the obstacles that must be removed in order to create a learning environment that is truly inclusive for all. A decent school, specially designed learning resources, or simply a secure environment are inaccessible to many. Schools may be located distant from homes or may not have enough teachers. In outlying and rural areas, technology might be an unachievable goal. Because low-income kids have a harder time keeping up in an increasingly digital world, the digital divide has made the gap even more pronounced. If governments and officials want to prioritise education for all children, regardless of their financial situation, then things can change. This ought to result in financing for education in underserved communities, offering financial aid to children in need, and implementing programs like free school lunches and financial rewards to keep kids in school. Communities and educators should consider other approaches to problem-solving, such as mobile learning centres in isolated villages or the use of technology to connect the digitally disadvantaged. Working together, governments, corporations, and non-profits may help close the educational gap by providing resources, mentorship, and creative learning models to the places that most need them.

Keywords: *Inclusion, Equity, Access, Empowerment*

FROM CREATORS TO CONSUMERS: HOW USER-GENERATED CONTENT SHAPES COLLEGE STUDENTS' PURCHASE INTENTION

Rajeshwari N, Research Scholar, Mother Teresa Women's University. e-mail:rajeshwari.n26@gmail.com

Lourdu Vesna J, Asst Prof. of Visual Communication Dept, Mother Teresa Women's University. e-mail: vesnaj20@gmail.

Marketing has undergone a significant transformation. With the evolution of social media platforms, user-generated content (UGC) has become one of the powerful tools to transform consumers behaviour. Multiple-way communication is feasible compared to traditional advertising methods. The study aims to explore college students & responses to user-generated content, focusing on engagement, trust and purchase intention. The research utilises a quantitative method that includes surveys to study the perceptions of UGC and to uncover the decision mechanisms among student communities who are regarded as tech-savvy. The survey aims to determine the targeted populations awareness of the hazards of UGC manipulation (fake reviews, sponsored content). The key takeaway is that college students cherish receiving user-generated content and evaluate social media ads based on their reliability, relatability and authenticity. One of the key theoretical contributions of our framework is to extend existing ones that help better understand user-generated content increase engagement and foster trust, ultimately leading to purchase intention. The study provides valuable insight for advertisers to optimize their social media strategies for targeting college students.

Keywords: *User-generated content (UGC), Social Media Advertising, College Students, Consumer Behaviour, Sponsored content*

DIGITAL MEDIA ETHICS: A NOTE ON INDIAN LEGAL SYSTEM

Rangaswamy D, Assistant Professor of Law, Karnataka State Law University, Karnataka, India
e-mail: ksludrdrswamy@gmail.com

Digital Media Ethics (DME) has been recognized as one of the crucial elements of digital governance of a country. It regulates Digital Media entities and ensure Cyber Security by stipulating minimum standards to be followed by the digital actors in their activities. It also offers unique opportunity to root out cyber world challenges such as misinformation and fake news, privacy and confidentiality, digital manipulations and deception, unfair and biased information and cybercrimes. Despite adoption ideal legal system for media ethics in general and the Information Technology (Intermediary Guidelines and Digital Media Ethics Code) Rules, 2021 particularly for DME, the cybersecurity is at greater risk. This disturbing state of affair of the cyber world has necessitated us to rethinking and rewiring our thoughts about the efficacy of system meant for DME. In this context, the purpose of this study is to take up DME as a research topic to address trends, practices and dynamisms of the legal systems in encapsulating DME and weaponizing the same against cybersecurity. The qualitative research methodology has been adopted by the author to analyze various legal as well as cyber security related sources collected through different database. It is evident from the current practices the Indian legal system is matured enough in legislating on DME. However, implementation of this legal mechanism and self-centered ethical duty on the part of digital media is very negligible. The paper concludes that there is a need of stringent implementation of the legal mechanism and reinforcement of professional codes of the media entities. Much importantly, there is a need of meaningful contribution of citizenry duties to implement the existing mechanisms in its letter and spirit.

Key Words: *Digital, Media, Ethics, India, Law, Challenges*

REPRESENTATION OF WOMEN IN INDIAN OTT CRIME THRILLERS: A CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF NETFLIX CONTENT IN 2024

Raviraja I Vadigeri, Research Scholar, PG Department of Studies & Research in Journalism & Mass Communication, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous) Mysuru. email: ravirajaivadigeri@stphilos.ac.in

Vagdevi H S, Assistant Professor, PG Department of Studies & Research in Journalism & Mass Communication, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous) Mysuru.

The emergence of over-the-top (OTT) platforms has significantly changed content viewing trends and allowed for the creation of varied storylines beyond media constructs. OTT has become one of the most popular and influential forms of mass media, it has promoted a binge-watching habit among viewers. It provides content in various genres to its audience. As digital media has been praised for its inclusiveness and diversity, concerns still arise about women's presentation in the recent OTT content. Employing critical discourse analysis (CDA), this study examines the representation of female characters in selected OTT crime thriller content in 2024. By critically examining a sample of selected streaming content based on its ratings and viewership, this study explores digital narratives of gender roles, agency, and stereotype. This paper uses feminist media theory and examines whether OTT content challenges or upholds prevailing gender stereotypes. The researcher aims to assess how these portrayals influence gender perception and power dynamics, contributing to broader discussions on women's representation in digital entertainment.

Keywords: *Women & representation, OTT platform, Crime genre, Netflix, Critical discourse analysis.*

MEDIA AND FREE SPEECH: ASSESSING THE IMPLICATIONS OF BHARATHIYA NYAYA SANHITA ON FREEDOM OF SPEECH AND EXPRESSION

Ravithej S P, Assistant Professor, PG dept. of studies and research in Journalism and Mass Communication, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Mysore. ravithejsp@stphilos.ac.in

Sanju T S, Assistant Professor, PG dept. of studies and research in Journalism and Mass Communication, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Mysore.

This study critically examines the implications of the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS) on freedom of speech and expression in the post IPC era, focusing on Sections 196, 152, 299, 356, and 295A. While the new criminal code BNS was introduced to replace the colonial era law Indian Penal Code (IPC) with a more reformed legal framework, this research questions whether it is truly reformative or a more stringent version of the IPC's draconian laws. The study argues that these sections retain vague and overbroad language, making them susceptible to misuse, particularly against journalists, activists, and dissenters. A key focus is on Section 152, which replaces the controversial sedition law (Section 124A of IPC) with modifications that still allow its misuse. The research highlights that even though certain words were removed from IPC but entirety of meaning of those sections remains unchanged in the BNS. Additionally, the inclusion of electronic communication within the scope of these laws raises concerns about digital censorship and surveillance, questioning its justifiability under article 19(2) of Constitution. The study employs a theoretical framework that includes the Chilling Effect Theory, explaining how the ambiguity in these sections discourages critical speech and journalistic freedom. It also explores how Authoritarian Media Theory is more applicable in this legal environment than Social Responsibility Theory, suggesting an increasing state control over media discourse. Through case study analysis, the research examines incidents where journalists have been prosecuted under BNS, including *Zakir Ali Tyagi v. State of UP* and *Mohammed Zubair v. State of UP*, illustrating how legal conflicts from the IPC era persist under BNS. The study also conducted a thematic analysis of IPC-era judgments and a legal examination of BNS provisions to assess continuity and change. Additionally, secondary sources such as reports from Article 14, Law Commission of India, Reporters Without Borders, and Index on Censorship are evaluated to provide a comprehensive legal and journalistic perspective. The findings suggest that despite claims of decolonization and reform, the BNS provisions which are mentioned above continue to pose significant challenges to democratic discourse, media freedom, and civil liberties in India.

Keywords: *Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, Post IPC era, Freedom of Speech and Expression, Sedition Law in India, Chilling Effect.*

INVESTIGATING CONSUMER TRUST AND PURCHASE INTENTIONS IN INFLUENCER MARKETING OF HEALTH PRODUCTS ON INSTAGRAM

Rishika V. Bujurke – Student Department of Media Studies Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore. e-mail: rishika.bujurke24@gmail.com

Vikash Chauhan, Assistant Professor, CHRIST (Deemed to be University) Bangalore Central Campus

The study examines how influencer marketing on Instagram impacts consumer trust and purchase intentions in the context of health-related products. By analyzing consumer attitudes

and behaviors, this research identifies the key factors that drive purchase decisions in digital marketing environments. A quantitative research methodology was employed, utilizing a structured Likert scale survey. The survey targeted Instagram users who follow health-focused Instagram pages promoting and selling health-related products. Data was collected through random sampling of followers of selected Instagram accounts, offering insights into their perceptions of influencer credibility, transparency, and trustworthiness in influencing purchase decisions. The results indicate that influencer credibility and transparency significantly impact consumer trust in health-related products. Followers perceive influencers as knowledgeable about health products, but skepticism persists regarding their authenticity and financial motives. Trust in an influencer correlates strongly with purchase intention; however, a segment of followers remains cautious due to concerns about undisclosed sponsorships and biased endorsements. The study also highlights that personal narratives and transparent influencer communication enhance consumer trust and drive purchase behavior. This study contributes to the existing literature by focusing specifically on the health product niche within influencer marketing, an area with limited prior research. It also provides a distinctive perspective by analyzing consumer responses to verified Instagram influencers, shedding light on their role in shaping consumer behavior. The findings offer valuable insights for brands, marketers, and policymakers aiming to enhance credibility, trust, and ethical marketing practices in the health influencer industry.

Keywords: *Influencer marketing, consumer behaviour, influencer, social media*

PROLIFERATION OF CRIME-NARRATIVES IN INDIAN PODCAST: A QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF TWO NATIONAL AND TWO REGIONAL PODCAST CHANNELS NARRATING TRUE CRIME STORIES

Reetuparna Bhattacharjee, Research Scholar, Mahindra University, Hyderabad.
e-mail: sc24pmac003@mahindrauniversity.edu.in

Podcast listening in India increased during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, indicating a major media consumption trend impacted by lifestyle, technology, and media habits. The pandemic has boosted podcast listening by 23%, demonstrating the rising acceptance and integration of audio content into daily life. With limited movement and entertainment alternatives, people turned to podcasts for fun and information. Screen weariness from work and entertainment on digital gadgets made audio podcasts a pleasant alternative. Audio's immersive quality lets listeners engage while multitasking (cooking, exercising, commuting), making it appealing during lockdowns. The era when the 24 hours news-channels emerged with a new concept of dramatizing crime then that content became the hotcakes we can say that the narrations of the true-crime stories can be treated as the next generation of that format. American Crime-podcast Crime Junkie was actively involved in ongoing crime case though homicide episodes included white women as victims, male suspects and offenders, and firearms as the main means of homicide in unsolved cases. Crime Junkie homicide episodes included white women as victims, male suspects and offenders, and firearms as the main means of homicide in unsolved cases, Hickmon, N. (2024). The impact of true crime podcasts on unsolved homicide

cases: The evolution of true crime media. This work examines the character of Hindi and Bengali podcasts that narrate the Crimes which had already occurred. I analysed 'Khooni', and 'Crime Kahaniyan' in Hindi as well as 'The Crime Paradox' by RJ Ayantika, and Sujoyneel. The four podcasts focus on true crime narratives, showcasing real criminal cases and their psychological elements, as well as their impacts on individuals and society. They utilize narrative-driven formats to engage listeners, often dramatizing stories to immerse them in the discussed events. These podcasts address broader themes of justice, morality, and the societal repercussions of crime, encouraging critical thought about the circumstances surrounding these events. Additionally, they investigate the human aspects of crime by examining motivations and psychological profiles, fostering empathy and understanding for both victims and perpetrators. This work will set a dialectical discourse on the impact of these narratives on the listeners, also it will analyze the level of authenticity accepted by the listeners. Apart from some common rarest of the rare cases or high-profiled murder cases some regional variations are also making them unique in nature, so that detailed analysis will also be there in this study.

Keywords: *Podcast, Crime, Storytelling, True-narratives, crime aficionado*

PORTRAYAL OF SEX WORKERS IN SOUTH INDIAN CINEMA

Roshni Rajagopal, Student, Department of Media and Communication Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore. e-mail: roshni.rajagopal@res.christuniversity.in

The portrayal of sex workers in South Indian cinema offers a lens through which to examine societal attitudes, cultural narratives, and gender dynamics in a region known for its vibrant film industries. This paper explores how South Indian films depict sex workers, focusing on recurring themes, character archetypes, and the interplay between stigmatisation and sympathy. These factors tend to have an influence on the public perception of the sex industry and those who are associated with it. Additionally, South Indian cinema often oscillates between melodramatic tropes and attempts at nuanced storytelling, having narratives like that of 'a fallen woman' and heavily glamorising the sex industry, especially in popular commercial films. Movies such as *Haraa* (in 2024) and *Vidiyum Munn* (in 2013) (films that are part of this study, among others) are examples of films that explore the role of gender, class, or morality in shaping the depictions of sex work, and consider whether the films reinforce or critique the marginalisation of sex workers. The objective of this study is to explore whether the films reinforce or critique the marginalisation of sex workers, whether they concretise specific stereotypes or give the audience a new perspective on the understanding of sex work. The study includes an analysis through the lens of Phipp's Inclusive Feminist framework (2014), looking at the intersection of classism, sexism and racism in the portrayal of sex workers in South Indian Cinema. The significance and aim of the study is to reflect on how these portrayals mirror South India's cultural complexities or influence real-world attitudes toward sex work. There is a need for further research or more authentic representations, tying back to the evolving landscape of South Indian cinema and its potential to reshape narratives around these often-misunderstood communities.

Keywords: *Sex workers, cinema, representation, feminism*

COMMUNICATION IN FINANCIAL LITERACY AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Rudrappa K.M, Associate Professor. GFGC, Davangere, e-mail: rudrappakm65@gmail.com.

Veerabhadrappe B. P, Former Vice-Chancellor. Kuvempu University Shivamogga, Karnataka

Financial literacy is a crucial skill for individual well-being and economic stability, encompassing budgeting, saving, investing, and debt management. As the global economy becomes more complex, the need for confident financial navigation is increasing. Financial literacy directly influences economic development, as a financially literate population is better equipped to make informed decisions, enhance financial stability, and contribute to local and national growth. This includes saving, investing prudently, and mitigating unnecessary debt, which not only bolsters personal financial health but also the resilience of communities. Additionally, financial literacy fosters a culture of entrepreneurship, driving economic innovation and job creation. As individuals become more adept at managing their finances, they are empowered to take calculated risks and invest in business ventures, leading to a dynamic and thriving economic environment.

Key Words: *Economic Development, Financial Stability, Financial Literacy, Stability, Knowledg.*

ANALYZING THE INFLUENCE OF INSTAGRAM ON FOOD CULTURE AND DIETARY HABITS AMONG YOUNG STUDENTS IN HIGHER ACADEMICS IN WEST BENGAL.

Ruma Saha, Assistant Professor, Department of Media Science and Journalism, Brainware University, Kolkata, India. e-mail: ruma.saha.kolkata@gmail.com

Debabani Mukherjee, Assistant Professor, Department of Media Science and Journalism, Brainware University, Kolkata, India.

Smita Singh, Doctoral Research Scholar, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, Manipal University Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Instagram exerts a profound influence on the culinary culture and dietary practices of university students in West Bengal via various mechanisms. The platform cultivates a dynamic food enthusiast culture, wherein users disseminate visually enticing food content, thereby affecting the food preferences and selections of the student populace. The phenomenon of influencer marketing further magnifies this impact, as prominent Instagram figures endorse particular food trends, thereby enhancing their allure to their followers. The research objective is to study the impact of food-related posts on Instagram on young students of Universities in West Bengal. The age group selected for the study is from 18 years to 24 years. The methodology applied is quantitative where the survey is done on young students from Indian Universities in West Bengal. Furthermore, the result will give insight into the distinct food preferences of this demographic, which further elucidates how social media influences their eating habits. Thus, researchers inferred that the interplay of visual representation and influencer promotion on Instagram profoundly molds the culinary landscape for college students mirroring broader patterns of social media& effect on dietary decisions.

Keywords: *Social media interaction, food porn, Instagram, influencer effect, university students, West Bengal*

BANGALORE PSYCHOEDUCATION: COMPARING INDIVIDUAL AND GROUP APPROACHES ACROSS MENTAL HEALTH AND ACADEMIC SETTINGS

Rupsa Roy, Student of Media and Communication Studies Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore. e-mail: rupsaroypg@gmail.com

This study examines the role of psychoeducation in Bangalore's mental health and academic contexts, focusing on the comparative effectiveness of individual and group approaches. While psychoeducation has historically evolved from family therapy into a distinct therapeutic model, its integration within educational and clinical settings remains underexplored. This research investigates how psychoeducation complements pharmacological treatments and enhances mental health literacy. Employing a qualitative methodology, the study combines a comprehensive literature review with in-depth interviews involving mental health professionals, educators, and other stakeholders. Through a multi-stakeholder perspective, it analyzes the distinct characteristics, benefits, and challenges of both individual and group psychoeducation, emphasizing their impact on knowledge acquisition, symptom management, and social support. The findings highlight that psychoeducation has transitioned into a structured intervention for illness management, where effectiveness is linked to skilled communication, personalized content delivery, and interactive engagement. Furthermore, this study explores the role of digital media and technological tools in psychoeducation, assessing their potential to improve accessibility and engagement. By bridging communication and psychology, this research positions psychoeducation as a multidimensional intervention that empowers individuals, caregivers, and educators. It underscores the importance of tailored psychoeducational strategies in fostering mental health literacy, reducing stigma, and promoting well-being in both academic and broader societal contexts.

Keywords: *Psychoeducation, Mental Health Literacy, Communication, Academic Health, Media and Psychology*

A STUDY ON ONLINE PRIVACY AWARENESS AMONG ADOLESCENTS

S. Ajantha Thamayanthi Baylis, Assistant Professor (T), Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu. e-mail: ajanthasanjit@gmail.com

G Balasubramania Raja, Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu. . e-mail:gbs_raja@yahoo.com

The increasing use of the internet for everyday tasks necessitates a strong understanding of online safety, particularly among adolescents. Students are aware of the risks to their personal information online, but often lack the skills to critically analyse and manage online privacy issues. This study investigates internet safety awareness among adolescents and the impact of online media privacy literacy training on their ability to protect their online privacy. A survey using random sampling was conducted among adolescents to assess their internet safety awareness. Based on the survey data, an experimental study was conducted with a control and treatment group of 100 students (50 boys and 50 girls). The treatment group received five days of

training (45 minutes per day) using a multimedia module covering computer crime, computer security measures, and privacy laws. A pre-test and a post-test were conducted among control and experimental groups to find out the effectiveness of the online media privacy literacy training. This study is also informed by Communication Privacy Management Theory, which helps explain how adolescents negotiate privacy boundaries in online environments. The study's findings suggest that privacy literacy training is needed to raise adolescents' awareness of internet safety. It also reveals that the new media literacy training improves the knowledge and skills to analyze online privacy issues. The study will be helpful for the students to use information and communication technology in a positive way for their betterment.

Keywords: *Online Safety, Privacy Literacy, Communication Privacy Management Theory, Online Environment, Communication Technology*

UNDERSTANDING THE NUANCES OF INFORMATION OVERLOAD WITH RESPECT TO PERSONAL HEALTH AND SOCIAL WELL-BEING

S. Augustin Jesuvadian, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu-627012. e-mail: augustinaj05@gmail.com

Gnana D Hans,

We live in an era of information where information can be accessed through various types of media. The abundance of information leads to challenges in processing and understanding voluminous information, especially among the young adults attending colleges. They use digital media for various purposes such as academics, entertainment, acquiring skills, knowledge acquisition, etc. The phenomenon of Information Overload occurs when individuals are inundated with such a vast amount of data that they struggle to process, interpret, and make sense of it all. This can lead to feelings of stress, confusion, and anxiety, as the brain finds it challenging to filter essential information from the noise. Information overload is particularly prevalent in modern life, where we are constantly bombarded with updates from social media, news outlets, emails, and other digital platforms. This relentless influx of information not only makes it difficult to focus but can also impact significantly the physical, social and psychological well-being. As we navigate this complex scenario of media and messages, it becomes increasingly vital to develop effective strategies for managing information consumption, prioritizing what is most relevant, and maintaining a healthy balance to safeguard our mental health and social connections. In this study, we employ qualitative methods and in-depth interviews to collect data from college students, and also we are going to understand how college student's psychological and social well-being is affected by information overload. And also we are going to explore what are the strategies that students use to reduce information overload and cognitive load.

Keywords: *Information Overload, Social Media, Well-being, Detoxification*

CULTURAL FLAUNT: A STUDY ON THE CULTURAL EXPRESSIONS THROUGH NEW MEDIA AMONG TIRUNELVELI'S YOUTH

S.G.Veeralakshmanan, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India e-mail: sgveera96@gmail.com

G. Balasubramania Raja, Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India

In the contemporary digital era, caste identities have discovered new and dynamic platforms for expression, particularly among the younger generation. This study delves into the phenomenon of 'Caste Flaunt' among youth in Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, exploring how they assert and showcase their social and caste affiliations through various digital mediums. By analysing content shared on social media, online discussions, and digital interactions, this research aims to understand the motivations behind such expressions, the modes they manifest, and their broader social impact. Employing a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methodologies with the theoretical framework of Manuel Castells, Network Society Theory, this study seeks to identify distinct patterns of identity assertion and community engagement within the digital space. It also examines how young individuals navigate traditional cultural frameworks while adapting to modern digital environments, striking a balance between heritage and contemporary online expression. Furthermore, the research contributes to ongoing discussions on caste and religious dynamics, the representation of social identities in the virtual world, and the role of digital ethnography in understanding cultural evolution. By shedding light on these aspects, the study enhances our comprehension of how digital platforms influence identity politics, shape inter-community interactions, and redefine the nature of cultural expression in the digital age

Keywords: *Caste Flaunt, Religious Flaunt, Digital Culture, social media, sanja Cultural Expression, digital flaunt, digital expression*

GENDER DYNAMICS IN K BALACHANDER'S TELUGU CINEMA- AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

S.Sujatha, Research scholar, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, Osmania University, Hyderabad. email: sujathaphdfilmstudies@gmail.com

Telugu Cinema has been a significant part in the Indian Cinema industry which was known from the hundred years plus Indian cinema. From the silent era to talkie movies, Telugu cinema has equally played an important role in south Indian cinema. My topic explores the portrayal of women in the popular writer cum director Phalke awardee Iyakkunar Sigaram (Director Everest) K Balachander's women in his Telugu films. Earlier days of Telugu cinema, women were depicted as the ideal wife or mother in an as submissive, homely and virtuous women, and their main aim is to support their husbands and family. They are more in singing and dancing roles with the leading star, who used to be second fiddle to him. By the 1960s and 1970s, the portrayal of women is more progressive and independent challenged the traditional patriarchal values prevalent in society. After the star system had arisen in the film industry, the heroine is mere a dancing doll in the film or eve teasing. There were hardly any women-centric Films were introduced by the filmmakers with bold story. K Balachander taken the cudgels of the women

issues and felt it is his responsibility, and supported them and made them act in his films, he could produce neo-realism characters with innovative ideas and social issue-based films. The human relations were his core subject of filmmaking. Though he had encountered with community people and other scholars on his 'Arengetram' film. undeterred KB sir, could weave a story on the issue-based cinema. His songs, lyrics, locations, performers skill, innovative ideas, are his forte. In almost in all his films he produced, Kalaimani KB has ended the story on a distinctive pessimistic line rather than optimistic. You will find despair, agony, negativity and dishearten showing the life come to its starting point, being women centric characters in the films. Liberal feminist theoretical framework will be instrumental which focuses on gender inequalities, not the just specifically the position of women in society through his films like Anthuleni Katha, Idi katha kaadu, Marocharitra, Rudraveena, Guppedu Manasu, Akali rajyam, etc. He explored various gender dynamics themes and concepts on greatest women centric films, who has left legacy behind sensibility of middle-class sensibility, relationships. He is clear about what he wants to do through his casting as per story board.

Key words: *women-centric, issue based, human relations, gender dynamics, middle-class sensibility.*

THE GIG ECONOMY, DIGITAL COMMUNICATION AND ECONOMIC CHALLENGES IN INDIA: EXAMINING QUICK COMMERCE.

Samridhhi Srivastava, Student, BA in Communication and Psychology, Department of Media Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University) Bangalore Yeshwanthpur Campus, Bangalore

Tanya Shukla, Student, BA in Communication and Psychology, Department of Media Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore Yeshwanthpur Campus, Bangalore

Divya Kumari K, Assistant Professor, Department of Media Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), Bangalore Yeshwanthpur Campus, Bangalore, email: divyakumari.kp@christuniversity.in

The gig economy in India has grown rapidly with the rise of Quick commerce platforms, creating opportunities for gig workers such as auto drivers and small restaurant owners. However, this sector faces significant challenges, including a pay gap and an uncertain financial future. This study aims to understand the pay gap, the business models of gig-based platforms, and the current situation of gig economy workers. Using in-depth interviews with gig workers, the research will explore the reasons behind the pay gap, how it affects workers' earnings, and the broader impact of this pay gap on the Indian economy, particularly in a developing country like India, where gig work is expanding rapidly. The study also aims to assess the digital communication of these quick commerce platforms in the form of customer reviews and ratings, algorithm job allocations, and how these factors shape and affect the financial stability of gig workers. Additionally, the research will assess the long-term implications of an unregulated gig economy. With today's generation, becoming more inclined towards gigs if the ongoing trends still persist, India may face widening income disparities, and reduced worker welfare. Analysing these issues helps to highlight the urgent need for fair wages, financial security, and policy interventions to support gig workers in India's evolving digital economy.

Keywords: *Quick commerce, gig workers, gig economy, Indian economy and digital communication*

VISUAL CONTENT ANALYSIS OF ADVERTISING MESSAGES OF INDIAN FMCG BRANDS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO EMAMI, PATANJALI, AND DABUR

Sakshi Agarwal, Postgraduate Student, (M.A. Media and Communication Studies) CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru , . e-mail:sakshi.agarwal@mames.christuniversity.in

Shantharaju S, Associate Professor, Department of Media Studies CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru

In the dynamic consumer goods market of India, FMCG brands like Emami, Patanjali, and Dabur have established themselves as significant players, each employing distinctive visual and advertising strategies to influence consumer behavior and preferences. These brands not only fulfill tangible needs but also tap into psychological, cultural, and aspirational dimensions, positioning themselves as integral components of a holistic lifestyle. With the rise of India's middle class and an increasing focus on natural and Ayurvedic products, it is essential to analyze how these brands communicate their values through visual content in advertising. This study investigates the visual content and advertising strategies of three prominent Indian FMCG brands, i.e. Emami, Patanjali, and Dabur. These brands, rooted in India's cultural and ayurvedic traditions, have become central to the Indian audience, where they distinguish themselves through unique brand identities and messaging. Through a detailed content analysis, this research explores how each brand employs visual and thematic elements to communicate its value propositions, including but not limited to traditional values and modern aspirations. The study examines specific advertising components such as color schemes, symbolic imagery, cultural references, and character representation to understand how these brands position themselves to appeal to the Indian consumer base. By comparing the visual strategies of Emami, Patanjali, and Dabur, the research highlights how each brand balances tradition and modernity to cultivate cultural resonance, consumer trust, and brand loyalty. The findings contribute to an understanding of the strategic role of visual content in Indian FMCG advertising, providing insights into consumer engagement and the evolving landscape of the industry.

Keywords: *Ayurvedic branding, FMCG advertising, Visual analysis, Indian market*

REAL-TIME CHALLENGES IN THE APPROPRIATION AND ACTUALISATION OF INFORMATION IN DIGITAL MEDIA APPLICATIONS

Sanjai R, Post Graduate Student, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu. e-mail: sanjay31sanjay@gmail.com

Veeralakshmanan G, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu.

Tamizhanban R M, Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu.

G Balasubramanian Raja, Professor and Head, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu.

Gnana D Hans, Assistant Professor, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu.

The inevitability of information is evident with the present-day digital media applications and appliances used by human beings at all levels. The challenge is the appropriateness of the information and its effectiveness. Moreover, in actual working conditions of these digital media applications, the efficacy of the processes is often hindered by the irrelevance and

inappropriateness of information. Majority of the digital media audiences are overwhelmed by the processes and services offered through the present-day digital media applications. Also, it should be noted that the affiliated unskilled industries and services mushroom around these digital media applications. The financial incentives that it generates to these unskilled workers and the economy associated with it is called the Gig Economy. Many social anthropologists have recognised the contribution of information converted to services through information and communication technology. Earlier it was believed that technological innovation could contribute to social innovation and change, which is noted in technological determinism. But in reality, due to the inappropriateness of information, real-time challenges pose a significant threat to sustainability in the life and livelihood of individuals depending on services based on the Gig Economy. This paper seeks to explore the real time challenges faced by Gig workers using digital media applications. The study will employ qualitative methodology in conducting in-depth interviews with people facing these challenges. The paper furthermore seeks to understand the nuances of these challenges about the gap created by inappropriate information, which questions the efficacy and effectiveness of the communication process in digital media.

Keywords: *Gig Economy, Digital Media Applications, Gig Workers, Technological Determinism, Information and Communication Technology*

FROM TRADITION TO DIGITAL: TRANSMITTING JOGATTI FOLK NARRATIVES THROUGH DIGITAL STORYTELLING IN THE 21ST CENTURY

Sanjana Suukyi M P, PhD Scholar, IIT Dharwad. e-mail:hs24dp001@iitdh.ac.in

Ridhima Tewari, Associate Professor, IIT Dharwad. e-mail:ridhima@iitdh.ac.in

This paper utilizes findings of the ICSSR-IMPRESS project titled “Women in the Intellectual and Historical Traditions of North Karnataka: A Digital Archive” undertaken at the Indian Institute of Technology Dharwad, to showcase how artists are employing digital storytelling for transmitting folk narratives from North Karnataka. Specifically, the paper focuses on how the much-neglected legacy of Jogatti (a transgender community) folk art has been revived using visual narratives and digital platforms under the Urban Folk Project founded by the artist Shilpa Mudbi. Utilizing semi-structured interviews with the artist and visual documents (derived from the Urban Folk Project's YouTube and Instagram platforms), the paper aims to elucidate how folk narratives of the Kannada language are increasingly finding a rich (and unlikely) breeding ground in the digital space while being contemporized for a largely Urban audience. The use of bilingual narration techniques and free platforms that promote accessibility to semi-urban and urban audiences in digital space forms the core philosophy of Mudbi's project. Mudbi, who started her career as a documentary filmmaker, shares with the researchers how she decided to become the 'medium' and singer herself to restore- through digital storytelling and visual narrative- the Jogatti performing arts of North Karnataka. Mudbi's 'Yellamma Aata' (Songs of Yellamma, a deity) is based on myths associated with the transgender community of Jogattis. The Jogatti perform the myth during the auspicious days of Yellamma Jathre (Yellamma festival). In the process of examining the use of digital storytelling and narrativization, the paper will also briefly focus on (a) the criticality of transmitting these stories in this day and age, (b) the use of these narratives to represent, reclaim, reinterpret mythological practices today vis-à-vis the Jogattis and, (c) issues pertaining to authorship/ownership and translation.

Keywords: *Shilpa Mudbi, Digital Storytelling, Jogatti Folk Art, Transgender Narratives*

THE ALGORITHMIC LENS: HOW AI-DRIVEN SOCIAL MEDIA SHAPES YOUTH PERCEPTIONS THROUGH ECHO CHAMBERS, FILTER BUBBLES, AND DOOM SCROLLING

Sanju TS, Assistant Professor, St. Philomena's College PG Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, Mysuru, Karnataka, India, email: sanjuts1997@gmail.com

Ravithej SP, Assistant Professor, St. Philomena's College PG Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, Mysuru, Karnataka, India

This exploratory study examines how social media, driven by AI algorithms, homogenizes youth perceptions by fostering echo chambers, filter bubbles, and promoting doom scrolling. Designed to maximize engagement, these algorithms curate content based on user preferences, amplifying dominant narratives while marginalizing dissenting voices creating an illusion of consensus. The study focuses on two key cases: the Trump campaign's strategic use of social media to mobilize supporters and the Kumbha Mela, where online narratives emphasized positive portrayals while downplaying incidents like human stampedes. These cases highlight a broader pattern of algorithmic curation shaping public discourse. Grounded in Marshall McLuhan's Medium is the Message and Noelle-Neumann's Spiral of Silence theory, the research also applies Uses and Gratifications Theory to explore how youth actively engage with personalized content streams. While algorithms often reinforce majority opinions, doom scrolling the compulsive consumption of negative news and polarizing content further deepens information silos, reinforcing existing biases and anxiety. Using a mixed-methods approach combining content analysis, youth surveys, and digital ethnography the study investigates how AI-driven content distribution influences youth preferences, perceptions, and choices. Ultimately, it assesses the broader impact of these algorithms on democratic participation and cultural narratives, tracing shifts in digital interactions before and after AI integration.

Keywords: *Social media algorithms, AI curation, youth perceptions, echo chambers, filter bubbles, doom scrolling.*

UPHOLDING CULTURE, EMPOWERING THE COMMUNITY: EXPLORING 'AGROFORESTRY' AS A DEVELOPMENT MODEL FORDONGRIA KONDH IN NIYAMGIRI, ODISHA

Sanskar Behera, MA Development Communication, AJK MCRC, Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, email: behera.sanskar2019@gmail.com

The Dongria Kondh, an indigenous Adivasi Community in Odisha, are known for their deep spiritual and ecological connection to the Niyamgiri Hills, relying on Forest Based livelihoods and Shifting Cultivation. While large scale mining projects threaten their land, alternative economic methods that align with their cultural values remain under-explored. The study investigates 'Agroforestry' as a Sustainable Development Model that ensures economic stability, ecological preservation, and community autonomy. The research identifies gaps in existing literature regarding tribal-led agroforestry governance, policy integration, and financial sustainability. Using semi-structured methods for surveys and interviews with associated members and policy analysis, the study will examine the latitude of successful agroforestry models in India, alongside government initiatives like Van Dhan Yojana, Odisha's Millet Mission and others. By engaging with the community, directly or indirectly, it will explore the feasibility of community-owned agroforestry cooperatives, sustainable value chains, and

alternative funding mechanisms like CSR initiatives and impact investments. The findings will delve deeper into a participatory and scalable agroforestry framework, ensuring 'Development without Displacement' and inquire the potential factors of economic self-sufficiency for Dongria Kondh, while preserving their land and culture.

Keywords: *Dongria Kondh, Niyamgiri Hills, Odisha, Agroforestry, Tribal Economy, Sustainable Development, Indigenous Rights, Tribal Displacement, Biodiversity Conservation, Community Empowerment*

POLITICAL POLARISATION IN YOUTUBE: A CRITICAL APPROACH TO DISCURSIVE STRATEGIES IN ONLINE YOUTUBE COMMENTS ON UAPA VIDEOS

Sarang K, PhD Scholar, Department of Electronic Media and Mass Communication, Pondicherry University

YouTube is a popular source of information in India; according to the top YouTube Impact in India report, more than 1 in 3 users have searched for news, and more than 93 per cent are using it to gather information and knowledge. The Unlawful Activities Prevention Act (UAPA) has been facing significant criticism for allegedly suppressing minorities and restricting freedom of speech in India. The study examines the discourses on UAPA using critical discourse analysis to explore the political polarization in YouTube comments both textually and contextually. The study also aims to find The strategies and sub-strategies used in the discourses and how they added to the political polarisation on the issue using the concept of “socio-cognitive strategies” by Van Dijk. The research employs a mixed-method approach to analyze the YouTube comments on Youtube. A total of 20461 comments from 470 videos within the time frame of 18-02-2020 to 13-12-2024 were scraped from YouTube using the video network module feature of YouTube Data tools API, which helps to find a link between videos based on the concept of co-commenting irrespective of the channels. Information such as the title, channel and Video ID, publisher, published dates, counts of views, likes, and comments are extracted using the keyword UAPA. The refined corpus of data is then analyzed using Maxqda to find frequently occurring words and word combinations and how they vary during different time frames. The selected comment sections of the videos are analyzed using CDA to examine the discursive strategies used by different opinion groups on the issue.

Keywords: Critical discourse analysis, UAPA, Media narratives, Framing, alternative media

DOPAMINE LOOPS AND PLAYER RETENTION: A STUDY ON REINFORCEMENT IN FREE-TO-PLAY GAMES

Sarvajith Kumar J N, Assistant Professor, Department of Management, Cresta First Grade College, Mysuru, Karnataka – 570028. e-mail: sarvajithjn@gmail.com

Manohar N, Assistant Professor, Department of Journalism, Government First Grade College for Women, M G Road, Hassan, Karnataka – 573202.

Free-to-play (F2P) games are ruling the gaming world and use dopamine driven reinforcement mechanisms to increase the player retention and monetization. This paper aims at exploring how random reward systems, time locked progression, artificial product scarcity,

social reinforcement and frustration as a form of monetization affect player engagement. This research is based on the qualitative content analysis of the popular F2P games including Genshin Impact, Fortnite, Clash of Clans and Candy Crush Saga. The study establishes that the game design elements trigger the dopamine release and thus encourage the habitual play and spending money in micro transactions. The results show that even though these mechanisms are quite effective in increasing the engagement, they pose a number of ethical questions with regard to gamification and exploitative monetization. This paper further suggests that game designers should develop morally right monetization models that would help in achieving the right balance between the profitability of the industry and the well-being of the players. The immediate future work should be directed at understanding the long-term consequences of dopamine loops, the impact of regulatory measures on F2P monetization, and the differences in gaming behaviour.

Keywords: *Dopamine Loops, Free-to-Play (F2P), Monetization, Player Retention Reinforcement Mechanisms, Exploitative Gamification*

THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC COMMUNICATION IN ADVANCING THE BIOECONOMY: A SOCIOECONOMIC PERSPECTIVE

Satya Prasad ,Professor & Head of Institution ,Nitte Institute of Communication, NITTE Deemed to be University.

Archan Mitra, Assistant Professor, Nitte Institute of Communication, NITTE Deemed to be University.
email: archan.mitra@nitte.edu.in

The bioeconomy, which integrates biological resources with economic and industrial development, is emerging as a key driver of sustainable growth. However, its successful implementation depends not only on scientific and technological advancements but also on effective communication strategies that shape public perception, stakeholder engagement, and policy formation. This study explores the role of strategic communication in advancing the bioeconomy, examining how different communication channels—media, governmental messaging, and corporate sustainability reports—affect awareness, acceptance, and decision-making processes. Using a mixed-method approach, including discourse analysis of policy documents and interviews with key stakeholders, the study assesses the influence of communication on public trust, misinformation mitigation, and the framing of bioeconomic policies. The findings highlight that clear, transparent, and science-based communication is crucial for fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, increasing public confidence in bio-based innovations, and promoting policy coherence. This study contributes to the growing discourse on the intersection of communication, sustainability, and economic transformation, emphasizing the need for strategic information dissemination in shaping the future of the bioeconomy.

Keywords: *Bioeconomy, Strategic Communication, Public Perception, Policy Framing, Sustainable Development*

SOCIAL MEDIA AS A CATALYST FOR GRASSROOTS ACTIVISM IN E-WASTE MANAGEMENT: EXPLORING COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES

Sharada T, Assistant Professor, NMKRV College for Women, Jayanagar, Bengaluru.

e-mail: Sharada.nmkrv@rvei.edu.in

This research examines the place of social media as a catalyst of grassroots activism for e-waste management. In the fast-paced digital space and the increasingly growing global e-waste burden, it is important to research how the use of communication strategies on the internet can mobilize people toward adopting sustainable environmental behaviour. By employing mixed-method approach the research aims to investigate and critically evaluate how social media promotes awareness, engagement, and policy advocacy among grassroots activists working to address e-waste issues. Through this, the research seeks to determine the most effective communication strategies that increase public awareness and influence concrete environmental actions and policy suggestions. The research is focused on the convergence of digital communication and community-led environmental change. By analysing both quantitative measures and qualitative experiences, this study adds to the rich understanding of digital environmental activism. It further offers actionable suggestions for utilizing social media as a useful instrument for grassroots mobilization and policy change in the context of e-waste management.

Keywords: *Social Media, Grassroots Activism, E-waste Management,*

EXPLORING MISINFORMATION AND DISINFORMATION IN THE 2024 LOK SABHA ELECTIONS: A QUALITATIVE STUDY SURROUNDING BJP AND INC

Sheril A, Student, Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru. e-mail:

sheril.a@mames.christuniversity.in

Meljo Thomas, Assistant Professor, Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru.

With the rapid evolution of the digital landscape, the dissemination of political misinformation has significantly increased, posing a threat to democracies worldwide. Several studies highlight India as a fake-news-prone country with growing social divides and communal disharmony. The Global Risk Report of 2024 also predicts India as high risk for political misinformation and disinformation. While much attention has been given to misinformation studies in the West, it is crucial that Asian countries like India receive equal academic focus. This study focuses on misinformation in the context of the 18th Lok Sabha general elections of 2024, providing insights into India's political landscape, trends, partisan politics, dominant narratives, and the evolving role of social media platforms. The study follows a qualitative analysis of 155 fake news items published by fact-checking websites Boom Live and News Checker during the election period (16th March – 4th June 2024). It identifies dominant themes of misinformation and disinformation narratives surrounding the BJP and Indian National Congress (INC) on social media platforms, as well as the predominant types of misinformation. The findings revealed 20 unique themes, including 'public support', 'hate speech', 'violence', 'party endorsements', 'corruption', 'vote fraud'. The predominant type of misinformation was cheap

fakes (95.5%), followed by deepfakes (4.5%). This study offers valuable insights into misinformation trends during the 2024 elections, which can aid future academic research and assist policymakers in combating fake news through media literacy initiatives. Future research should expand data sources to include multiple fact-checking platforms, social media channels, and regional sources for a more diverse and representative dataset.

Keywords: *Political communication, Misinformation, BJP, Congress, Election*

INDIA'S STANCE ON THE TIBETAN CRISIS: INSIGHTS FROM PARLIAMENTARY DEBATES

Shreeraj Gudi, Assistant Professor, Manipal Institute of Communication, MAHE Manipal.

e-mail: shreeraj.gudi@manipal.edu

Padma Rani, Professor and Director, Manipal Institute of Communication, MAHE Manipal

email: padma.rani@manipal.edu

Nanda Kishor, Professor and HoD, Department of Politics and International Relations, Pondicherry

University email: srijankishor@pondiuni.ac.in srijankishor@gmail.com

The Indian Parliament, as the nation's highest legislative body, has played a crucial role in shaping India's stance on Tibet. Through debates, resolutions, and policy discussions, it has highlighted the ethical, strategic, and humanitarian aspects of the issue while documenting the evolution of India-Tibet relations. Parliamentary debates have reflected diverse views on India's diplomatic approach to Tibet. While India officially recognizes Tibet as an autonomous region of China, discussions have ranged from condemning Chinese aggression to advocating a pragmatic realpolitik approach. These debates reveal the balance between India's moral principles and strategic interests. India's democratic ethos and historical ties to Tibet have made the preservation of Tibetan culture a recurring theme in parliamentary discourse. Members have voiced concerns over the suppression of Tibetan religion, language, and traditions under Chinese rule, emphasizing India's role in safeguarding Tibet's cultural and spiritual heritage. The Indian Parliament has also influenced policies regarding Tibet and Tibetan refugees, with Tibet's geopolitical and historical significance making it a long-standing subject of discussion. Particularly after the mid-20th century, when Tibet's sovereignty was challenged, the issue became central to India's legislative deliberations. The Lok Sabha Archives house over 4,000 documents on the Tibet issue, providing insights into India's nuanced engagement with this complex geopolitical and humanitarian subject. These records include parliamentary debates, policy discussions, and diplomatic correspondences, shedding light on India's evolving stance and its broader implications for regional stability and Sino-Indian relations. Categorized under themes like border security, the 1959 Tibetan uprising, refugee management, and Indo-Tibetan-Chinese relations, these documents enable in-depth analysis of India's policies. They highlight how the Parliament has shaped discourse on Tibet, balancing national security, humanitarian concerns, and diplomatic imperatives while underscoring India's commitment to sovereignty, non-alignment, and human rights.

Key words: *Indian Parliament, Tibet, Political Communication, Democracy, Foreign Policy*

A STUDY ON SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE PATTERNS AMONG RURAL FEMALE STUDENTS IN URBAN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Sharmila Christy. S, Research Scholar, Central University of Tamilnadu, Tiruvarur. E-mail: christyphd2020@gmail.com

Social media in this digital decade is deep-rooted in students & existence, impacting their communication, relationships and education. Issues related to cyberbullying, mental health, peer pressure and unrealistic expectations are diverting students' attention from studies, leading to lower academic performance and difficulty in concentrating on tasks are reportedly increasing day by day. Hence, this study explores the social media usage patterns of rural female students studying in urban educational institutions. It examines their intention of use, preferred platforms, time spent, and the impact of social media on their academic and personal lives. The study also examines the difficulties they encounter, including internet accessibility, cultural barriers, and digital literacy. Through quantitative convenient non probability sampling techniques 100 samples will be collected to study the above mentioned areas. The rural female students in urban educational institutions face unique challenges and experiences when adapting to digital platforms, the study aims to understand these questions. As this study offers insights into how these students adjust to social media in a new setting and how it influences their life experiences, it is important to study for inclusive digital growth.

Keywords: *Social media usage patterns, Rural female students, Urban educational institutions, Impact of social media*

CAN THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM BE USED AS A REITERATIVE METHOD TO PROMOTE LEARNERS' LEARNING ENGAGEMENT?

Shilaja C L, Assistant Professor, Department of English, Stella Maris College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu
e-mail: shilaja@stellamariscollege.edu.in

Jeyapriya U, Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science, Stella Maris College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu. e-mail: jeyapriya@stellamariscollege.edu.in

In recent years, the concept of the; flipped classroom; has garnered interest in the field of tertiary education. It offers a unique approach to teaching and learning with a potential to transform the conventional method of teaching. However, there is a dearth of research about the effectiveness of this instructional model. Therefore, to contribute to this line of research on the flipped classroom model of instruction, this study investigated the perspectives of the flipped classroom model and examined the impact on the learners. The research instruments for investigating students' perception of flipped classrooms were a) questionnaire b) analytics on the number of views of videos. Students were positive in their perception of flipped classrooms and agreed that in-class activities improved their understanding of concepts. It was also noted that students had the flexibility to watch the videos whenever they had doubts or wished to deepen their understanding, allowing them to learn at their own convenience. Moreover, the students showed a positive learning environment in the flipped classroom. In the Google Classroom, the materials in the form of activities and videos provided detailed instructions. The YouTube channel created for self- made video tutorials offered the students the chance to view the content at their own pace, enhancing their understanding of the concepts. The flipped classroom model

has shown promising results in tertiary education across various disciplines. By watching short lecture videos both self-made and MOOC and answering questions on in-video quizzes their self-efficacy improved and the instructor also found more time to engage the students actively in classroom activities. The population of this study consisted of 45 second-year students of the Literature programme in the Faculty of Arts, and 48 students of Computer Science in the Faculty of Science programme at Stella Maris College, Chennai. This study adds to the literature by providing evidence on how a flipped classroom can potentially benefit students' academic performance, leading to higher training satisfaction and deeper disciplinary understanding in challenging core courses.

Key words: *Flipped classroom, self-made videos, teaching-learning, conventional method of teaching, questionnaire*

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA CONTENT ON PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF POLITICAL NEWS

Shwetha P.B., Assistant Professor, NMKRV College, Bengaluru. e-mail: shwethavibhareddy@gmail.com

Social media has emerged as a powerful tool in shaping public perception, particularly in the realm of political news. This study aims to analyze the influence of social media content on political opinions by examining shifts in public sentiment, assessing the impact of user engagement, and identifying the types of content that drive opinion changes. A quantitative survey method will be employed to evaluate how different forms of political content, including news, opinion pieces, and misinformation, influence public perception. The research will involve a sample size of 50 participants, with data collected through an online survey. The findings will provide valuable insights into the role of social media in political discourse and contribute to a deeper understanding of the impact digital platforms have on shaping public opinion.

Keywords: *Social media influence, political opinion shifts, user engagement, digital platforms, public perception, misinformation*

LOCATION SPECIFIC CONTENT: A CRUCIAL TOOL FOR CLIMATE ACTION COMMUNICATION AT GRASSROOTS LEVEL

Sirasani Anilkumar, Ph.D. Scholar in Mass Communication, School of Media and Communication, Pondicherry University. e-mail: anilvarma771@pondiuni.ac.in

Climate change is a complex and multifaced challenge, but it is not felt equally everywhere across the globe. Different regions experience varying impacts of climate change depending on factors like the geography of a particular region and the socio-economic conditions of the people. In fact, this sad reality highlights the urgent need for coordinated climate action. Climate action is one of the major goals of 17 UN-SDGs, which affects directly or indirectly the rest of all sustainable development goals across the world. To tackle this situation, the transformation of global SDGs to the local level by using effective communication strategies to combat the effects of climate change is required, and this created the need for rethinking communication flow in the global age. For this, location-specific content emerges as a vital tool in the global effort to combat

climate change by offering tailored communication strategies that resonate with diverse regional contexts with localized solutions that address the specific challenges and needs of different communities. While traditional communication is often based on broad generalized narratives that fail to resonate with diverse audiences, this usage of location-specific content technique enhances the public understanding of climate change by strategically crafting the message to reflect regional vulnerabilities, fosters engagement by connecting people with environmental issues that affect them, and drives people to take an action against climate change by fostering strong sense of personal relevance. To bridge the gap between scientific data/communication and the localized tangible impacts/action of climate change, this paper explores the role of location-specific content in climate action communication by analyzing narratives and local stories and by examining case studies across the globe. Ultimately, this research underlines the importance of location-specific content and its key considerations in creating localized content to amplify global efforts in mitigating climate change and adopting its impacts.

Keywords: *SDGs, Global Age, Effective Communication, Climate Change, Local Level*

REPORTING CLIMATE CHANGE IN WEST BENGAL: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ANANDABAZAR PATRIKA AND BARTAMAN IN 2023

Sirsha Chakraborty, Department of Media and Communication Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), India. e-mail:sirsha.chakraborty@mamcs.christuniversity.in

This research investigates how two leading Bengali-language newspapers, Anandabazar Patrika and Bartaman, during 2023 frame and prioritise climate change coverage. The study addresses the critical role of regional media in shaping public awareness and engagement with climate issues, particularly in a state like West Bengal, which faces significant climate risks such as cyclones, flooding, and coastal erosion. This research addresses the gap in academic this course by analysing the framing, article focus, and placement of news. It explores how these newspapers communicate climate change to the readers and whether the narrative has a sense of urgency, responsibility or local relevance. The study employs a qualitative content approach, analysing articles that explicitly mention climate change or related environmental issues. Thematic coding is used to categorise articles based on framing, article focus, and news placement. findings reveal distinct differences in how the two newspapers frame climate change, with Anandabazar Patrika emphasising local impacts and solutions, while Bartaman adopts a more political narrative. News placement analysis indicates that Anand Bazaar Patrika gives higher importance to climate change by placing stories prominently, whereas Bartaman covers at least frequently on the front page. The study includes that these framing and placement strategies significantly influence public perception and engagement with climate issues in West Bengal. The study highlights the potential of regional media to bridge the gap between global climate discourse and local realities, empowering communities to engage with climate action. By shedding light on the framing strategies and editorial priorities of Bengali newspapers, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of climate communication in multilingual societies and underscores the importance of region-specific narratives and fostering public engagement with climate issues.

Keywords: *Climate change communication, regional media, media framing, bengali newspapers*

DIGITAL MEDIA IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN INDIA: A CRITICAL REVIEW

Somashekara C L, Working Professional, University of Mysore, Mysuru
e-mail: shekargowda.c.l.2012@gmail.com

The proliferation and adoption of digital media have significantly transformed public administration in India, enhancing governance, transparency, and citizen engagement. Social media platforms, government portals, and digital initiatives have enabled more inclusive policymaking, streamlined public service delivery, and improved responsiveness to citizens' concerns. The advancement of digital media has also played a vital role in bridging the gap between government institutions and marginalised communities in India, including Dalits, Adivasis, religious minorities, PWDs and other underrepresented groups, by amplifying their voices and facilitating direct interaction with policymakers. The integration of digital platforms in public administration has allowed for real-time communication, efficient grievance redressal, and greater public participation in governance. However, challenges such as the digital divide, limited internet penetration, cybersecurity threats, misinformation, data privacy concerns, and algorithmic biases continue to hinder its full potential. Additionally, issues of online surveillance and censorship raise questions about digital freedom and inclusivity in governance. Despite the growing relevance of digital media in public administration, there is a lack of academic research exclusively addressing its impact, challenges, and scope in the Indian context. This paper aims to systematically review existing literature on the role of digital media in public administration in India, exploring its implications for governance, service delivery, and citizen participation.

Keywords: *Public Administration, Digital Media, Marginalised, Social Media*

WICKED WOMEN AND MORAL DILEMMAS: CHARACTERIZATION OF ANTAGONIST FEMALE CHARACTERS IN MALAYALAM CINEMA

Soumya P, School of Digital Media and Communication, Mahindra University, Hyderabad- 500043.
e-mail: soumyaraj189@gmail.com

Alga Albin, School of Digital Media and Communication, Mahindra University, Hyderabad- 500043.
e-mail: algalbin14@gmail.com

In Malayalam cinema, female antagonists are increasingly portrayed as morally dubious individuals who commit crimes without feeling guilty. With an emphasis on how these characters subvert conventional ideas of guilt and atonement, this study analyses the way these women are portrayed in *Joji* (2021), *Rorschach* (2022), *Mukundanunni Associates* (2022), *Sookshmadarshini* (2024) and *Rekhachithram* (2025). Unlike the traditional female villains who either repent or pay for their crimes in a narrative sense, these women launch a frontal assault on gendered norms in criminal narratives that celebrate their agency in acting morally unconscientious. The disputes raging around them are the main themes examined in character study: justice, revenge, and power, and examining how these female offenders respond to the definitions of their crimes. The inquiry further interrogates whether Malayalam films treating crimes and the transgressions of women differ from those that deal with men. The study intends to examine how those images in contemporary Malayalam cinema reflect shifting cultural ideas concerning female power and morality through feminist film theory and narrative analysis.

Keywords: *Female antagonists, Malayalam cinema, crime, morality, power, feminist film theory*

UNMASKING THE FACE: POLITICAL FACE-WORK OF REGIONAL ACTORS THROUGH EMERGING FORMS OF MEDIA

Sourav Karthikeyan, Research scholar, Department of English and Cultural Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore. e-mail:sourav.karthikeyan@res.christuniversity.in

Arya Aiyappan, Associate Professor, Department of English and Cultural Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bangalore

Cinema and politics have been complementary and intertwined factors that impact each other in multiple ways. Using the expressive medium of cinema to forge political images of both individuals and parties in the Indian context has not been a very infrequent trend. Tamilnadu and, lately, Kerala have emerged as fertile grounds showcasing how cinema and media substantially influence the state and the national electoral demography. If in Tamilnadu, 'Dynasty politics' practised and propagated by political parties has shaped the state's socio-political fabric, then Kerala's strong rootedness in theatre and other vibrant art forms has steered its political contours across time. In this context, the political makeover of two eminent film actors from Tamil Nadu and Kerala, Udhayanidhi Stalin and Suresh Gopi, respectively, gain significance. Their foray into politics through cinema and other powerful forms of media have comfortably aided the acquisition of a political 'Face' to consolidate their electoral victories and subsequent course of action. Using Erving Goffman's concept of face-work as the positive self-image individuals utilise in interacting with others, the article probes into the political face-work deftly exercised by the two actors. The paper seeks to explore and understand the political makeover of these film artists by facilitating an 'Expressive order' to negotiate with their audiences and the general public using viable and popular media platforms. Analysing the specific content of their recent films and their stronghold on diverse media platforms helps make nuanced inroads into contemporary regional politics.

Keywords: *Cinema, Politics, Suresh Gopi, Udhayanidhi Stalin, Face-work*

UNITY, NATIONALISM, AND CONTROVERSY: A STUDY OF POLITICAL COMMUNICATION ON TWITTER BY INDIAN POLITICIANS DURING INDIA-PAKISTAN CRICKET ENCOUNTERS (2019-2024)

Spandan Khimani, Department of Media and Communication Studies, Christ (Deemed to be University), India. e-mail:khimanispandan.parthbhai@mames.christuniversity.in

The research evaluates how BJP and INC leaders exploited Indian cricket matches against Pakistan for political purposes from 2019 through 2024 by studying their social media posts. It highlights how sports events with high stakes create challenges for political narrative development while studying how these communications organize sentimental expressions alongside thematic structures and patriotic messages. The study measured political messages through content quantification and sentiment analysis as well as the identification of national narrative elements to examine leader engagement. Results show that BJP leaders structure their social media communications through religious and military narratives that stress national security interpretations and cultural essence by using nationalist hashtags and multimedia elements. INC leaders seek national integration through patriotic content combined with delicate visual approaches that avoid controversy. After achieving victories social media users from both parties exhibit jubilation but their posts become less festive after electoral losses. Research

shows political actors deliberately use cricket-based speech to achieve power benefits while positioning their beliefs as public preferences. The research focused on Twitter yet emphasizes that future studies should address high-stakes sports across multiple social media platforms because they drive political storytelling effects and the transformation of public perception in India.

Keywords: *Political narratives, social media analysis, cricket diplomacy, sentiment analysis, nationalism and patriotism*

EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES FOR SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHANGE

Sundresh K C, Assistant Professor & HOD, Department Of Sociology, Bharathi College (Autonomous), Bharathinagara. e-mail:sundreshgowda86@gmail.com

Effective communication is essential for driving socio-economic change by shaping public perceptions, mobilizing communities, and influencing policy decisions. Strategic communication raises awareness, encourages behavioral change, and supports policies that foster social and economic development. Through mass media, digital platforms, and participatory approaches, information is disseminated effectively, promoting engagement and collective action. Behavior Change Communication (BCC) applies psychological and sociological insights to encourage positive actions in areas such as public health, environmental conservation, and financial literacy, while policy advocacy and stakeholder engagement use research, storytelling, and case studies to inform decision-making and drive meaningful reforms. Culturally sensitive communication ensures messages resonate with diverse communities, fostering trust, inclusivity, and active participation, while crisis communication plays a vital role in managing uncertainty, combating misinformation, and guiding communities through challenges. By embracing these strategic communication approaches, governments, organizations, and communities can bridge gaps between challenges and solutions, fostering a more informed, engaged, and resilient society.

Keywords: *Mass Media, Participatory Communication, Behaviour Change Communication (BCC), Policy Advocacy, Crisis Communication*

THE IMPACT OF INTERNET AND DIGITAL MEDIA ON READING HABIT OF DEGREE STUDENTS

Suvarna Kambi, Assistant Professor, JSS College of Arts, Commerce and Science Ooty Road, Mysore, Karnataka, India. e-mail: suvarnakambi007@gmail.com

This study aims to investigate the effects of digital media and the internet on reading habits of degree students. The students' traditional reading habits have changed as a result of shifting workplace cultures and environments. Nowadays, students are searching for ways to read content electronically. It lessens the strain on the individual to continue visiting the library, and they can now read materials when travelling or relocating globally. Both digital and traditional libraries complement one another to satisfy the demands of different types of readers. Students from the younger generation occasionally like reading books online or responding to book

reviews because they believe that these are useful ways to encourage a love of reading. Numerous factors such as environment, subject matter, background, and age significantly impact the reading experience. Additionally, students are affected by contemporary technologies that have transformed functional activities across various aspects of life. The primary objectives of this research are to examine the influence of the internet and digital media on the reading habits of undergraduate students. The study will be take place at JSS College of Arts, Commerce and Science, located on Ooty Road in the Mysuru District of Karnataka. A survey methodology will be adopted for this study. A total of 40 students will be chosen from each academic program, including BA, B.Com, BCA, BSc, and B.Voc, resulting in a total of 200 degree students participating as respondents in the proposed research.

Keywords: *Digital Media, Internet, Digital libraries, Traditional libraries, Reading habits.*

UNDERSTANDING INFORMATION CONSUMPTION BEHAVIOUR AND MEDIA SELECTION AMONG MILLENNIAL AND GEN-X IN THE 21 ST ERA: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Swarnali Dutta, Supervisor – PR, Fortis Hospital Anandapur , Kolkata. e-mail:swarnalidutta.sdutta@gmail.com

Venugopal Gowda M K, HoD, Assistant Professor, Post Graduate and Research, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, St. Philomena's College (Autonomous), Mysuru, Karnataka. e-mail: venugopalgowdamk@stphilis.ac.n

The rapid evolution of communication technology in India has significantly transformed media consumption patterns, particularly among younger generations. With increasing internet penetration, digital platforms have become central to news consumption, yet traditional media such as television and newspapers continue to play a vital role. This study examines generational differences in media consumption behaviour, comparing Millennial and Generation X in their preferences for digital and traditional news sources. It also assesses satisfaction levels regarding development-related news coverage across various media platforms. The study employs a quantitative research design, surveying 200 respondents from both rural and urban areas of Mysore and Mandya districts using a structured questionnaire. Data were collected through a closed-ended questionnaire. A simple random sampling method was used to select respondents. Findings reveal that newspapers and television remain the most trusted sources of information. A majority of respondents prefer audio-visual content for news consumption, with a significant proportion favouring news in their mother tongue. Social media, while widely used, is perceived as the most misleading platform. Political news receives high media coverage, yet respondents express dissatisfaction with its portrayal. Development related news is perceived as neutral in terms of coverage and public engagement, whereas education-related news is considered under prioritized. Respondents demonstrate mixed opinions on sports and job-related news, showing neutral satisfaction levels. Entertainment news, in contrast, receives positive reception. Notably, religion-related news is perceived as receiving greater priority, while agriculture-related news is seen as underrepresented.

Keywords: *Millennial, Gen-X, Media Consumption, Generational Differences, TraditionalMedia, Digital Media, News Satisfaction*

LEGACY MEDIA: NAVIGATING THE CHALLENGE OF DISENGAGEMENT AND DISTRUST IN NEWS IN THE DIGITAL AGE

Swati Bakshi, Researcher (Independent), Centre for Research and Education in Art and Media (CREAM), University of Westminster, United Kingdom. e-mail: swatibakshi11@gmail.com

The question of trust in the news media has taken on unprecedented urgency in recent times, even though scholars have been studying various facets of trust in journalism for more than 80 years. It is interesting to note that, despite a long tradition of research on trust in news, it is almost impossible to emphasize a unified understanding of what exactly we mean when we talk about trust in news and how to rebuild it. This is a very clear indication that trust has a specific socio-cultural context in which news media operate and that it requires a variety of measures to earn people's trust. The declining public trust in the news media is visible in many transnational surveys and research reports, such as the Reuters Institute of Journalism Trust in News Report (2023), compiled from data collected in India, Brazil, the US and the UK. The report suggests that the 'trust problem' is a multifaceted and multi-layered issue. This paper brings together insights from various surveys, research articles and reports published between 2014-2024 to provide a discussion of the complexity of the idea of trust in news in different socio-cultural contexts. It explores arguments about why trust in news matters and perceptions about how people conceptualize the idea of a trustworthy news source. Finally, the paper identifies strategies and solutions that could help rebuild trust in legacy media in an increasingly cluttered digital environment where artificial intelligence poses a real threat to the objective, fair, and unbiased news and information that is essential for democratic citizenship.

Keywords: *Digital Media, Social Media, Trust in News, Artificial Intelligence, Legacy Media*

ANTI-HERO ATTRACTION AMONG KERALA'S YOUTH: ANALYSIS OF AAVESHAM

Syam C, M.A. Mass Communication, Department of Media and Communication, Central University of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavur. E-mail: syamc2000@gmail.com

Shamala R, Assistant professor, Department of media and communication, Central university of Tamil Nadu, Thiruvavur

Traditional stories that portray virtuous heroes have been challenged by the emergence of anti-heroes and ethically questionable figures in modern film. Through an analysis of the Malayalam film Aavesham, this study investigates the phenomenon of Kerala youth's preference for negative-shade protagonists. The study focuses on the protagonist's character development since his unethical actions are depicted in a complex and interesting manner, evoking admiration from a large audience. Here the researcher used the qualitative descriptive method in in-depth interviews. And used moral engagement theory to analyze the individual data. In this partially fulfilled research study, the majority of respondents recognized the significance of differentiating on-screen behavior from real-life principles and saw the protagonist's acts as entirely fictional.

Keywords: *Anti-hero enjoyment, Moral disengagement, Malayalam movie, Affective disposition theory, Thematic analysis*

THE ROLE OF NEW MEDIA IN CULTURAL HYBRIDIZATION: TRANSFORMING LIFESTYLES

Tamizhanban R M, Ph.D Scholar, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Abishekpatti Tirunelveli - 627012. Tamil Nadu India. e-mail tamizhanban1721@gmail.com

The advent of new media has revolutionized the way cultures interact, leading to unprecedented levels of cultural hybridization. This phenomenon has profound implications for lifestyles, as individuals increasingly blend traditional practices with global influences. This study explores the role of new media in facilitating cultural hybridization and its impact on lifestyle transformations. By examining this, the research aims to provide insights into the complex dynamics of cultural hybridization and its effects on modern lifestyles.

Keywords: *New media, cultural hybridization, lifestyle, globalization.*

EXPLORING THE ROLE OF ONLINE PLATFORMS IN BUILDING LEARNING COMMUNITIES: A CASE STUDY OF KRISHNA KANTA HANDIQUI STATE OPEN UNIVERSITY

Trisha Dowerah Baruah, Assistant Professor, Bhupen Hazarikia School of Mass Communication, Krishna Kanta Handiqui State Open University, Guwahati, Assam. e-mail: trishabaruah@kkhsou.in

The rapid expansion of online platforms has significantly influenced the dynamics of Open and Distance Learning (ODL), particularly in fostering learning communities that transcend geographical boundaries. This study explores the role of online platforms in building and sustaining learning communities within the context of Krishna Kanta Handiqui State Open University (KKHSOU), a prominent institution in India's ODL landscape. Through a mixed-methods approach, the research investigates how digital tools and virtual environments facilitate collaboration, engagement, and knowledge-sharing among learners and educators. Data would be collected through surveys, interviews, and analysis of online interactions to assess the effectiveness of these platforms in creating a sense of community and enhancing the learning experience. Preliminary investigation reveals that online platforms play a pivotal role in promoting peer-to-peer interaction, reducing isolation, and supporting self-directed learning. However, challenges such as digital literacy, access to technology, and the need for structured facilitation were also identified. The study is expected to introspect on optimizing the use of online platforms to strengthen learning communities in ODL systems and emphasizing the importance of inclusive design, institutional support, and continuous engagement strategies. This research would contribute to the growing body of knowledge on technology-enhanced learning and provides insights for ODL institutions aiming to leverage digital tools for community building. The study would also identify challenges and areas for improvement, including the need for faculty training on technology integration, infrastructure development, and digital literacy programs for students. The findings of this study is expected to contribute to the existing body of knowledge on technology-enhanced learning, highlighting the potential of technology to transform the learning experience in open and distance learning institutions.

Keywords: *Online platforms, learning communities, ICT, Open and Distance Learning(ODL), Krishna Kanta Handiqui State Open University, digital engagement, collaborative Learning*

SELECTIVE USE OF DIGITAL MEDIA TECHNOLOGY FOR LIFE AND LIVING, ON NOMADIC COMMUNITIES STUDY ON INTRAVENOUS AND EXTRANEIOUS FACTORS CONTRIBUTING TO SELECTIVE USE OF TECHNOLOGY AMONG NARIKURAVAR COMMUNITY

V.Venkatesh, Doctoral Research Scholar, Department of Communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli-627011, Tamilnadu. e-mail: venkatvijaykumar05@gmail.com

Gnana D Hans, Assistant professor, Department of communication, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli-627011, Tamilnadu.

The internet and smart phones are making communication easier in present times, while artificial intelligence and online learning are improving access to knowledge related data bases. It is argued collectively that technological innovation in communication would transform or change individuals in the society and their communities towards the trajectory of technological development. Even though not all communication researchers and scholars may agree with actualize with technological determinism that facilitate large scale development, there is a trivial scope of selective transformation. The problem of selective transformation was analysed among the Narikuravar community, a nomadic group in Tamil Nadu, was officially recognized as a Scheduled Tribe in 2023. Their lifestyle involves frequent movement, which makes it difficult for them to access education, healthcare, and stable jobs. Though some younger generations are now interested in education, they still struggle with social stigma and lack of resources. government and NGOs have started programs to support these communities with education and skills training. Efforts have been made to provide permanent settlements, but many Narikuravars still maintain their nomadic lifestyle while trying to adapt to modernization. It is observed that amidst pervasiveness of digital applications and appliances, individuals employ these technological innovations for certain aspects of the life. The selective engagement of the digital media is not facilitated through any agencies. This paper attempts to understand the selective use of digital media and its impact on their life and livelihood.

Keywords: *Digital Media, Communities, Intraneous, Extraneous*

AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON VOICE ASSISTANTS TECHNOLOGY IN DIGITAL PAYMENT APPS: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY AMONG RETAIL MERCHANTS IN BANGALORE

Vamsha Shetty A, Ph.D. Research scholar, Department of Electronic Media, Bangalore University, Bangalore. e-mail: vamshashetty0103@gmail.com

Vahini Aravind, Associate Professor, Department of Electronic Media, Bangalore University. Bangalore. e-mail: vahinias@gmail.com

Digital payment apps have brought about a revolution in the way transactions occur in our day-to-day lives. United Payment interfaces, such as BHIM, Phonepe, and Google Pay, provide a platform for users to send and receive money instantly. Integrating AI-based voice assistant technology into digital payment apps has emerged as a transformative innovation in the financial sector. This cross-sectional study examined the impact and prospects of voice- activated payment systems across genders, educational backgrounds focusing on their ability to enhance

user experience, increase transaction efficiency, and improve accessibility. By harnessing advanced natural language processing, voice assistants facilitate seamless interactions between users and payment platforms, enabling the consumer to know how much

money they have received through an instant voice note once the transaction ends. This not only streamlines the payment process, but also caters to individuals who are illiterate, technology laggards, and people with disabilities, thus promoting inclusivity. The objective of this research is to understand the perceptions of different age groups. In addition, the benefits of incorporating and mapping voice assistant technology among consumers in using digital payment apps. To understand the gratification factors of digital payment apps with voice assistance capabilities. This research also employs a quantitative method approach. The questionnaire will be used to collect data from 136 retail merchants from different sections of society in Bangalore. This study will contribute to the future expansion of digital payment apps in terms of user-friendliness and safety features.

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, natural language processing, voice assistance, digital payment apps, Technology.*

A TYPOLOGY OF THE ROLES ASSIGNED TO CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANISATIONS AS NEWS SOURCES

Varsha M. Joseph, PhD Scholar, Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru. e-mail: varsha.joseph@res.christuniversity.in

Aasita Bali, Associate Professor, Department of Media Studies, CHRIST (Deemed to be University), Bengaluru. e-mail: aasita.bali@christuniversity.in

Climate change is a global as well as a local issue that affects everyone simultaneously. The media plays an important role in communicating about climate change. In the present times, where opportunities to produce and consume media content are greater than ever, the authenticity of content is very important. This is especially so in the case of news stories, given that fake news and misinformation are on the rise. The print media has long been considered a credible source of news and information. This credibility stems, at least partly, from its rigorous process of verifying facts and information from trustworthy sources. The sources quoted in a news story add to its authenticity. Civil society organisations (CSOs) are important sources of information in the context of climate change news. They are marked by diversity, as the focus area of one CSO can differ from another while the same CSO may focus on multiple aspects of climate change. This diversity is likely to be reflected in how they are quoted as news sources as well. The present study aims to identify the types of roles that are assigned to CSOs as news sources in stories on climate change. Using purposive sampling, climate change-related news articles would be selected from mainstream English-language Indian newspapers. The news articles would then be thematically analysed to inductively create a typology of the roles assigned to CSOs as news sources. Such a typology is expected to help future researchers understand the linkage between the focus of a climate change news story and the CSO news sources that are quoted.

Keywords: *Climate change communication, civil society organisations, news sources, media*

THE POWER PLAY: POLITICAL INFLUENCE AND THE EROSION OF MEDIA FREEDOM

G Vasanth, Associate Professor & Head, Department of Visual Communication, D G Vaishnav College, Tamil Nadu. e-mail: drvasanthgopal@gmail.com

Media is essential for a democratic society, enabling informed public debate and holding those in power accountable. However, the concentration of media ownership among political entities can undermine the principles of free speech. This paper scrutinizes the impact of political control over media on journalistic independence, leading to biased reporting, suppression of dissent, and the deterioration of democratic values. By analyzing contemporary case studies, especially in regions with notable declines in press freedom, this study delves into how political ownership shapes editorial decisions, narrative construction, and public opinion. Political ownership of media appears in various forms, such as direct state control, ownership by political affiliates, or corporations with political interests. This results in the systematic silencing of opposition, selective information dissemination, and the manipulation of public opinion to favour the ruling party's ideology. Investigative journalism, crucial for democratic accountability, often faces stifling due to fears of legal repercussions, censorship, and economic pressure from politically motivated advertisers. Consequently, the media transitions from a watchdog role to a propaganda tool, reducing its function as the fourth pillar of democracy. The influence of political-media connections is particularly visible during elections, policy debates, and crises, where narratives are shaped to favour incumbents and discredit opponents. The digital age has further complicated this scenario, with governments controlling not just traditional media but also online platforms through regulatory mechanisms. Techniques like algorithmic manipulation, state-sponsored disinformation, and targeted censorship have worsened the lack of diversity in public discourse. This paper contends that restoring journalistic independence requires a multi-faceted approach, including regulatory safeguards against media consolidation, the promotion of independent public service broadcasting, and stronger protections for press freedom. Global watchdog organizations, civil society, and alternative digital platforms play pivotal roles in countering political control over media. By fostering a diverse and independent media ecosystem, democracies can ensure the protection of free expression and empower citizens with accurate and unbiased information necessary for informed decision-making.

Keywords: *Media Ownership, Press Freedom, Political Influence, Censorship, Democracy*

CULTURAL HYBRIDIZATION AND COMMUNICATION TRENDS IN OTT PLATFORMS: AN OBSERVATION

Hemalatha R., Assistant Professor, DOSR in Journalism and Mass Communication, Karnataka State Open University, Mysore-06. e-mail: nallahalli.1@gmail.com

Vidyashree C. Halkerimath, Research Scholar, DOSR in Journalism and Mass Communication, Karnataka State Open University, Mysore-06. e-mail: vidyahalakerimath@gmail.com,

In India, the rise of Over-the-Top (OTT) platforms has significantly transformed the media landscape, contributing to cultural hybridization and reshaping communication trends. Platforms like Netflix, Amazon Prime, Disney+ Hotstar, and regional services such as ZEE5 and

SonyLiv have become central to the Indian entertainment ecosystem, offering a diverse array of content that blends local narratives with global influences. This has led to a fusion of

cultural elements, where regional traditions, languages, and storytelling techniques merge with international formats, creating content that appeals to a broad, diverse audience. OTT platforms in India facilitate the exchange of both traditional and modern cultural expressions, allowing for localized versions of global content and vice versa. Bollywood films, web series, and regional content are now being tailored for international audiences, while Western content is being adapted to resonate with Indian viewers. This cultural hybridization highlights the dynamic nature of India & media consumption, where global and local cultural products coexist and enrich each other. Above all OTT platforms have redefined communication trends in India, offering on-demand, personalized viewing experiences. The growing demand for diverse genres, languages, and content in multiple regional languages has given rise to niche audiences. This shift is reshaping how Indians engage with entertainment, creating new avenues for cultural exchange and influencing the way media is consumed. This paper explores the role of OTT platforms in driving cultural hybridization and influencing communication trends in India, highlighting the impact of digital media on Indian entertainment and cultural dynamics.

Key Words: *OTT Platforms, Cultural Hybridization, Communication Trends, India*

INDIAN CINEMA AND HEGEMONY: AN ANALYSIS OF LABOUR NARRATIVES IN POST-COLONIAL INDIA

Vikas Pathe, Symbiosis International (Deemed University), Pune, India, e-mail: vikas@gmail.com

Cinema has long served as a prominent medium of visual engagement within Indian society. Rather than merely documenting social events or depicting alternate worlds, cinema represents a meticulously constructed product of industrial and economic power dynamics. It transcends the viewers & lived experiences, reflecting and shaping the evolving socio-political landscape. In the Indian context, particularly Hindi films provide a foundation to comprehend the legitimization of socio-political power through narratives that resonate with diverse social groups. These films have intricately crafted historical narratives of the Indian nation, emerging as a potent vehicle for bourgeois hegemony. Although multiple studies indicate a tendency of Hindi cinema to favor the dominant bourgeois class and caste, there remains a notable lack of discourse on the representation of labor within Hindi cinema. By analysing selected Hindi films in the neoliberal post-independence era, this discussion aims to explore the relationship between cinema and cultural hegemony through the lens of labour narratives. Utilizing Gramsci's concept of & hegemony, & it seeks to examine the evolving role of Hindi cinema within the broader context of capitalist development. Furthermore, it investigates how Hindi cinema contributes to sustaining and perpetuating unchallenged capitalist exploitation.

Keywords: *Cultural Hegemony, Hindi Cinema, Labour, Neoliberal, Post-colonial India*

ANALYZING THE DEVELOPMENT OF A RESILIENT FACT-CHECKING ECOSYSTEM: UNDERSTANDING COLLABORATIVE APPROACHES TO FACT-CHECKING FOR ANALYZING EFFORTS TO COMBAT INFORMATION WARFARE

Y Sravan Kumar, Research Scholar, IGNOU, New Delhi. e-mail: ssravan.mahi@gmail.com

Glen D'Silva, Research Scholar, Mahindra University, Hyderabad, Telangana.

In an era characterized by rapid information dissemination and the pervasive threat of misinformation, establishing a robust fact-checking ecosystem is essential for safeguarding democratic processes and societal integrity. This research proposal aims to explore the systemic integration of fact-checking processes and procedures as a proactive approach to counter information warfare at the state or national level. By investigating the roles of various stakeholders—including media organizations, technology companies, and governmental bodies—this study seeks to develop a comprehensive framework that enhances the efficacy of fact-checking initiatives. The findings will contribute to understanding how a cohesive ecosystem can mitigate the adverse effects of misinformation and strengthen public trust in information sources.

Keywords: *Fact-checking, eco-system, information warfare, misinformation, stakeholders*

Organizing Committee

Organizing Committee		Rector
1) Conference Chief Patrons	Rev Dr. Lourdu Prasad Joseph Dr. Ravi J.D. Saldanha	Principal
2) Advisory Committee	Rev.Fr. Gnana Pragasam Rev. Fr. David Sagayaraj Mr.M Nagaraj Urs Mr. Ronald Prakash Cutinha Mr. A Thomas Gunaseelan Dr. Noor Mubasheer C.A Dr. Venugopal Gowda M K Dr. Vagdevi H.S	Campus Administrator Assistant to Rector Vice Principal (Academic) Vice Principal (Administration) IQAC Coordinator PG Coordinator HoD, MA Journalism Assistant Professor Dept. of MA Journalism
3) Conveners	Dr. Raviraj I Vadigeri Mr. Ravithej S.P Mr. Sanju T S Dr. Yamuna B Raj	Assistant Professor Dept. of B.voc Assistant Professor Dept. of MA Journalism Assistant Professor Dept. of MA Journalism Assistant Professor UG Dept of Journalism
4) Co- Conveners	Mr. Raviraj I Vadigeri Mr. Ravithej S.P Mr. Sanju T S Dr. Yamuna B Raj	Assistant Professor Dept. of B.voc Assistant Professor Dept. of MA Journalism Assistant Professor Dept. of MA Journalism Assistant Professor UG Dept of Journalism
5) Conference Kit arrangement	a) Guest b) Participants c) Students (From college)	HoD, Dept. of B.voc 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year B. Voc 1st Year B. Voc
6) Travel	Mr.Francis Devasahayam B . Prajwal Vaishnavi P Nandini S V Rithesh KatteKodi	HOD, Dept. of Criminology and Forensic Science 2nd Year MA Journalism 1st Year MA Journalism 1st Year B. Voc 1st Year B. Voc
7) Accommodation Committee	Dr. Venugopal Gowda M K (HOD) Dr. Vagdevi H. S Dr. Yamuna B Raj Prajwal Vaishnavi P Nandini Brinda S	Assistant Professor Dept. of MA Journalism Assistant Professor Dept. of MA Journalism Assistant Professor, UG Dept of Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism 1st Year MA Journalism 1st Year B. Voc 1st Year MA Journalism

Organizing Committee

8)	Registration Committee	a) Outside participants b) within the college registration	Mr. Raviraj I Vadigera Lhakpa Dolma Sristi Chakma Mehrin Taj Rajath Rane	HoD, Dept. of B.Voc 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year B. Voc UG Final Year Journalism
9)	Venue/Stage committee	a) Inauguration (Indoor Stadium) b) Plenary Sessions (MBA Conference Hall) c) Paper Presentation (3-4 Class Room) d) Online Paper Presentation	Dr. Venugopal Gowda M K Dr. Vagdevi H. S Dr. Sowmya P Ms. Soumya Shree Ms. Rashmi Vincia Siddartha Maiya Girish R Sowmya C H Dikshitha C Razia Mahdis	HOD, MA Journalism Assistant Professor, Dept. of MA Journalism Assistant Professor Dept. of Sociology Assistant Professor Dept. of Economics Assistant Professor Dept. of sociology MA 1st year Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism MA 1st year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism
10)	Food Committee	a) Guest and outsiders participants b) College Students food	Dr Nandeesh H K Dr.Ginson George Siddartha maiya Tsering Tenzin Nandini Soumya C H Nidhi Y	HoD, Dept. of MA Economics HoD, Dept. of Psychology MA 1st year Journalism 2nd Year B. Voc B. Voc, 1st year MA 1st year Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism
11)	Hospitality Committee	a) Paper Presentation venue b) hospitality c) Plenary Session d) Sanitation/ Hygienic Tissues and Water Bottles	Dr. Ashwini K J Ms. Namitha Jois K S Sanika B Keerthana Pal Parveen Banu	Assistant Professor, Dept. of Economics Assistant Professor, Dept. of Economics 2nd Year MA Journalism B. Voc, 1st year 2nd Year B. Voc

Organizing Committee

12)	Technical Committee	a) Audio and Video, Zoom, Projector, YouTube, Internet	<p>Mr. Sanju TS Mr. Martin Mr. Swaminathan Mr. John Joshua J Anthony Rithesh Kottekodi Manas S P (B. Voc, 1st year) Prakash Naik M Bharath S Jaswanth Singh MP V Kiran Sagar D Moger Afnan Pasha</p>	<p>Assistant Professor, Dept. of MA Journalism Technical Staff Technical Staff Technical Staff B. Voc, 1st year B. Voc, 1st year 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism UG Final Year Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism MA 1st year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism</p>
13)	Certificate Committee	a) Physical (Coordination with Registration Committee) and online	<p>Mr. Raviraj I Vadigera Ms. Reena Joice Yeshi Dorji Pratiksha Chettri Mohamod Shah Ulfat Vaishnavi S Patil</p>	<p>Assistant Professor, HoD, B. Voc Assistant Professor, Dept. MA English 2nd Year MA Journalism B. Voc, 2nd year MA 1st year Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism</p>
14)	Documentation Committee	a) Photos, Videos, Reports, Feedback	<p>Mr. Ravithej S P Dilsha Shaji Meghna Madhu Sneha Jaswant Singh MP Siddharth Maiya Prajawal Deekshitha C</p>	<p>Assistant Professor, Dept. of MA Journalism MA 1st year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism UG Final Year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism MA 1st year Journalism</p>
15)	Publicity Committee	a) Online and Offline Publicity	<p>Dr. Yamuna B Raj Vaishnavi S Patil Rithesh Kottekodi Lhakpa Dolma Afnan Pasha Bharath S Manasa S P Adarsh A</p>	<p>Assistant Professor, Dept. of Journalism UG 2nd Year MA Journalism B. Voc, 1st year 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalis MA 1st year Journalis B. Voc, 1st year B. Voc, 1st year</p>

Organizing Committee

16)	Cultural Night Committee		Dr. Nandini Dr. Ashwini K J Keerthana PB	Assistant Professor, Dept. of Chemistry Assistant Professor, Dept. of Economics UG Final Year Journalism
17)	Invitation and Banners	a) Invitation (Inauguration, Cultural Night, and Valedictory) b) Scheduled Print (Paler Presentation, Plenary) c) Banners (Main Gate, PG indoor Stadium), Text St. Joseph College Video LED Screen. d) Backdrops Indoor Stadium e) Panellist Digital Banner f) Certificate Design g) Session Conference Digital Backdrops h) Book Front page back design i) ID cards for our students, Participants, Guests, Organizer	Mr. Raviraj I Vadigera Sanju T S Joshiva J Anthony Prakash Naik M Nidhi Y V Kiran Rithesh Kottekodi Parveen Banu Meharin Taj Siddharth Maiya Prajwal Afnan Pasha	HoD, B.Voc Assistant Professor, Dept. of MA Journalism B. Voc, 1st year 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism B. Voc, 2nd year B. Voc, 2nd year B. Voc, 2nd year MA 1st year Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalis MA 1st year Journalism
18)	MC Committee	➤ Inauguration ➤ Plenary Session ➤ Paper Presentation ➤ Cultural Night ➤ Valedictory	Dr. Vagdevi H. S Ms. Nidhi V Gummadi Ms. Joseph Ashwin Jeyakanthan Ms. Sahana R Vaishnavi S Patil Lhakpa Dolma, Monika Keerthana PB Afnan Pasha Sristi Chakma Razia Mahdis Nidhi Y Tsering Tenzin Hussaina Taher Nandini Deni	Assistant Professor, Dept. of MA Journalism Assistant Professor, Dept. of MA English Assistant Professor, Dept. Criminology And Forensic science Announcer and News Reader at AIR 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalis B. Voc, 2nd year UG Final Year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism B. Voc, 2nd year

Organizing Committee

			<p>Keerthana pal, Sagar D Moger, Vaishnavi. P, Dilsha Shaji Meghna Madhu Parveen Banu</p>	<p>B. Voc, 1st year UG Final Year Journalism B. Voc, 1st year MA 1st year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism B. Voc, 2nd year</p>
19)	Finance Committee	<p>a) Honorarium Receipts Signature b) Traveling Bill Collection c) Hotel Bill</p>	Mr. Ravithej S P V Kiran	<p>Assistant Professor, Dept. of MA Journalism 2nd Year MA Journalism</p>
20)	Publication Committee	<p>a) Proceeding book (Online and Hard Copy) b) Principal Message, Rector Message, From the Organizing Committee</p>	<p>Dr. Venugopal Gowda M K Dr. Vagdevi H. S Dr. Sowmya P Ms. Niranjana Husena Taher Noorain Fathima Noor Saba</p>	<p>HoD, MA journalism Assistant Professor, Dept. of MA Journalism Assistant Professor Dept. of Sociology Assistant Professor, UG Dept. of Psychology UG Final Year Journalism UG Final Year Journalism UG Final Year Journalism</p>
21)	Philo's Bulletin	<p>a) Reporting b) Editing c) Photograph</p>	Dr. Yamuna B Raj	<p>Assistant Professor, UG Dept. of Journalism B. Voc & BA Journalism Students</p>
22)	Discipline committee		<p>Dr. Praveen Saldanha Dr. Ginson George Noorain Fathima Soumya C H Sagar D Moger</p>	<p>Dean of Arts And HoD of Economics UG Assistant Professor, Dept. of Psychology UG Final Year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism MA 1st year Journalism</p>

About the Department

The Department of Journalism and Mass Communication at St. Philomena's College is a hub of academic and professional excellence. Established in 1996 with an undergraduate program, it has grown into a thriving centre for media education, launching its postgraduate program in 2013. Recognized as a research centre by the University of Mysore in 2019, the department emphasizes research-oriented and industry-driven learning. Through its undergraduate and postgraduate programs, it equips students with the skills and knowledge required to excel in the rapidly evolving media landscape. The department fosters critical thinking, innovation, and ethical practices, shaping future-ready media professionals and scholars who contribute meaningfully to society. In 2015, the department introduced the B.Voc in Media and Entertainment program, a specialized undergraduate course designed to align with current trends in the media industry and adapt to evolving communication technologies.

Book Name : Book of Abstracts
ISBN Number : 978-93-342-4858-6